

HCXAI

HUMAN-CENTERED EXPLAINABLE AI

Proceedings of the 5th HCXAI Workshop @ CHI

**New Frontiers of Human-centered Explainable AI (HCXAI):
Participatory Civic AI, Benchmarking LLMs, XAI,
Hallucinations, and Responsible AI Audits**

CHI 2025

April 26–May 1, 2025 in Yokohama, Japan

Explainable AI (XAI) is more than just “opening” the black box — who opens it matters just as much, if not more, than the ways of opening it. Human-centered XAI (HCXAI) advocates that algorithmic transparency alone is insufficient to make AI explainable. In our fifth CHI workshop on Human-Centered XAI (HCXAI), we shift our focus to new, emerging frontiers of explainability: (1) participatory approaches toward explainability in civic AI applications; (2) addressing hallucinations in LLMs using explainability benchmarks; (3) connecting HCXAI research with Responsible AI practices, algorithmic auditing, and public policy; and (4) improving the representation of XAI issues from the Global South. We have built a strong community of HCXAI researchers through our workshop series, whose work has made an important conceptual, methodological, and technical impact on the field. In this installment, we will push the frontiers of work in HCXAI, emphasizing the operationalization of sociotechnical perspectives.

2025 marks a special year for the organizers of HCXAI @CHI, since this workshop series has now been held for half a decade. In 2020, we argued that explainable AI must put more focus on end users and various stakeholders, and that we should work together to systematically operationalize and standardize methods and measurements to be used in this emerging field of human factors research. In some years, HCXAI was the most attended workshop at the CHI conference, and we are especially happy that our focus on online and hybrid engagement was welcomed even after the end of the pandemic.

Nevertheless, the last two years have also highlighted potential struggles of our community. In particular, the AI field is changing and moving fast, and new AI tools such as transformer models impose new requirements on XAI, while the issues emerging from previous model generations have still not been fully resolved. At the same time, AI systems are increasingly implemented in the real world, with all the consequences.

At HCXAI 2025, we aim to address these developments in our program. Again, we have a heterogeneous program consisting of a main event (Who Speaks, Who Listens: The Dialogues We Need in Explainable AI, with Mary L. Gray, Maryam Ashoori, and Jacob Metcalf), four paper sessions to present recent research, as well as group work for community building.

We hope you have a great workshop experience with us in Yokohama, Japan!

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Towards Explainable AI for Government Workers

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Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) is crucial for ensuring transparency, fairness, and accountability in AI-driven decision-making within government institutions. Unlike AI in commercial or healthcare settings, government AI systems operate in a unique regulatory and political environment where decisions impact millions of citizens, influence public trust, and shape democratic governance. However, the lack of explainability in government AI raises serious concerns, as opaque systems can be weaponized to undermine civil service integrity, manipulate decision-making, and erode public accountability. Therefore, AI can serve as a tool to improve democratic governance or as an instrument for obfuscating accountability. Given the high stakes of government AI, ranging from national security to social services, explainability is not merely a technical requirement but a foundational necessity for ensuring ethical and effective governance. A world where government AI is truly explainable is one where civil servants can confidently use AI-driven insights without fear of blindly following algorithmic recommendations. It is a world where policymakers can critically evaluate AI-assisted decisions rather than deferring to black-box models. Most importantly, it is a world where citizens retain their agency, knowing that decisions affecting their lives are made with fairness, accountability, and the possibility for appeal. Without clear and interpretable AI systems, we risk replacing human expertise with unchecked automation, weakening democratic oversight, and allowing powerful actors to manipulate AI for personal or political gain. This paper argues for the urgent need to develop XAI frameworks specifically tailored for government workers. We examine how government AI differs from other domains, why most existing XAI research fails to address these challenges, and how new frameworks can mitigate the risks of algorithmic opacity in public institutions. By prioritizing explainability, we ensure that AI serves the people, rather than the other way around, safeguarding ethical decision-making, maintaining the legitimacy of public institutions, and building a future where AI strengthens, rather than undermines, the democratic process.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: XAI, public sector, government AI, explainability, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170506

1 INTRODUCTION

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) is essential for ensuring transparency, fairness, and accountability in AI-driven decision-making. While extensive research has explored XAI in commercial, healthcare, and consumer applications, its role in government settings remains mostly underexamined. Government workers interact with AI in a unique regulatory, data, and operational environment, requiring a distinct approach to XAI that aligns with public accountability, legal constraints, and ethical considerations [1–4].

The need for XAI in government is particularly urgent given the rise of politicized attacks on expertise and institutional knowledge. As public agencies increasingly integrate AI into decision-making processes, a lack of transparency can fuel distrust, manipulation, and outright abuse of power. Recent examples, such as politically motivated dismissals of government experts [16], highlight how opaque AI systems can serve as tools for undermining civil service and democratic accountability. As noted in analyses of anti-expertise movements [10, 17], efforts to delegitimize professionals often stem not from genuine concerns about efficiency, but from ideological agendas and attempts to consolidate power among elites. Without robust explainability, AI risks becoming an instrument of political and corporate influence rather than an aid for effective governance.

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In addition, modern government AI systems are deployed in high-stakes environments, such as defense, social services, and public health, where algorithmic opacity can have disastrous consequences. Biased or poorly understood AI-driven decisions have already contributed to wrongful arrests, unfair benefit allocations, and national security breaches [9, 10]. Government AI directly impacts millions of citizens, making its interpretability a matter of public interest and democratic integrity. The erosion of trust in experts, combined with the rise of AI as a tool of governance, highlight why explainability is not just a technical issue but a foundational requirement for maintaining public trust in democratic institutions.

This paper argues for the urgent need to develop XAI frameworks specifically for government workers. We outline how government AI systems differ from those in other domains, why existing XAI research has not fully addressed these challenges, and why a new research agenda is necessary [1, 2, 5–7]. Without explainable AI, the weaponization of opacity in governance will continue, eroding both the effectiveness of government agencies and the democratic norms they are meant to uphold.

2 UNIQUE DEMANDS AND CONSTRAINTS OF GOVERNMENT EXPLAINABILITY

2.1 Government AI Systems Operate in High-Stakes, Regulatory-Heavy Environments

In contrast to AI in private industry, government AI systems operate under strict legal and regulatory constraints. Decisions made by these systems impact citizens' rights, social services, law enforcement, and national security, making explainability critical for public trust and compliance.

Existing research in HCXAI [1] highlights the importance of power dynamics and structural inequalities in AI systems. In government settings, these dynamics are heightened due to the power asymmetry between the state and its citizens. If AI systems deployed in government remain opaque, they risk amplifying existing inequalities and eroding public confidence in institutions [9, 13].

2.2 Government Data Environments Are More Complex and Sensitive

Government AI relies on heterogeneous, sensitive, and high-volume datasets, integrating information from sources such as criminal records, tax filings, healthcare data, and citizen profiles. This differs from commercial AI systems, which typically use structured, proprietary datasets [8].

A key challenge lies in the fact that many government AI models rely on incomplete or biased data. As discussed in [9], AI models can perpetuate algorithmic biases due to flawed training datasets. When government AI is used in high-stakes applications such as criminal sentencing, fraud detection, and immigration processing, algorithmic bias can have life-altering consequences [2]. While errors in private-sector AI might lead to financial losses or product inefficiencies, failures in government AI can lead to:

- Wrongful arrests and discriminatory policing due to biased law enforcement algorithms.
- Denial of critical social services caused by flawed AI-based fraud detection.
- Threats to national security when AI errors compromise intelligence assessments.

2.3 The Need for Multi-Stakeholder Explainability

Government AI systems require different levels of explainability:

- **For Government Workers:** AI models must generate interpretable outputs to allow human decision-making rather than blind reliance on AI recommendations.

- **For Policymakers:** Decision-makers need to understand AI operations to ensure they align with policy goals and legal standards.
- **For the Public:** Citizens must be able to contest AI-driven decisions, necessitating transparent and user-friendly explanations.

Prior work in HCXAI [1] argues for participatory approaches in XAI to ensure tailored explanations for different user groups. This is particularly relevant for government applications, where non-technical users (e.g., judges, social workers) must critically assess AI-driven recommendations.

2.4 The Threat of AI-Induced Public Distrust

A growing anti-expertise movement fueled by political and ideological interests has contributed to public skepticism toward government institutions [10]. Opaque AI systems only exacerbate this problem by reinforcing the perception that government decisions are made in secrecy, without public accountability. Government AI systems should not only be transparent but also empower citizens to understand and contest AI-generated decisions. Without XAI, the public may perceive AI-driven governance as unfair, arbitrary, or politically motivated.

3 LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT XAI RESEARCH

Although work in Feminist XAI [1] and Conversational XAI [2] has explored broader user needs, current XAI research largely focuses on commercial, consumer, and healthcare applications, prioritizing technical interpretability for AI engineers rather than end-users in bureaucratic and policy-driven environments [9]. Scholars have begun to examine XAI applications in government contexts [11–15]; however, existing studies have not fully addressed some key aspects necessary for effective XAI adoption in bureaucratic settings. Key gaps in existing XAI research include:

- **Lack of Context-Sensitive XAI for Bureaucratic Decision-Making:** Government AI often involves administrative rules, legal interpretations, and case-by-case discretion, requiring XAI models that incorporate these contextual factors.
- **Insufficient Focus on Public Accountability:** Most XAI research prioritizes technical explainability (e.g., feature importance, model interpretability) over explainability in terms of legal reasoning and ethical considerations. Additionally, government AI systems lack clear mechanisms to assign responsibility when errors occur. Legal implications and accountability mechanisms should be considered in the design of XAI systems.
- **Limited Exploration of Multi-User Explainability:** A key challenge in XAI research is the limited attention to the diverse user base within government agencies, where multiple layers of decision-making—from caseworkers to agency directors to legislators—require adaptive explanation models. The majority of existing approaches do not adequately address the varying levels of technical and domain expertise found across these roles.
- **Neglect of Cultural Adaptation:** XAI frameworks tend to ignore cultural diversity in government settings, assuming universal norms across different population groups both between countries and within a given society. As a result, there is a risk that policies may be disregarded due to cultural mismatches, or worse, that they may reinforce dominant cultural norms and exacerbate inequalities.
- **Insufficient Focus on Human Capacity Gaps:** Existing tools rarely address the training needs of policymakers or public literacy barriers. Non-technical government workers require training to understand AI outputs and prevent misuse, while citizens need not only clear explanations, but also a basic understanding of how AI informs policy in order to trust the system.

- **Resistance to Automation:** XAI research assumes adoption readiness, ignoring bureaucratic inertia and fear of automation. However, government workers may reject AI tools if they are perceived as threats to their expertise or job security, and may distrust AI recommendations, especially in high-stakes areas like law enforcement.

4 FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA FOR EXPLAINABLE AI IN GOVERNMENT

AI should empower government workers to make more informed, fair, and efficient decisions while maintaining human oversight. Based on these ideas, we argue for the need of a new agenda in Explainable AI.

4.1 Legal and Policy-Aware Explainability

Since government AI implementations are fundamentally constrained by comprehensive legal frameworks and regulatory requirements, AI-driven decisions in the public sector must be interpretable in ways that align with legal principles such as due process and non-discrimination [9]. Future research on XAI for government workers should focus on:

- Developing legally compliant AI explanations that align with constitutional rights, administrative law, and public policy.
- Ensuring fairness and non-discrimination by making AI decision-making auditable and contestable.
- Designing AI explanations that stand up to legal challenges, ensuring that automated decisions do not violate civil liberties.

4.2 Multi-Stakeholder Explainability

To address the lack of exploration in multilevel explainability, future studies should investigate:

- How can AI explanations be designed to serve both technical experts and non-technical decision-makers?
- What are the most effective methods for presenting AI-generated explanations to the general public in a transparent and accessible way?
- How can participatory approaches be used to co-design explainable AI systems with government workers and citizens?

4.3 Bias Mitigation and Ethical AI Governance

Due to the severe consequences government AI can have on millions of citizens [3, 8], XAI research must focus on ensuring that explanations help uncover and mitigate bias in decision-making. Key research questions include:

- How can explainability techniques be used to detect and reduce bias in AI-driven government decisions?
- What role does algorithmic transparency play in mitigating public distrust of government AI?
- How can ethical AI governance frameworks be designed to ensure fairness and accountability in government AI?

4.4 Measuring the Impact of XAI in Government

Government XAI must be measured based on public trust, fairness, and legal compliance [2]. Therefore, it is essential to move beyond commercial metrics and develop government-specific methods to assess the impact of XAI in public service. New studies should formulate:

- Methods to ensure decision-makers fully understand policy recommendations and their potential consequences.
- Metrics assessing how effectively explanations support citizens in contesting AI-driven decisions.

- Instruments to evaluate how stakeholder trust evolves after XAI implementation.
- Culturally-aware metrics to ensure that explanations are meaningful and accessible to diverse populations.
- Legal Compliance Rubrics.

4.5 Explainability and the Need for Human-AI Collaboration in Public Administration

Whereas private-sector AI often aims for full automation, government AI should support human decision-making rather than replace it. However, poor explainability can hinder effective human-AI collaboration, forcing civil servants to either over-rely on AI or reject its recommendations due to lack of trust. New studies should explore:

- How XAI can facilitate human-AI collaboration rather than replace human expertise in government.
- What types of explanations improve usability for bureaucrats and policymakers.
- How to measure the effectiveness of AI explanations in real-world government workflows.

AI needs to empower government workers to make more informed, fair, and efficient decisions while always maintaining human oversight.

4.6 Security and Explainability Trade-offs

Some government AI applications, such as those in national security and intelligence, operate under classified or sensitive data constraints [13]. Research must explore how to balance the need for explainability with the necessity of keeping certain aspects of AI models confidential. Some key research questions include:

- How can explainability mechanisms that protect sensitive data while ensuring transparency be designed?
- What are the trade-offs between security and interpretability in government AI?
- How can policymakers be given meaningful explanations of AI decisions without exposing classified methodologies?

4.7 Culturally-Aware XAI

Since current XAI frameworks tend to assume universal interpretability standards, ignoring cultural diversity in government settings, further XAI research should address key questions such as:

- How can XAI frameworks be designed to adapt explanations to local cultural values, linguistic nuances, and governance traditions?
- What participatory methods can empower marginalized communities to co-define interpretability standards?
- Can culturally grounded explanations improve both algorithmic accountability and public trust in high-stakes government AI systems?

4.8 Operationalization Challenges for Government XAI Systems

Adoption barriers must also be considered in the development of XAI systems for the public sector. New studies should explore:

- HCI-driven training programs to support non-technical government workers in interpreting AI outputs while maintaining accountability.
- HCI-designed educational materials to help the public understand AI's role in shaping policy recommendations.
- The potential of XAI to reduce resistance to AI-driven automation within the public sector.

5 CONCLUSION

Explainable AI is crucial for ensuring transparency, accountability, and fairness in government decision-making. However, existing XAI research does not fully address the unique challenges faced by government workers, who operate in high-stakes, regulatory-heavy, and multi-stakeholder environments.

A new research agenda focused on XAI for government workers is needed—one that incorporates legal reasoning, social justice principles, and participatory design approaches. Building on prior work in HCXAI, Feminist XAI, and Conversational XAI, along with emerging research on XAI in the public sector, this agenda will help create AI systems that are not only explainable but also just, equitable, and accountable to the public.

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Explanations for Trustworthy AI in Critical Infrastructure: A Case from Wastewater Treatment in Norway

Position paper for the CHI 2025 workshop HCXAI

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Artificial intelligence applications in critical infrastructure poses requirements for explainability and interpretability, something that is also accentuated in recent European legislation on AI. In this position paper, we provide a glimpse into an ongoing project on AI development and implementation to improve highly instrumented wastewater treatment processes, with demands for explainability and interpretability to satisfy quality demands and requirements for trustworthy AI. Taking a starting point in previous HCXAI and XAI contributions, we discuss three takeaways from the case concerning (a) the benefit of targeted explanations, (b) the need for explanations to drive user action, and the implications of inaccurate explanations. In conclusion, we reflect on the role of explanations in assessments and audits of AI-applications critical infrastructure.

CCS CONCEPTS • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Human-centred explainable AI, trustworthy AI, critical infrastructure

ACM Reference Format:

Asbjørn Følstad, Sølve Eidnes, Hilde Johansen. 2025. Explanations for Trustworthy AI in Critical Infrastructure: A Case from Wastewater Treatment in Norway. Position paper presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15170429>

1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds promise for substantial improvements to critical infrastructure, such as that of transportation and supply of water or energy. Expected cross-sector benefits include, e.g., increased efficiency, performance improvements, and predictive analysis [1,17]. Responsible uptake of AI in critical infrastructure, however, requires that it is developed and implemented in adherence to principles of trustworthy AI [5,13] where the accuracy and robustness of AI, as well as its explainability and interpretability are key. The importance of explainability and interpretability is accentuated in recent European legislation on AI. As such, human-centred explainable AI (HCXAI) is becoming a legally required aspect of assessments and audits of AI systems in critical infrastructure.

In this position paper, we share experiences from an ongoing case of developing AI applications for a specific critical infrastructure, that of wastewater treatment, and use these as background on which to reflect on implications for HCXAI in assessments and audits for this purpose, specifically with regards to model performance. The case thereby expands on topics of previous studies presented to at previous HCXAI workshops, particularly Schneider et al.'s [14] discussion of targeted explanations in safety-critical domains and Mansi and Riedl's [12] framework for AI explanations and user action. It also relates to Cabitza et al.'s [4] study on the potentially detrimental effects of inaccurate explanations presented at the conference Explainable AI (XAI) 2024.

In the remainder of the paper, we first provide an overview of our specific case. We then allow previous HCXAI and XAI studies to guide our discussions of key takeaways from the case. Specifically, we discuss the benefit of targeted explanations, the need for explanations to drive user action, and the implications of inaccurate explanations, before reflecting on the role of explanations in assessments and audits of AI-applications in critical infrastructure, specifically in the light of the evolving landscape of AI regulation.

2 THE CASE: EXPLANATIONS FOR TRUSTWORTHY AI IN WASTEWATER TREATMENT

The case of our position paper is the development of AI-applications to improve efficiency and quality of wastewater treatment at a Norwegian wastewater treatment facility, Veas (<https://veas.nu/>). Wastewater treatment is part of the critical infrastructure of any urban settlement. As cities grow, the volume of wastewater from households, commercial and government institutions and industry increases to a point where the underwater environment is at risk [16]. To mitigate negative environmental impact, wastewater treatment has advanced substantially of the past decades, with complex processing to remove garbage, organic matter, and nutrients [10]. Current wastewater processing is highly instrumented with advanced control systems, paving the road for improvements through AI [11].

At Veas, time series data from the control system is made available for the training of AI models to make predictions on the wastewater treatment process. AI model development and assessment is conducted as part of the European research and innovation action FAITH (<https://faith-ec-project.eu/>), specifically addressing human-centred trustworthy AI.

Currently, Veas AI models are being developed for the wastewater treatment phase concerning removal of nitrate, a significant wastewater nutrient leading to increase in algae growth and destabilization of marine ecosystems. By predicting nitrate levels in outflowing wastewater, given relevant process parameters, the aim is to substantially increase the efficiency and effectiveness of nitrate removal [2]. However, AI models for this purpose need to account for the substantial variation in the wastewater treatment process due to seasonal variation and weather conditions. For example, heavy rainfall or low water temperatures significantly impacts wastewater treatment effectiveness. The accuracy of model predictions may, hence, vary substantially over different time periods [9].

For Veas stakeholders, the decision to make use of AI applications in wastewater treatment requires that the underlying AI models are sufficiently accurate and robust. Here, robustness concerns accuracy when a particular perturbation is applied [3]. Given the substantial variability in model accuracy across time periods, with perturbations driven by season or weather, general assessments of model accuracy and robustness is not sufficient. Rather assessments of accuracy of specific predictions should be available to process engineers and operators at runtime, to assess the need for human action at times of insufficient accuracy. Furthermore, prediction accuracy and robustness needs to be assessed as part of routine reviews and audits required as per general quality system requirements, e.g., in ISO 9001 [7].

In consequence, for stakeholders at Veas, intuitive and accessible runtime measures of accuracy and robustness will be highly important. And, in cases of inadequate accuracy or robustness, explanations of the basis for model predictions are

required. This may in particular be relevant for longer time periods where accuracy is low, to identify factors that might impact robustness and, thereby, propose mitigating actions.

Explanations for AI model performance is also important to satisfy future possible requirements related to recent AI legislation in Europe. Norway, as part of the Europe Economic Area, is currently implementing the European AI Act [6]. The legislation entered into force in 2024 and will have full applicability in 2026. It imposes substantial requirements on AI for purposes classified as high-risk – such as safety components of critical infrastructure [ibid., annex III]. To comply with the requirements of legislation, high-risk AI systems need to be transparent, with needed traceability and explainability, so as to enable appropriate use [ibid., article 13] with adequate levels of accuracy and robustness [ibid., article 15]. Furthermore, management of risk associated with the AI system is a cornerstone of the AI Act, where AI system owners are required to conduct AI risk management continuously throughout the entire life-cycle of high-risk AI systems [ibid., article 9].

Following this brief presentation of the case, we now discuss three key takeaways with the basis in previous papers on HCXAI and XAI and make concluding reflections with regards to one of the main workshop topics.

3 TAKEAWAY 1: THE BENEFIT OF TARGETED EXPLANATIONS

The success of AI-applications to improve efficiency and effectiveness in critical infrastructure, such as that of wastewater treatment, requires explanations that target stakeholders and users. As argued by Schneider et al. [14] in a 2024 HCXAI paper, AI-powered automation may widen the gap between operator accountability and control. When this happens, the explainability and interpretability of AI-based systems may be instrumental to provide stakeholders with needed information and visibility to negotiate the alignment of accountability and control. For this purpose, explanations and access to metrics needs to be tailored to the specific needs of the stakeholders.

This insight is highly relevant for our case of AI-applications for wastewater treatment. The introduction of AI for process control potentially may challenge accountability and control unless information and explanations needed for user and stakeholders, such as process engineers and operators, fit their needs. The lack of relevant information and explanations would reduce the trustworthiness of the AI-applications and hamper their uptake. Acknowledging the importance of targeted explanations, the design and development of the interface will follow the principles of human-centred AI [15], where a key components are substantial stakeholder involvement throughout the process and an iterative approach to AI development and implementation.

4 TAKEAWAY 2: THE NEED FOR EXPLANATIONS TO DRIVE USER ACTION

Explanations of AI can be instrumental to drive needed user action. Mansie and Riedl [12] addressed this in a paper presented at HCXAI 2023 and provided a framework connecting AI explanations and corresponding relevant user actions. The framework was motivated by a need in the XAI community to gain such an overview, and it is also useful as a map to guide project-specific considerations and expectations with regards to relevant XAI interactions.

The mapping of Mansie and Riedl is helpful for our purposes in the development of AI-models for critical infrastructure. In a domain such as wastewater treatment, model performance is highly important, and corresponding considerations for users may entail judgements of consistency or performance and decisions on continued usage or the need for mitigating action. For explanations concerning model performance, Mansie and Riedl notes that users may, e.g., require more or different information or request an audit. In our case, the human-centred process will allow for identifying needs for information and explanation during AI model and application development. Specifically, we aim to use dedicated stakeholder evaluation workshops throughout the development process for this purpose. This will help provide needed

runtime provision of information and explanations of relevance to assessing and understanding model accuracy and robustness, so as to take needed mitigating action, for example in the form of human intervention or AI model changes to address robustness issues for time periods. Furthermore, in line with implications from the work of Mansie and Riedl, we will during evaluations focus on user actions enabled by provided information and explanations.

5 TAKEAWAY 3: THE IMPLICATIONS OF INACCURATE EXPLANATIONS

While it is well established that explanations may enhance users' ability to make adequate use of AI, Cabitza and colleagues [4] in a paper presented at XAI 2024 note that for explanations to have this effect they need to enable users to form an adequate understanding of eventual issues and possible means of mitigation. In situations of inadequate or even misleading explanations, users may be induced to take erroneous mitigation actions – or fail to take needed action. Cabitza and colleagues refers to this as an explainability paradox, and make specific note of situations where misleading explanations may lead uses to disregard valid AI system advice in decision making processes.

The explainability paradox may be a valuable phenomenon to consider with regards to our use case on AI models to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of wastewater treatment. As note, it is key for stakeholders to assess the prediction accuracy during operations and both prediction accuracy and robustness during routine reviews and audits, where simple reviews could be conducted as often as on a daily basis. To maintain AI trustworthiness, it will be highly important to adequately address deviations in accuracy or robustness. To do this, Veas process engineers and operators will have access to information on AI prediction accuracy as well as explanations for predictions. One relevant form of explanations may be based on identifying time periods with similar characteristics and model performance issues to the current time period, which in turn may be used to identify characteristics associated with the given issue. However, following the explainability paradox, it will be necessary to ensure that provided explanations motivate users to make adequate decisions on whether or not to disregard AI model predictions. Following the lead of Cabitza and colleagues this could, for example, be set up as experimental user studies.

6 CONCLUDING REFLECTIONS: EXPLANATIONS IN ASSESSMENTS AND AUDITS OF AI-APPLICATIONS CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

We have presented a case of AI development for improving efficiency and effectiveness in wastewater treatment. To achieve this objective, and comply with requirements for trustworthy AI [5,13], the AI application needs to be sufficiently accurate and robust to provide adequate control. It further needs to provide information and explanations that allow process engineers and operators insight into the basis for its output, both as a source of validation or to drive identification of issues and mitigation needs.

Being critical infrastructure, wastewater treatment at Veas already is subject to extensive quality management processes, following international standards for quality management [7] and management of environmental impact [8]. As part of their quality system, process operators and engineers engage in routine reviews and audits of management of the wastewater treatment processes and related support systems. Consequently, any implementation of AI support in the wastewater treatment process will need to be included in adequate corresponding quality management processes and relevant reviews and audits.

For this purpose, information and explanations on AI model performance and prediction accuracy and robustness will be highly important input to quality management in general and routine reviews and audits in particular. Information on AI prediction accuracy and robustness will be a key point of assessment for AI models applied for wastewater treatment process control. Furthermore, explanations of model predictions may be instrumental in part to decide (a) whether and

when human intervention is needed as part of a human-in-the-loop response procedure and (b) whether and how any mitigation measures are needed to improve the AI model or its interface to the users.

The evolving regulatory landscape adds to the relevance of information and explanations on AI predictions. Europe is a leading region in terms of AI regulation and the ongoing implementation of the AI Act entails both promise and challenges. For AI system providers and owners, a key initial need will be to clearly characterize any specific AI application in terms of its risk level. For applications characterized as high risk – such as safety components in the management and operation of critical infrastructure – there will be substantial requests for information and explanations of AI model as input to required AI risk management processes. The AI Act will be fully implemented in 2026. To prepare for this, considerations of how to design and develop AI applications to enable needed information and explanations should have high priority.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is funded by EU Horizon Europe, HORIZON-CL4-2023-HUMAN-01-02, under the project FAITH (grant agreement No. 101135932). The work presented here reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Culturally Attuned Explainable AI: Developing a Research Agenda for Globally Inclusive AI Systems

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As artificial intelligence (AI) reshapes critical decisions worldwide— from healthcare to justice— Explainable AI (XAI) stands as a vital tool for building trust, transparency, and accountability. Yet, its current form is strikingly Western-centric, sidelining the vibrant cultural diversity of global users and risking systems that disconnect rather than unite. This paper unveils a bold research agenda for Culturally Attuned XAI (CAXAI), championing explainability frameworks that weave cultural responsiveness into their core. We identify gaps in the literature—particularly the scarcity of empirical studies on cultural variations in explanatory preferences—and highlight how overreliance on WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic) perspectives threatens AI’s global relevance. Drawing on fresh insights from cross-cultural human-computer interaction (HCI) and XAI, we propose an interdisciplinary, cross-cultural path to craft AI systems that honor diverse epistemologies and lived realities. This vision bridges technical ingenuity with ethical urgency, offering a roadmap to inclusive, equitable AI that resonates across humanity’s pluralistic tapestry—urging a reimagining of explainability as a global necessity.

Keywords: Explainable AI, Cultural Diversity, Human-AI Interaction, Global AI Ethics, Cross-cultural HCI, Algorithmic Fairness, Inclusive AI Systems, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170449

1 INTRODUCTION

AI systems are increasingly embedded in socio-cultural contexts, influencing high-stakes decisions in healthcare, education, hiring, and law enforcement. As their presence expands globally, the need for Explainable AI (XAI)—which enables stakeholders to understand, question, and trust AI decisions—has become more pressing. Yet most existing XAI research is rooted in Western-centric models of reasoning, with little attention to cultural variability in explanatory preferences, styles, or needs. Recent reviews underscore a stark underrepresentation of non-Western perspectives in XAI user studies, with a vast majority of empirical research relying exclusively on participants from WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic) populations [9]. This raises serious concerns about the generalizability of findings and highlights the risk of AI systems perpetuating cultural hegemony and miscommunication. As this paper will demonstrate through theoretical analysis, empirical recommendations, and case-based evidence, culture is not an external variable to be accounted for post hoc—it is central to how AI is experienced, understood, and legitimized.

This position paper argues for the development of culturally attuned explainability—one that is empirically grounded, interdisciplinary, and capable of accommodating pluralistic knowledge systems. By integrating diverse cultural perspectives into AI governance and design, we can enhance the adaptability, effectiveness, and ethical responsibility of AI technologies on a global scale. Building on existing human-centered and feminist approaches to XAI, we identify the core principles for such a framework and propose a concrete research agenda. This framing invites a reconsideration of how we design, evaluate, and govern explainability systems. Culturally attuned XAI (CAXAI) offers a way forward that prioritizes equity and contextual relevance by incorporating insights from legal pluralism, interdisciplinary collaboration, Indigenous knowledge, and participatory governance. By re-centering the explanatory process around the lived experiences and values of diverse communities, CAXAI has the potential to reshape the global development of ethical and trustworthy AI.

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2 CULTURAL FACTORS IN HUMAN-AI INTERACTION AND EXPLAINABLE AI

Human-AI interaction is not merely a technical or cognitive process—it is also a profoundly cultural one. As AI systems become increasingly embedded in decision-making processes that affect individuals and communities globally, cultural frameworks shape how people interpret, engage with, and trust AI technologies. Nowhere is this more evident than in the domain of explainable AI (XAI), where user satisfaction and system transparency hinge on the capacity to provide meaningful, culturally sensitive explanations.

Research in social psychology and cognitive science has demonstrated that explanatory preferences differ significantly across cultures. While individuals in individualistic, often Western (so-called WEIRD) societies tend to favor internalist explanations that focus on the mental states or traits of actors—such as beliefs, desires, or confidence—those in collectivist, often non-Western cultures are more likely to prefer externalist explanations [5]. These emphasize contextual, situational, and social factors such as norms, roles, obligations, or environmental constraints.

This cultural divergence poses a direct challenge to current XAI systems, which are predominantly designed with Western cognitive norms in mind. For example, many post-hoc XAI systems adopt an “intentional stance,” using metaphors such as “the model thinks...” or “the classifier knows...” These human-like mentalistic descriptions may resonate with individualist cultures but can alienate or confuse users from collectivist societies where social interdependence and external reasoning structures dominate.

To illustrate, studies have shown that Korean participants prefer explanations with rich contextual framing compared to their American counterparts, who lean toward direct and trait-based explanations [1]. Similar findings apply to Malaysian vs. U.S. users when choosing between complex and simplified explanations. High-context communication cultures such as Japan or China favor indirect, embedded meanings, while low-context cultures such as Germany and the U.S. prefer clarity and brevity. These distinctions matter greatly in how users interpret the trustworthiness and usefulness of XAI outputs.

Culturally misaligned explanations can erode trust in AI systems. Trust is central to successful human-AI collaboration, especially in high-stakes domains such as healthcare, education, and criminal justice. When users perceive explanations as opaque, irrelevant, or culturally inappropriate, they may disengage from the system, doubt its legitimacy, or misinterpret its outputs. This is especially critical in hybrid human-AI decision environments, where trust and shared understanding must be maintained continuously.

Moreover, people from collectivist backgrounds may refrain from engaging with systems that require public speculation about inner states—such behavior may be seen as presumptive or culturally inappropriate. This reluctance could result in uneven uptake of AI technologies across regions or demographic groups, further entrenching global digital divides.

Addressing these challenges requires reimagining XAI design to include diverse epistemologies. For instance, developers can implement systems that allow users to choose between internalist and externalist explanation formats, or that dynamically adapt explanations based on cultural context or user profiles [10]. Comparative studies [9] show promising avenues for developing such adaptable systems.

Crucially, this also means that the datasets used for training and testing XAI must be curated with cultural representativeness in mind. As highlighted in recent works [11], the political and cultural assumptions baked into dataset curation directly shape downstream AI behavior. If the training data reflect predominantly Western assumptions about normativity, then the explanatory outputs, regardless of interface or design, will likely reflect and reinforce those assumptions.

The path forward calls for several interventions. First, we must diversify the participant samples in XAI user studies. Currently, over 80 percent of such studies involve participants from WEIRD societies, yet the results are often extrapolated as universal. This practice produces “hasty generalizations” and obscures cultural variability in explanatory needs.

Second, researchers should explicitly report the cultural backgrounds of their participants and include “constraints on generality” in their conclusions, thereby avoiding overreach. Lastly, interdisciplinary collaborations between AI researchers, anthropologists, and cross-cultural psychologists can yield more robust frameworks for developing culturally responsive systems.

In conclusion, cultural factors are not peripheral but foundational to human-AI interaction and the efficacy of explainable AI systems. Without acknowledging the profound impact of cultural norms, values, and communication styles, XAI risks failing the majority of its users. A culturally reflexive approach to system design and evaluation not only enhances inclusivity and trust but also improves the overall effectiveness of AI across global contexts.

3 RESEARCH AGENDA FOR CULTURALLY ATTUNED XAI

To advance Culturally Attuned XAI, we propose a multi-pronged research agenda that includes the following priorities:

- **Empirical studies of cultural explanatory preferences:** These studies should compare explanatory formats (e.g., counterfactual, causal, analogical) across diverse cultural groups to identify patterns in perceived helpfulness, trust, and satisfaction [12].
- **Ethnographic and participatory design research:** Field-based work that involves communities in the design and evaluation of XAI interfaces can uncover cultural narratives and values that might otherwise be overlooked.
- **Dataset audit and intervention:** Inspired by recent research [2], future research should critically examine how cultural assumptions embedded in training data affect explanatory behavior, and develop corrective strategies.
- **Multilingual and multimodal explainability:** Cultural accessibility also depends on linguistic and media representation. Developing explanation interfaces that support local languages and culturally relevant media (e.g., oral storytelling, visuals) can improve understanding.
- **Collaborative AI governance:** Embedding cultural responsiveness into algorithmic governance through community-based advisory boards, civic deliberation methods, and inclusive impact assessments.

4 POLICY AND GOVERNANCE DIMENSIONS

Culturally attuned Explainable AI (XAI) raises critical questions about governance, accountability, and the institutional practices that shape AI deployment [6]. Policymaking in AI often proceeds from normative frameworks developed in Western liberal democracies, which may not translate effectively across other governance contexts. International guidelines, such as those from the OECD or UNESCO, increasingly acknowledge the need for cultural inclusion, but concrete mechanisms to enact this inclusivity remain scarce. In addition, meaningful cultural governance must extend beyond the level of technical standards to encompass frameworks that recognize diverse legal traditions, including customary, religious, and Indigenous legal systems. In many parts of the world, algorithmic decisions interact with overlapping legal orders, and for culturally attuned XAI to gain legitimacy, it must be embedded within these pluralistic governance environments.

To address these challenges, we argue for a multi-faceted approach including:

- **regional AI ethics frameworks that integrate local values and practices;**

- **governance models that incorporate community-based oversight and participatory audits; and**
- **capacity-building initiatives to ensure Global South researchers and policymakers are not only included but centered in the development of AI norms.** For instance, efforts in algorithmic accountability, such as participatory data stewardship frameworks and community-led audits, as promoted by organizations like Data Society and the Ada Lovelace Institute, offer promising blueprints for culturally aligned governance. These mechanisms could bridge the gap between technical assessments of fairness and the lived experiences of those most impacted by AI. Moreover, language accessibility plays a critical role—transparency initiatives must ensure that explanations, consent documents, and appeal procedures are not only translated into local languages but also culturally adapted to reflect how different communities understand authority, causality, and risk. Investing in local legal and linguistic expertise as part of XAI governance could drastically improve its reach and credibility, ensuring that culturally attuned XAI aligns with both technical and socio-cultural realities.

5 CASE STUDIES AND EMERGING PRACTICES

Recent initiatives illustrate what culturally attuned XAI can look like in practice. They demonstrate, for example, how algorithmic fairness must be redefined in contexts like India, where communal identity, social hierarchies, and legal norms interact differently with data-driven systems [11]. Their findings call for incorporating locally relevant social science frameworks and for algorithmic explanation interfaces that reflect regional histories and institutional trust dynamics.

Similarly, Indigenous data sovereignty movements highlight the importance of data governance that reflects collective rights, not only individual consent. Projects like OCAP® (Ownership, Control, Access, and Possession) principles by First Nations in Canada set precedent for AI models that are not only explainable but also accountable to community-specific knowledge systems.

Another compelling case is the participatory design of natural language processing tools for African languages in the Masakhane research community. This decentralized, multilingual effort demonstrates how grassroots, community-led AI development can surface new requirements for explainability—particularly around how models communicate uncertainty, reflect indigenous knowledge, and center user agency.

Likewise, the Encode Justice initiative, led by youth across the Global North and South, shows how advocacy, storytelling, and grassroots education can shape public understanding of AI accountability and transparency. Their campaigns have influenced how policies frame explanations—not merely as technical features but as rights-based demands.

These examples show that XAI is not a one-size-fits-all proposition; instead, it must be tailored to local realities through direct engagement with affected communities, taking into account legal, epistemological, and ethical distinctions.

6 INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES TO XAI

Building effective culturally attuned Explainable AI (XAI) demands contributions from a wide range of disciplines, including anthropology, design, ethics, sociology, linguistics, and beyond. These fields bring tools for contextualization, co-design, and narrative framing that are rarely considered in traditional computer science, enriching the development of culturally sensitive explainability. For instance, feminist HCI has long emphasized situated knowledge, power asymmetries, and participatory methods—all of which are vital to ensuring explanations resonate across diverse cultural contexts [8]. Anthropology offers methodologies to understand embedded cultural practices and beliefs; design research brings iterative and user-centered frameworks; and linguistics contributes to localized semantics and discourse analysis

necessary for adapting explanation formats. Engaging these disciplines enables a richer account of user diversity and helps tailor XAI to reflect the complexities of global populations [7].

Beyond methodological contributions, interdisciplinary work also challenges foundational assumptions in AI about neutrality, universality, and objectivity. Scholars in science and technology studies (STS) have long shown how technological systems embed social and political values, even when framed as impartial tools. Including STS scholars in XAI development can illuminate which values are being encoded into explanations and whose interests they serve, fostering greater accountability. Similarly, postcolonial and decolonial theorists can help critique how AI systems replicate colonial knowledge hierarchies through explanation formats that dismiss or marginalize non-Western epistemologies. These critical perspectives ensure that culturally attuned XAI (CAXAI) is not only inclusive in design but also accountable in purpose. However, fostering such interdisciplinary collaboration requires institutional mechanisms—funding calls, cross-disciplinary review criteria, and academic incentives—that recognize the value of non-technical contributions to AI design. By integrating these diverse disciplinary insights, CAXAI can move beyond technical optimization to become a truly pluralistic and equitable framework.

7 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE CHALLENGES

While the case for culturally attuned explainable AI (CAXAI) is strong, several challenges remain. These include difficulties in collecting representative data across cultures, ethical concerns around personalization, and the risk of reinforcing cultural essentialism if not carefully managed. There are also methodological limitations, as many tools for evaluating explainability do not account for cultural context [13]. One notable challenge is the assumption that ‘culture’ can be easily quantified and integrated into technical systems without flattening complexity. As pointed out by Diaz et al. [3], representation is not just a matter of statistical parity but also of how different social groups are semantically framed in the data. Moreover, the trade-offs between personalization and generalization must be carefully negotiated to avoid creating hyper-individualized systems that lose social accountability.

Compounding these issues is the underrepresentation of non-Western experts and institutions in the research and standard-setting processes related to XAI. Global South researchers often face structural barriers to participating in influential academic, technical, and policy forums where explainability standards are debated and defined. This lack of inclusion not only limits the diversity of perspectives but also reinforces epistemic injustice by privileging certain ways of knowing and excluding others from shaping AI futures. Future research must tread carefully, balancing generalizability with sensitivity and resisting the urge to universalize findings from specific cultural contexts. Structural interventions are needed to democratize access to funding, publishing, and policy influence, fostering a more representative and just AI research ecosystem. Building collaborative, cross-regional research consortia could offer more ethically grounded and empirically rigorous pathways forward, ensuring that CAXAI evolves in a way that reflects global diversity and equity.

8 CONCLUSION

Explainable AI (XAI) must evolve to meet the realities of a global, culturally pluralistic world. The prevailing Western paradigms in XAI research and design limit the accessibility and legitimacy of AI systems across diverse contexts, underscoring the urgent need for transformation. By acknowledging cultural variation in explanatory preferences, redesigning systems with cultural reflexivity, and reforming data practices, we can move toward globally inclusive and ethically sound AI ecosystems. Culturally Attuned XAI (CAXAI) is not just a design enhancement—it is a fundamental requirement for justice, equity, and human-centered innovation in artificial intelligence. To that end, explainability

should be treated as a sociotechnical challenge requiring interdisciplinary collaboration, participatory co-design, and governance mechanisms that foreground the perspectives of those historically excluded from AI development.

The insights from this paper also call for structural transformation across the AI ecosystem—from how datasets are built and annotated to how institutional review boards and policy frameworks define harm, consent, and accountability. Initiatives in governance, interdisciplinary scholarship, and participatory design highlight the need to develop inclusive infrastructures that support CAXAI long-term. As AI systems become further entrenched in public and private life, the demand for explanations that are not only technically sound but also culturally meaningful will only grow. By embedding cultural knowledge at the heart of XAI, we can reimagine explanation not just as an interface feature, but as a tool for epistemic justice and social transformation. The future of explainability must therefore be one of translation, collaboration, and deep cultural humility. It is through such commitment that we can build AI systems that do not merely work—but work justly, for everyone.

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Explainable AI through the lens of Legitimate AI

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Fig. 1. Explanations through the lens of legitimacy and its four aspects relating to steps in an AI's life-cycle. These aspects reveal questions that a person subjected to automated decisions may have to judge the legitimacy of that automation. Questions that a more explainable AI system can help answer.

Explainable AI (XAI) is frequently linked to responsible AI, under the assumption that it allows organisations to implement AI responsibly. However, with AI's growing use in civic settings, the number of people subjected to (partially) automated decisions rises, which should make us question if explanations from a responsible AI perspective would also benefit these subjects. We propose legitimate AI as an alternative and more relevant perspective to guide explainable AI (XAI) research focused on these subjects. If subjects are aided in their judgement of whether an AI is legitimate, they can serve as a societal check if the development and usage of an AI were done responsibly. In addition, explanations supporting that judgment enable them to decide to contest or accept a decision. We outline four aspects of legitimacy and their relevance to XAI, discussing a subject's potential questions for each aspect, highlighting topics that are currently under-explored. This perspective also uncovers the complexity of explanations aimed at empowering subjects, as such explanations need to reveal complex and intertwined topics through limited to no direct interaction.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Social and professional topics** → *Computing / technology policy*; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; • **Security and privacy** → Human and societal aspects of security and privacy.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Explainable AI, Legitimate AI, XAI, Contestability, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170257

1 Introduction

The topic of explainable AI (XAI) is often related to the need to have AI that is implemented and used responsibly [1, 12, 38]. Responsibility in AI considers the extent to which developers, data agencies, auditing organisations, and similar executive organisations ensure that an AI meets ethical expectations and behaves within legal boundaries [1, 6, 36]. From this perspective, XAI is a means of obtaining the necessary insights to determine if an AI is ethical and legal [2]. In addition, XAI has been discussed as a means for users to obtain insights for purposes such as collaboration [33],

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Fig. 2. Two perspectives to Explainable AI. Responsible AI focuses on executive organisations whereas Legitimate AI focuses on those subjected to the use of an AI. Whether an AI is deemed legitimate or not, should dictate if executive organisations took their societal and legal responsibility.

trust [15], and acceptance [24]. In short, the perspective of responsible AI is applied by executive organisations, such as developers, data agencies, and auditing organisations – those held responsible for an AI. The perspective of legitimate AI applies to those subjected to an AI, such as patients, loan applicants, and those suspected of fraud – those judging the use of an AI. See 2 for this distinction. In this work, we focus on the subject and argue that the perspective of legitimacy is better suited to identify their needs than the responsible AI perspective.

This work contributes to the HCXAI'25 workshop topic of promoting responsible AI practices by arguing for a change in perspective when dealing with the subject role. Legitimacy is a term for public policy, and this work illustrates how XAI can draw inspiration from that field. As subjects are most prevalent in civic applications of AI (i.e., the public domain [34]), this work is also relevant for the workshop's civic AI theme.

Legitimacy in the context of AI is about its behaviour and sociotechnical system “being desirable, proper or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions” [35]. Legitimacy is relational, with a behaving entity and a judging entity involved [19]. For legitimate AI, those who are subjected to an AI judge its legitimacy, not the executive organisations who are responsible for ensuring that it is legitimate. These subjects have their data collected, processed and used in the advancement and development of AI [9, 16]. They experience the effects of AI decisions as it is deployed. Subjects are not the users of an AI. A user receives support from that AI for their decision-making or employs it to achieve particular goals [9]. A user is in a position to ensure the responsible use of an AI. Instead, a subject is the person who judges whether the use of an AI aligns with their norms and values. As such, when dealing with the information needs of a subject, the perspective of legitimacy is better suited than the perspective of responsibility.

XAI's role concerning legitimacy is to provide individuals with the necessary understanding to judge whether an AI and its sociotechnical system align to their norms and values. In the literature, this is mainly limited to empowering subjects to contest AI outcomes [25]. Our work introduces the perspective of legitimacy and illustrates that this can reveal new questions and needs that are currently being overlooked.

2 Aspects of legitimacy

This work follows the definition from Suchman [35] which defines legitimacy as a relational concept based on the judgment of behaviour in terms of norms, values, beliefs and definitions. This recognises that what is legitimate is fluid by nature as the basis of judgement changes with cultures and experience [3, 19, 20]. Often, legitimacy is portrayed as

multidimensional; with an ethical dimension (is this AI ethical?), a legal dimension (is this AI allowed?), a political dimension (does this AI reflect my community?) and a societal dimension (should I accept this AI?) [5].

In the context of AI, and particular XAI, a system approach to legitimacy seems most relevant. First introduced by Scharpf [30], a system approach underlines the need for a holistic view towards legitimacy and that it consists of different intertwined aspects. These aspects are input and output legitimacy [30], throughput legitimacy [17, 31], and outcome legitimacy [5, pp. 60-61]. When mapped to AI, these relate to questions such as “Was my community represented in the development of this AI?” (input), “How is this AI involved in decision-making?” (throughput), “Is this AI reliable?” (output), and “Am I treated the same as others?” (outcome). This system approach to legitimacy matches the call from the HCXAI community for a more holistic and sociotechnical view toward XAI [13, 28, 32].

Below we describe each aspect in more detail in relation to XAI and discuss the new research directions the perspective of legitimacy reveals. Figure 1 illustrates the four aspects and the subject’s judgment call for each with examples of questions the subject may have. This figure also illustrates that a subject’s judgement allows them to decide to contest or accept an AI’s decision. If the subject decides to contest the decision, this could lead to the acceptance or rejection of their concerns by an executive organisation. When accepted, this may result in an improved version of the AI, a decision to use it differently, or to discard its use entirely. When a subject’s concerns are rejected, a conflict arises between the subject as society’s representative and an executive organisation responsible for the AI. A conflict that could be resolved through mediation or legal steps. The perspective of legitimacy on XAI, reveals that subjects should be empowered to make the necessary judgement calls. The four aspects of legitimacy allow for the identification of distinct questions to be answered.

2.1 Input legitimacy

Input legitimacy is about understanding what went into the development of an AI and judging that development process. It is important for the subject to understand if they were sufficiently represented during development and how this shaped the eventual AI and its surrounding sociotechnical system. For example, a subject’s judgment on the legitimacy of an AI is affected when they realise that this AI was not tested on bias that could be harmful to them. Similarly, a subject’s data may have been used in the development or testing of the AI, and they might wonder if and how they consented to this. For XAI to support subjects in their judgment regarding input legitimacy, these questions need to be identified and answered before subjects can judge whether their norms and values were sufficiently represented.

These topics often relate to legal transparency requirements [18] that state that such information should be present in the event of legal disputes. Here, we argue that for subjects to judge if an AI is legitimate, they require this information to be explained to them when confronted with the use of an AI. HCXAI strongly advocates for the recognition and participation of subjects in the research, design, and development of XAI [13]. Input legitimacy offers a lens through which that involvement and impact can be disclosed to subjects.

2.2 Throughput legitimacy

Throughput legitimacy is about a subject’s judgement on how an AI is used in the decision-making process, including its oversight. For subjects, it is important to understand that an AI is used in the first place. Not all use of AI is always obvious. Second, they should know what role an AI played and the broader sociotechnical system in which it operates. For example, if an AI only collected and presented data to a decision-maker who is regularly audited or made a decision entirely on its own with minimal human oversight. Finally, a subject should understand what parties are involved in assessing if they trust those parties in their role. For example, an AI assisting a physician to achieve better diagnoses

might be experienced differently than an AI assisting a medical student to allow them to act as a physician to help reduce their workload. Although the AI might be the same, the way it is used can be a reason for a subject to judge it illegitimate.

The aspect of throughput legitimacy seems to be a more prevalent topic in XAI compared to input legitimacy. For example, see the research on procedural fairness and the role of explanations address how subjects may contest the way an AI is used [29, 32, 39]. Similarly, the work of Yurrita et al. [40] introduces process-centred explanations that explain the decision-making process of an AI with the aim of empowering subjects to scrutinise this process. Throughput legitimacy implies more than these explanations on the AI's functioning. Explanations may also address the degree of human involvement, the organisations involved in the decision-making process, or who can view a subject's data. Throughput legitimacy underlines the need to expand towards a more social and holistic take on XAI, where explanations address more than an AI's functioning [10, 11].

2.3 Output legitimacy

Output legitimacy is about understanding and judging the benefits and risks the AI's contribution to a decision offers a subject. If an AI makes a decision that affects the subject, they should be able to understand if this is in their best interest. Subjects, for example, may want to know if the use of that AI results in a better or more efficient decision for them. Alternatively, they may want to know if cases like theirs result in correct and consistent outputs. Output legitimacy in relation to XAI is about allowing subjects to judge if an AI's output offers any value to them without introducing undue risk.

It seems that so far a limited number of explanations have been identified to help subjects judge if an AI's output is beneficial to them. Research on explanations that help AI users assess the disparity in error rates between demographic groups may come closest [7, 32]. Such explanations might also prove to be useful in communicating to subjects the differences in an AI's performance between their demographic group and others. However, these explanations must be adapted to a subject instead of a user role. Technical work on explanations that convey the consistency [27] and confidence of an AI [37] might offer similar directions, but require similar adaptations.

2.4 Outcome legitimacy

Outcome legitimacy concerns the judgement if the effects of a decision with an AI's involvement are acceptable to the subject. It refers to the fairness, relevance, and accuracy of a decision and its consequences. Subjects may wonder how the decision was made, what data was used, and what the importance of certain data was. Here, subjects may also ask themselves if they are able to understand how the AI functions and if that understanding is sufficient for them to feel confident in their judgment of its legitimacy.

Outcome legitimacy is at present the most researched, as it relates to explaining the (un)fairness of a decision and allows subjects to contest it if necessary. This is not without its challenges, as such explanations might leave the subject believing that an AI is fair when it is not [32]. Although the principle of fair treatment might be the most prevalent topic in the literature regarding outcome legitimacy, it is not the only one. Another relevant topic of explanation are the consequences of a decision in the first place [21]. Not all subjects in every domain might be able to understand this easily (e.g., patients with low health literacy who have trouble understanding an AI-aided diagnosis). The ability to recognise the consequences of a decision forms the basis for the subject's agency to determine whether and how to judge the legitimacy of decisions [22, 23]. Finally, common ethical principles such as accountability (i.e., who is

responsible for the consequences?) and privacy (i.e., who knows about this decision and its consequences?) could prove to be equally important depending on the domain, decision, and subject.

3 Example: welfare benefits fraud scoring

To further clarify the value of the legitimacy perspective for XAI, we map it to a real-world case. Rotterdam, a major Dutch city, used an AI to score the risk of fraud among citizens on their welfare benefits from 2017 to 2021 [8, 14]. These citizens were the subjects of this AI. The executive organisations comprised of the Rotterdam municipality using this AI and its developer Accenture. They were tasked with ensuring that the AI was developed and used responsibly. This AI, a gradient boosting model, used 315 attributes to provide a score to around 30.000 citizens, using around 500 decision trees. The attributes used ranged from the gender, age and financial status of the subject to more invasive attributes, such as the duration of their last romantic relationship. In addition, attributes included if any comment fields were filled in by case workers, such as on the subject's ability to handle pressure, their motivation, attitude, appearance, and ability to be flexible. Of the 30.000 citizens analysed, roughly 10% received a sufficiently high risk score that warranted a deeper investigation.

The Responsible AI perspective towards XAI would dictate that the executive organisations should understand this AI sufficiently to decide how it can be used in an acceptable and legal manner. The Legitimate AI perspective towards XAI instead highlights the importance for the citizens, as subjects of the AI, to understand that an AI was used (throughput legitimacy), what data it used (input legitimacy), what their risk score was and why (output legitimacy), and how this resulted in an invasive investigation of their private life (outcome legitimacy). A WIRED article illustrates where explanations are used to disclose information for subjects [8]. It uses feature attributions to reveal the influence of questionable features on the outputted risk score (input legitimacy). In addition, it communicates several counterfactual explanations based on illustrative personas of typical subjects through 'scrollytelling' (output legitimacy). Research on XAI should not focus solely on helping executive organisations in their efforts to implement AI responsibly. Research should also address how subjects and those that act on their interests, such as journalists and NGO's, can be empowered to make a judgement call if an AI is indeed developed and used responsibly.

4 Empowering explanations

A subject's judgment if an AI and its use is legitimate is a means for society as a whole to be able to accept or disregard particular uses of AI. However, it is not the only added value of this judgment. It also serves the individual subject in their decision to contest or accept the decision with an AI's involvement. This requires the explanations not only to inform subjects but also to empower them to make a judgement and take appropriate action. This requires the suggestion of concrete actions that a subject can take [26]. For example, an explanation should not only convey the potential bias in a decision (outcome legitimacy), but also offer a suggestion who to contact to correct or mitigate this.

The four legitimacy aspects are intertwined and complementary to each other. First, it is not as if one legitimacy aspect is violated, the use of that AI suddenly becomes entirely illegitimate. This final judgment involves a personal weighing of a subject's own norms and values. Explanations should support this weighing by addressing multiple, if not all, aspects at a time to reveal important relations between them. For example, an explanation can address all aspects at once by explaining that a particular decision is biased (outcome legitimacy), but that this is inconsistent with other past decisions (output legitimacy) and occurred despite the involvement of the subject's demographic group in the AI's design (input legitimacy) with no option to address this to at present (throughput legitimacy). Such an explanation addressing all aspects offers the subject the necessary overview to decide if they want to take action and what that

action might be. Combined with clear suggestions on how they can act (e.g., report to an oversight committee), this would empower them greatly.

An open question remains how such explanations should be communicated to subjects. By definition, they are not in direct interaction with an AI. At best, they are informed by the AI or a human decision maker (e.g., during a doctor visit), at worse, they are informed through a static message (e.g., a letter from a government agency). Since the necessary explanations are likely multi-faceted and information dense, it is better to communicate them in an interactive manner such as through an explanatory dialogue [41] or an exploratory interface [4]. Alternatively, subjects may engage in conversation with someone who can explain this to them, who in turn has access to such dialogue and exploratory interfaces. Either option requires significant effort from organisations to implement. It would require a more involved interaction with the decision makers or an additional point of interaction with an AI.

The legitimacy perspective offers the HCXAI community a way to frame the needs of the subjects to empower them. At the same time, it reveals the complexity of supporting and empowering subjects in the reality of civil applications of AI.

5 Implications

Subjects, as individuals affected by AI decisions, should have the ability to challenge an AI's usage by judging its legitimacy based on their norms and values. This is the perspective of legitimacy for XAI in which subjects are empowered through explanations to signal illegitimate use of AI due to, for example, irresponsible development practices. We discussed four legitimacy aspects: input, throughput, output, and outcome, connecting them to potential questions a subject may have to inspire future topics for explanations. These include typical topics from XAI literature such as counterfactuals and procedural fairness, as well as novel ones like the degree of design participation and the benefits of an AI's usage for subjects. Legitimacy and its four aspects offer an interesting new perspective on an existing challenge. In addition, it serves as a frame that reveals the complexity of such explanations with topics being intertwined and the difficulty of communicating them. Subjects will rarely be in a position to interact directly with the explanations. How will we communicate complex and intertwined topics to them in a way that empowers them to make the necessary judgements and take appropriate action? This is a question that needs to be answered as we, as the HCXAI community, continue to pose explanations as a means of subject empowerment.

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Thoughts without Thinking: Reconsidering the Explanatory Value of Chain-of-Thought Reasoning in LLMs through Agentic Pipelines

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Agentic pipelines present novel challenges and opportunities for human-centered explainability. The HCXAI community is still grappling with how best to make the inner workings of LLMs transparent in actionable ways. Agentic pipelines consist of multiple LLMs working in cooperation with minimal human control. In this research paper, we present early findings from an agentic pipeline implementation of a perceptive task guidance system. Through quantitative and qualitative analysis, we analyze how Chain-of-Thought (CoT) reasoning, a common vehicle for explainability in LLMs, operates within agentic pipelines. We demonstrate that CoT reasoning alone does not lead to better outputs, nor does it offer explainability, as it tends to produce explanations without explainability, in that they do not improve the ability of end users to better understand systems or achieve their goals.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170393

1 Introduction

Explainable AI (XAI) has increasingly become acknowledged as a crucial, highly desirable property for developing and deploying AI systems responsibly [3], accountably [32], and effectively [10]. Explanations are intended to help people understand and make appropriate use of AI systems' outputs, and to provide insight into systems' functionality to a range of interested parties [10]. The need for such explanations is only heightened by the widespread interest in (and adoption of) AI systems based on large language models (LLMs) like the generative pretrained transformer (GPT) models central to ChatGPT [26] and DeepSeek [13]. Recently, model architectures have begun implementing "chain-of-thought" (CoT) techniques [25, 39] that prompt a model to "verbalize step-by-step reasoning" [36] and condition its output on that verbalization to improve outcomes [33, 41]. This CoT verbalization has been incorporated into frontier models as part of their 'scratchpad' memory to do compositional thinking before generating an output [1], and has also been proposed as a form of 'CoT Explanations' or explainability, offering insight into the so-called reasoning process that lead to a particular output [40] (but cf. [18, 35, 36]).

While CoT can often resemble abductive reasoning [14, 21], rationalizing and fitting likely explanations to given data, CoT text may often lead to *explanations without explainability*, prone as it is to generating seemingly plausible but erroneous, contradictory, or irrelevant content [28]. In this paper, we introduce an agentic pipeline framework developed as part of a perceptive task guidance system to support factory technician task execution in a manufacturing setting, which is being tested and validated in a non-factory setting using the assembly and disassembly of toy vehicles (cranes, dump trucks, bulldozers, etc.) as a proxy for manufacturing tasks [30]. The agentic pipeline framework we introduce below demonstrates that CoT reasoning does not lead to better outputs, nor does it offer explainability for those outputs.

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We present an empirical study of the former point and an analysis of the latter point, accompanied by a proposal for how our agentic pipeline can be used in concert with CoT approaches to produce greater explainability for AI systems.

2 Related Work

The emerging subfield of human-centered AI explainability builds on traditional explainability by broadening focus from AI models to include sociotechnical components of AI deployment. This includes consideration of how non-expert AI end-users understand how AI systems work, how inputs are created, and how explanations inform user behaviors [15]. The emergence of LLMs has complicated this field, as explored in prior iterations of the CHI HCXAI workshop [5, 11, 29, 43]. While we are still in the early days of untangling this knot, agentic systems have been proposed as a means to produce explainability [9, 24, 28, 38], in that they can produce a record of how instructions are passed between agents, “allowing end users to trace conclusions back to their source data” [24]. (See Section 4 for more detail on this architecture.) However, agentic architectures risk producing, instead of explainability, crowds of LLMs playing a sort of children’s game of “telephone” in which people whisper what they think is the same message from person to person in a chain until the last person says the message and everyone finds out it has been inevitably distorted, in often funny ways, by its passage between multiple people. These crowds of LLM agents present new challenges of “cascading risks,” [20] where humans have ceded control and oversight to information passing through a multi-actor system[6].

3 Data

We prepared a benchmarking dataset to evaluate the answering performance of various models within the agentic pipeline. This dataset consists of two categories of questions: task-based (Task) questions and organizational/social (Org-Soc) questions. We modeled our task-based questions on the Assembly 101 dataset [30], which provided an open-source way to build a system that supports human performance of physically situated tasks. Our Task questions revolve around putting together and taking apart toys like cranes, trucks, excavators, etc. and were used to probe the model about task-based performance support (e.g., How do I remove the wheels?). For our Org-Soc questions, we took a novel participatory approach[19]. We interviewed manufacturing technicians with whom we collaborate building our perceptive task guidance system. We worked with them to compile a set of questions they would want to ask the agent in the course of their real-world work. This process revealed that technicians assume that AI assistants like our system has a far wider range of abilities than they actually do. This insight (forthcoming) points to a gap between the way that foundation models’ performance is measured using existing benchmarks, and the real world of complex overlap between tasks, organizations, and social reality into which LLMs and agentic systems are being deployed. This participatory approach brings the evaluation of our system closer to the real world. Our dataset from toy assembly consists of 152 participatory Org-Soc questions, 43 Task questions per toy (3 toys evaluated). Both sets of questions (Task and Org-Soc) were posed to multiple models. The responses (N=750/300 (Task), 300 (Org-Soc), 150 (Thoughts)) were then scored along a Likert-like scale (-1, 0, 0.5, 1)¹ for their accuracy, comprehensiveness, and helpfulness, using an idealized technician performing a required task as the entity for whom an answer should assist. The scoring was first conducted on a subset of question-CoT-answer tuples by three authors, who all scored the same sub-subset of tuples to coordinate inter-annotator agreement, and then LLM-as-a-judge (GPT-4o[27]) was prompted with the scoring scheme, which scored the tuples (N=2529). Alongside this numerical scoring and quantitative analysis, we also conducted a qualitative analysis of the CoT texts in relation to questions and answers.

¹On this scale, “1” was a correct answer, “0.5” was a partially correct answer or an answer that had correct content in it but also included unhelpful or confusing information, “0” was an incorrect answer, and “-1” was a dangerous or unsafe answer.

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Fig. 1. Shows sample agentic flow depending on the type of input query from the user. Once the question is ingested, the lead planner generates a plan which is a sequence of agentic calls. The output of each of the agent in the flow is shown here.

4 Agentic architecture

The allure of agentic architecture is its ability to decompose the task (using planners), leveraging external systems (tools & other agents), perception, memory components and different task action experts (e.g. RAG, Reformulator etc.). Our implementation consists of: i) Perceptors: Perceive visual and language data, ii) Planners: tasked with decomposing, iii) Actors: Expand context, generate response and verify safety. Upon receiving the inputs from the perceptors, the system’s lead planner sequences the agents & tools invocations. Depending on the input (e.g., Org-Soc or Task), the planner decides to invoke the RAG (Retrieval Augmented Generation)-based flow or Chit-chat module. A detailed description of the system implementation can be found in Appendix A. The answer planner is then tasked with planning if there is sufficient information to answer the question, or if a follow-up question needs to be generated. The safety agent performs the final check.

Each agent in the agentic flow contains its own LLM. We experiment with 3 different LLMs (Llama3 - 8b [8], Qwen - 7b, 14b [4]) and their reasoning based Deepseek distilled alternatives [7]. Deepseek distilled reasoning models achieve impressive performance in numerous tasks while generating CoT reasons [7]. In this work, we aim to analyze the application of the models for our task guidance application and the unique dataset we developed, which requires better context understanding and complex reasoning. The context for the answer generation consists of lengthy specification documents (instructional documents detailing the steps needed carry out the process), instructions, historical chat data, and additional data from supporting agents. The questions from the users often requires reasoning and/or searching for a needle in a haystack [2, 17]. The goal of our work is to evaluate the responses generated by the agentic system.

5 Experiments

We conduct the experiments to evaluate the agentic architecture offline. The questions are input to the systems where agentic flow generate the responses. The responses are then reviewed and scores assigned by expert human reviewers & LLM-as-a-Judge. Since ground truth answers are rather difficult to generate and compare to the system generated answers, we adopt human & reference-free LLM-Judge evaluation. The experts assign scores to every answers generated by the agentic flow using 6 different LLMs. The reviewer scores are thus assigned by human experts and LLMs-as-a-judge. To further analyze the thoughts generated, we generate the scores for the thoughts (both human reviewers and LLM-as-a-judge) . The reviewers are tasked to assign 4 scores to the answers using question, reference response (and spec documents for task based questions) as context (see Footnote 1 for the judgment scale).

6 Results

Non-reasoning models perform better: We find that the thought models’ generated response (Deepseek distilled models-7b, 8b, 14b) achieve lower reviewer scores than the models not generating/trained to generate thoughts. We

Tuple	Content
A	<p>Input: What is the dump box connected to?</p> <p>CoT: Okay, so I'm trying to figure out what the "dump box" is connected to in this context. From the conversation history, there's a mention of a guide detailing a 152-step process for disassembling and reassembling a toy. The user specifically asks about the dump box connected to something. First, I need to understand what a "dump box" typically refers to. In mechanical terms, a dump box is often part of a motor or transmission system. It's usually a component that holds clutch plates or other parts that need to be engaged or disengaged rapidly. The dump box is connected to the clutch system and operates with solenoids to engage or release the clutch plates, which allows the vehicle to shift gears. Looking back at the guide mentioned earlier, it involves taking apart various components of a mechanical toy, possibly similar to a robot or an RC car. The steps include disassembling parts like the crane arm, transmission, and other mechanical systems. Since the user is asking about the dump box specifically, I should focus on its connection points. In a typical setup, the dump box is connected to the motor via a transmission system. It might also be linked to the gear shifter or control mechanism of the toy. In the context of the guide, during disassembly, one would need to disconnect the dump box from the clutch and other components before taking them apart further. During reassembly, the process would reverse, ensuring the dump box is correctly reattached and aligned with the rest of the system for proper functionality. So, putting this together, the dump box in this context is likely connected to the motor and transmission systems of the toy. It's a crucial component for shifting gears and controlling the movement of the toy's mechanical parts.</p> <p>Output: In the context of the detailed guide for disassembling and reassembling a complex mechanical toy, the "dump box" is a component typically found in the transmission system. It is connected to both the motor and the clutch system, allowing for rapid engagement or disengagement of the clutch plates. This connection ensures proper gear shifting and control over the movement of the toy's mechanical parts during operation. Summary: - "Dump Box Function": Part of the transmission system, responsible for engaging/disengaging clutch plates. - "Connection Points": Linked to the motor and other subsystems like the gear shifter. - "Disassembly/Reassembly": Requires careful handling to ensure correct reattachment and functionality during reassembly.</p>
B	<p>Input: How do you ensure data privacy and security?</p> <p>CoT: Okay, so I'm trying to figure out how an AI like MARIE ensures data privacy and security. I know that as a helpful agent developed at Intel Labs, it's probably designed with some safeguards in place. But I'm not exactly sure about the specifics. First, maybe there are layers of encryption. That makes sense because when you send information, especially sensitive stuff, you want it protected during transit. So if MARIE uses HTTPS or something similar, that could be part of it. Then, access controls come to mind. Only authorized people should handle data, so maybe there are strict permissions and role-based access. That way, even if someone gets in, they can't access everything without proper clearance. Data anonymization is another point. Maybe personal information is removed or obscured before processing. That way, the data isn't identifiable even if it's intercepted. Regular audits might also be part of the process to check security measures and ensure compliance with regulations like GDPR or CCPA. This helps keep things up to standard. Moreover, secure development practices must be in place. Following best practices when coding ensures that any vulnerabilities are caught early, making the system more secure overall. Physical security isn't something I initially thought about, but if MARIE is deployed in a physical space, securing servers and data centers from unauthorized access would be crucial. Lastly, continuous monitoring and incident response plans can catch any breaches quickly. This proactive approach helps minimize damage and recover faster if something goes wrong. I wonder how these measures are implemented technically, like specific algorithms or protocols they use for encryption. Also, how they handle updates and patches to maintain security over time.</p> <p>Output: MARIE ensures data privacy and security through a multi-layered approach: 1. "Encryption": Utilizes HTTPS and other secure communication protocols to protect data during transit. 2. "Access Controls": Implements strict permissions and role-based access to restrict data handling to authorized personnel only. 3. "Data Anonymization": Removes or obscures personal information before processing, making data non-identifiable even if intercepted. 4. "Regular Audits": Conducts compliance checks with regulations like GDPR and CCPA to maintain standards and ensure proper practices. 5. "Secure Development Practices": Follows best practices in coding to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities early, enhancing overall security. 6. "Physical Security": Secures servers and data centers against unauthorized access, ensuring physical protection. 7. "Continuous Monitoring and Incident Response": Monitors for breaches and has plans in place to respond quickly, minimizing potential damage and recovery time. These measures are technically implemented through algorithms and protocols, with ongoing updates and patches to maintain security over time.</p>
C	<p>Input: Can you communicate with humans in multiple languages?</p> <p>CoT: Okay, so I'm trying to figure out how an AI like MARIE ensures data privacy and security. I know that as a helpful agent developed at Intel Labs, it's probably designed with some safeguards in place. But I'm not exactly sure about the specifics. First, maybe there are layers of encryption. That makes sense because when you send information, especially sensitive stuff, you want it protected during transit. So if MARIE uses HTTPS or something similar, that could be part of it. Then, access controls come to mind. Only authorized people should handle data, so maybe there are strict permissions and role-based access. That way, even if someone gets in, they can't access everything without proper clearance. Data anonymization is another point. Maybe personal information is removed or obscured before processing. That way, the data isn't identifiable even if it's intercepted. Regular audits might also be part of the process to check security measures and ensure compliance with regulations like GDPR or CCPA. This helps keep things up to standard. Moreover, secure development practices must be in place. Following best practices when coding ensures that any vulnerabilities are caught early, making the system more secure overall. Physical security isn't something I initially thought about, but if MARIE is deployed in a physical space, securing servers and data centers from unauthorized access would be crucial. Lastly, continuous monitoring and incident response plans can catch any breaches quickly. This proactive approach helps minimize damage and recover faster if something goes wrong. I wonder how these measures are implemented technically, like specific algorithms or protocols they use for encryption. Also, how they handle updates and patches to maintain security over time.</p> <p>Output: Currently, [the agentic pipeline system] is only capable of communicating in English.</p>

Table 1. Example tuples. Input is from the Task and Org-Soc participatory benchmark dataset, chain-of-thought and output are produced by the agentic pipeline.

perform Wilcoxon rank-sum test and show that the differences are significant (Figure 2). **LLM-as-a-Judge or not:** Usage if LLM-as-a-Judge remains an area of debate [12, 34, 42]. In this work, we find that the LLM Judge & human reviewer scores exhibit weak correlation (Cohen's Kappa = 0.48 (org-soc), 0.28 (task)). We find that the LLM-as-a-Judge, in spite of its limitation, can be a reference-free approach that could serve as an indicator of the quality of the response. **Reviewer scores for the answers in reasoning models are weakly correlated with the thoughts** Interestingly, we find that the reviewer scores for the thoughts are correlated with reviewer scores for the responses. This indicates that the thoughts do not necessarily guide the models to the correct responses. If the thoughts were strongly correlated

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Fig. 2. Shows the reviewer scores for the answers as rated by humans and LLM-as-a-judge on Task and Org-Soc questions. We observe that the reviewer scores for the non-reasoning models are better than their reasoning (Deepseek-) counterparts. We can also observe that the thoughts reviewer scores are weakly correlated with the answer reviewer scores.

to the answers, we might infer that the "correctness" or "incorrectness" of the answers could be explained by the thoughts. However, we observe that the thoughts have a high degree of incompleteness (0.5 reviewer score) irrespective of the answers being correct or wrong (middle column in the heatmap Figure 2). We highlight this as an interesting area for future exploration.

7 Discussion

The data presented above indicates that CoT can lead to incorrect answers, hampering explainability. To investigate these implications, we also conducted a qualitative content analysis (QCA) [16, 22] of CoT reasoning. QCA can act as a form "reverse engineering" [31] that allows analysts to focus on the entire system that produced outputs. Take, for example, the prompt-CoT-output tuple A in Appendix Table 1. Given the input, the output is unhelpful and incorrect. It contains reference components that are not part of a toy dump truck (e.g., transmission system, clutch) that are not mentioned in the assembly instructions. From an inspection of the CoT, it does not offer users an explanation for why the output is so unhelpful, but *it does show how quickly the CoT reasoning went astray*.

A QCA of the CoT, however, does provide some clues as to what may have led it astray by pointing to larger elements than the tuple itself. A qualitative reading of the CoT shows how quickly the text moves away from references to "disassembling and reassembling a toy" (as provided by the assembly instructions) and toward references to what is more "typically" associated with a dump box: an actual machine. Here, the CoT pulls in a range of tokens related to machine components like a "clutch", "transmission", or "gears" but while it continues to mention the "toy", nouns and verbs related to actual machines predominate. Put together, one hypothesis generated by QCA points toward the tendency of LLMs to fall victim to the "Einstellung Paradigm" [23] in which a focus on familiar or common approaches leads away from the correct approach. Here, the CoT focuses on tokens much more commonly associated with dump trucks (machine-related) in the LLM rather than the tokens germane to the task (toy-related and provided in the RAG). Another possible hypothesis generated by a QCA is that the RAG agent seemed to face an issue in filling up the context window, and therefore drew on the foundation model, which returned text on dump trucks, generically, as complex machinery. Crucially, while the QCA has pointed us in potentially helpful directions for troubleshooting this unhelpful output, such detailed analysis of the CoT does not lead to explainability. Rather, considerably more effort is required to

make sense of inputs and outputs, even if the CoT generates more material with which to engage in such sensemaking. Tuple B in Appendix Table 1 also evinces a susceptibility to the Einstellung paradigm.

Another way explainability is hindered by CoT is seen in tuple C in Appendix Table 1. The input is a question from the Org-Soc questions, “Can you communicate with humans in multiple languages?” that indexes a need users might have to know how best to communicate with the system. The output, stating that it cannot, is incorrect, even though a test prompt in a non-English language returns a legitimate result in that other language.² Here, the CoT text illustrates three important ways that CoT can materially hinder explainability: 1) It takes as a fact something that is not true even though no prompt provided as context to an input states this, although it is true that all prompting is *in* English. 2) It makes a flawed inference based on this claim: “Since the context only lists English... right now it’s just English”, evincing a form of logical fallacy known as *hasty generalization* [37]. 3) The CoT produces more text than is needed to arrive at its (erroneous) conclusion, introducing difficult-to-parse text that the user needs to wade through in search of a useful explanation and also reinforces logical errors. Each of these interferes with explainability by introducing irrelevant text or erroneous forms of argument, raising the burden for anyone seeking explanatory content in the CoT.

Limitations and Future Work: There are several limitations of our work. We assume agentic architecture as a preferred choice for developing the system while there exists a plethora of ways to developing the system. We aim to compare and evaluate alternate ways to develop task guidance system and evaluate via ablations the value of each agent in the system. We deploy the same LLM in each of our agent for ease of comparison. We acknowledge that different LLMs could serve as a different task experts. Our dataset while participatory in nature is limited in size. The aim of this work was to carefully evaluate every response from every model. In the future work, we aim to address this issue by scaling the analysis to a larger sample.

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²The input “Wo wohnen sie?” (“Where do you live?”) returns an output stating that, as an AI, our task-based guidance system cannot be thought of as having a traditional place of residence. Interestingly, the CoT for this prompt is output in English.

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A Agentic implementation details

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Agent	Function	Input
Lead planner	Fixed lead component tasked with creating a pipeline graphs which each node is an agent.	Definitions of the agents, input (question), and task description
Query planner	Assesses the query and decides if the query needs to be reformulated and which database to use for retrieval augmented generation	Task description, Original query, Additional text context (output of trailing agents)
Answer planner	Decides if the context has sufficient information to answer the question. If it does, the answer planner is invoked to generate the answer else, a question generator.	Task description, context (output of trailing agents), query
Intent detection	Detects the intent (defined by domain experts) of asking the question. This can be especially useful for either the RAG module or other subsequent module.	Task description, intent candidates, Original query
Visual action recognition	Identifies the action being performed in the visual frame	Vision frames
Object detection	Identifies objects in the visual frame	Vision frames
Chit-chat	For non-task related queries, the system answers the queries following a set of policy rules defined in the guideline prompt	Task description, Policy document, Query
Question answerer	Answers the task-related query utilizing the enhanced context	Task description, Query, context
Question generator	Generates the question typically requesting for missing information utilizing the query and the context	Task description, Query, context
Reformulator	Converts the original query into a paraphrase query utilizing additional context parameters (typically objects and the actions)	Task description, Query, Visual context
RAG	Retrieves the documents using the query and summarizes the documents for the context utilizing the query	Task description, Query, Vector database
Safety Agent	Utilizes a policy document to distinguish safe from inappropriate response	Policy document, response (question or answer)

Table 2. Table describes the agents, functions and inputs to each agent.

Task examples	Org-Soc examples
What is the bull bar?	What is your name and model number?
How many pieces are there, in total?	Can you tell me more about your capabilities and limitations?
Which way do I turn the screws to unscrew?	Can you communicate with humans in multiple languages?
Where is the windshield?	How fast can you process information?
Which side of the dump box faces out?	How do you ensure your own maintenance and self-preservation?
What position should the grill bar be in?	Can you understand and process human language as easily as a human can?
How tight should the nuts be?	How do you ensure privacy and security of my data?
What is the correct way to remove the nuts?	How do you ensure that you do not misunderstand a my request or need?

Table 3. A few examples from our dataset that the system was evaluated on.

Fig. 3. The figure shows our agentic implementation of the perceptive task guidance system. The agents are categorized into perceptrs, planners and action agents. The agents are autonomous and rely either on LLMs or alternative deep learning models to accomplish their task. The agentic pipeline consists of fixed flow and dynamic flows. The dynamic flows involves planner invoked components. The plan generated by the planner is converted into agent invocations (Routers).

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Fig. 4. Shows more examples of dynamic flows in the agentic flow. The examples show the input question from the users in the Perceptor. The Lead planner creates the plan and creates the Route which consists of agent calls. RAG consists of spec documents for each toy which is further chunked. The RAG module further converts the input context into a query to the database. The retrieved document along with the inputs is passed to the following agents. The Response generation module consists of planners which decides if the context is sufficient to answer the question or not. The answer planner then invokes the expert question generator or the answer generator. The responses are always verified before publishing the responses to the users.

Mitigating LLM Hallucinations with Knowledge Graphs: A Case Study

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Fig. 1. The LinkQ system [15], a natural language interface that combats an LLM's tendency to hallucinate by instructing it to answer users' questions by creating and executing knowledge graph (KG) queries. LinkQ ensures all data retrieved and summarized by the LLM comes from ground truth, up-to-date data in the KG.

High-stakes domains like cyber operations need responsible and trustworthy AI methods. While large language models (LLMs) are becoming increasingly popular in these domains, they still suffer from hallucinations. This research paper provides learning outcomes from a case study with LinkQ, an open-source natural language interface that was developed to combat hallucinations by forcing an LLM to query a knowledge graph (KG) for ground-truth data during question-answering (QA). We conduct a quantitative evaluation of LinkQ using a well-known KGQA dataset, showing that the system outperforms GPT-4 but still struggles with certain question categories – suggesting that alternative query construction strategies will need to be investigated in future LLM querying systems. We discuss a qualitative study of LinkQ with two domain experts using a real-world cybersecurity KG, outlining these experts' feedback, suggestions, perceived limitations, and future opportunities for systems like LinkQ.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Information extraction**; • **Human-centered computing** → **Interactive systems and tools**; **Natural language interfaces**; **Visualization systems and tools**; • **Information systems** → **Question answering**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Large language models, knowledge graphs, visual analytics.

Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170463

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI) methods is crucial for high-stakes domains to avoid unintended and potentially catastrophic consequences of using AI-enabled systems [2, 6]. As large enterprises and government

Fig. 2. An overview of LinkQ’s [15] human-in-the-loop system design, described in Section 2. The LLM, System, and User have their own responsibilities for completing the question-to-query translation: the LLM constructs queries, the System works to illuminate possible hallucinations, and the User iterates with the System and LLM to modify, refine, or follow-up on generated queries.

entities adopt Responsible AI policies [12], it is important for the research community to develop AI capabilities that help operators not just understand a model’s outputs, but also provide them with the tools to interrogate and question the data associated with a model [11, 23].

Large language models (LLMs) have gained popularity in national security applications [5, 17, 19], partly for their ability to support question-answering over large amounts of text that operators cannot keep up with alone [21]. However, LLMs still produce hallucinations, biases, and “*intentional lies*” [16], which can lead to inaccurate, misleading results and ultimate distrust in AI [9]. This workshop paper provides learning outcomes for this area of research through two new evaluations of the LinkQ system [15]. LinkQ is a natural language interface system that combats an LLM’s tendency to hallucinate during question-answering by forcing the LLM to answer users’ questions by constructing and executing queries to a knowledge graph (KG). KGs are used to store complex, meaningful knowledge in graph form as a collection of nodes (*entities*), edges (*relations*), and properties (*attributes*). Due to their robustness, KGs are a popular data structure for many real-world applications such as question-answering and recommendation [1, 7, 10, 14, 22].

We conducted a quantitative evaluation using a standardized KG question-answering (KGQA) dataset [20] (Section 3), as well as a qualitative study with two domain experts using the BRON [8] cybersecurity KG (Section 4). Our quantitative evaluation shows that LinkQ strongly outperforms OpenAI’s GPT-4 in generating accurate KG queries, but could not answer all question types with ideal accuracy. This suggests that, while LinkQ can be used for more trustworthy question-answering, future querying strategies will need to be implemented for better generalizability. Our qualitative study illuminates a real-world scenario of domain experts using an LLM to query a domain-specific KG, opening new directions of research in this area of LLM-based question-answering without hallucinations.

2 LINKQ SYSTEM DESIGN

LinkQ uses a prompting protocol illustrated in Figure 2, in which the LLM works with the System to query a KG based on the user’s questions. The exact prompts and algorithmic protocols used for LinkQ are explained in more detail in LinkQ’s original publication [15] and are available open source at <https://github.com/mit-ll/linkq>.

First, the user and LLM engage in a back-and-forth dialogue to ensure a well-formed KG query can be written (Figure 1). To construct the query, the LLM and System work together to fuzzy search for entities (‘nodes’), find relevant relations (‘edges’), and traverse the KG to identify all the correct data IDs. Whenever the LLM needs to access data

in the KG, LinkQ intercepts these requests and calls the appropriate KG API, then passes the KG graph structure and ground-truth IDs to the LLM via System messages.

Finally, the system provides the LLM with few-shot training [4] to write an accurate KG query. LinkQ visually displays the ground-truth query results in tabular format and provides an LLM-generated summary of the results. By having the LLM generate a query instead of directly answering the user’s question, LinkQ both mitigates LLM hallucinations and retrieves up-to-date data for its answers.

3 QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION OF LINKQ

We conducted a quantitative evaluation to test LinkQ’s capabilities in mitigating hallucinations by generating accurate queries from *realistic* (i.e. not overly simplistic) natural language questions, using the Wikidata KG [24]. We compared LinkQ to a standalone LLM (OpenAI’s GPT-4) to understand when LinkQ’s prompting strategy (Figure 2) performs well or poorly. The entirety of our quantitative evaluation is available at <https://github.com/mit-ll/linkq>.

3.1 Evaluation Design

Complexity Type	Topic	Exemplar Question
Multi-hop	books	Where was the Nobel Prize in Literature winner from 2002 born?
Comparative	sports	Who has won more NBA Season MVPs, LeBron James or Steph Curry?
Yes/No	politics	Was John Adams the second president of the United States?
Generic	history	What year did Marie Curie win the Nobel Prize for Chemistry?
Intersection	music	Which member of the New Kids on the Block was the brother of Mark Wahlberg?

Table 1. A subset of questions that we tested LinkQ on, from the Mintaka [20] *complex questions* dataset.

Dataset and Question Selection: We selected a portion of questions from the Mintaka [20] Wikidata question bank, focusing on 5 question types that we posited to be *realistic* for natural language to KG query generation: (1) **Multi-hop**, (2) **Comparative**, (3) **Yes/No**, (4) **Generic**, and (5) **Intersection**. An example of each question type we tested is shown in Table 1. We randomly selected 3 questions for each of the 8 domain topics (history, music, etc.), ensuring all chosen questions adhered to these criteria: (1) the question can be objectively answered, (2) the answer is not dependent on out-of-date data, and (3) the answer can be currently found in Wikidata. For Yes/No questions, we selected an even split of “yes” and “no” answers. For Comparative questions, we did not select any that could result in a binary answer to avoid overlap with Yes/No questions. In total, our evaluation dataset has 120 questions (5 types \times 8 topics \times 3 questions).

Baseline: We used off-the-shelf GPT-4 as the baseline method, instructing it to generate an appropriate KG query that finds the answer in Wikidata. Comparing the results of LinkQ (which uses GPT-4 under the hood, along with its message passing and prompting strategy) against plain GPT-4 provides evidence of how well LinkQ’s prompting strategies improve upon the usage of a standalone LLM for KG query generation.

Correctness Criteria: We executed each of the questions from our curated dataset **three independent times** to account for the probabilistic nature of LLMs with non-zero temperatures [3]. If LinkQ or GPT-4 produced a correct answer *at least once* from those three attempts, it was counted as a correct answer. An incorrect answer could be due to a query that is syntactically incorrect, finds a wrong answer, or returns empty results.

3.2 Analysis of Results

Fig. 3. Results from our quantitative evaluation (Section 3) comparing LinkQ (blue) and GPT-4 (orange). Left: LinkQ and GPT-4’s overall question accuracy on 24 questions for each question type (x-axis), with a breakdown showing the number of correct attempts per question (y-axis). Right: LinkQ versus GPT-4’s runtime to generate a corresponding query.

LinkQ outperformed GPT-4 in accuracy for every question type tested, indicating that LinkQ’s message passing and prompting strategy increases the objective correctness (and consequently the runtime) of an LLM in translating natural language questions to KG queries without any fine-tuning. Figure 3 shows the full results.

The **Comparative** question type resulted in LinkQ’s highest performance (91.7%), while the **Yes/No** type resulted in GPT-4’s (54.2%). Since Yes/No questions were the only tested complexity type that could result in a binary true or false, it is possible that GPT-4’s performance on this type is due to random chance – since all other question categories resulted in far lower accuracy for GPT-4. In general, Comparative, Yes/No and Generic question types are common across knowledge graph question-answering (KGQA) sets, as they reflect low-level analysis questions that users would typically ask – e.g., when using a natural language interface for initial data exploration. LinkQ’s performance on these categories suggests that using its prompting strategy is sufficient when answering straightforward analysis questions.

The complexity of Multi-hop questions (which require at least two steps to answer correctly) is reflected in our evaluation results (LinkQ: 75%, GPT-4: 16.7%) as well as the runtime required to translate. Based on LinkQ’s (54.2%) and GPT-4’s (12.5%) performance on Intersection questions (which require pattern-matching on two or more conditions to answer correctly), they seem the most difficult for an LLM to correctly translate into KG queries.

Learning Outcomes: Future systems should explore how breaking a complex question down into smaller steps—perhaps by following a chain-of-thought approach—could improve performance. Altogether, our results suggest that systems like LinkQ can perform well on writing KG queries that look for data existence, conduct fact-checking, and retrieve data from more than one to two hops away. However, certain complex questions that are Multi-hop, Intersection – and possibly others we did not include in this evaluation – will need further prompting strategies if avoiding fine-tuning. Ultimately, if the LLM is unsuccessful in translating a question into a KG query, the LLM should ask the user to help it transform the query step-by-step (i.e. follow LinkQ’s human-in-the-loop approach) to avoid it hallucinating.

4 QUALITATIVE STUDY WITH DOMAIN EXPERTS

We discuss the results of a qualitative study with the BRON [8] knowledge graph with two subject matter experts (SMEs). BRON is a cybersecurity graph database that connects MITRE’s ATT&CK MATRIX of Tactics and Techniques,

NIST’s Common Weakness Enumerations, NIST’s Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures, and NIST’s Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification list. While these data sources on their own are informative, they are highly dependent on one another. Therefore, BRON—a unification of these independent data sources—provides necessary context to cybersecurity experts who investigate the linkage of cyber alerts, threats, and vulnerabilities [18]. At the time of this writing, our tests suggest GPT-4 has not been trained on BRON, which could result in it hallucinating if SMEs wanted to ask questions about BRON without LinkQ.

LinkQ Demonstration: As BRON is extremely domain-specific, we worked with two subject matter experts in cybersecurity who are end-users of BRON. These SMEs do not consider themselves KG experts; regardless, they must use BRON in their own daily work. Both SMEs sought to test whether LinkQ could be used to support their previous work with BRON. The first question they asked LinkQ was: “*Give me a list of all available APTs [advanced persistent threats],*” an entity type in BRON that represents cyberattacker groups, “*and all of their properties.*” LinkQ successfully wrote and executed the query to retrieve all APTs and their properties. From this list, the SMEs had LinkQ (successfully) retrieve all possible *techniques* associated with a specific APT, which would inform them of the methodologies behind a cyberattack of interest. Finally, we asked the SMEs to think of an example of a particularly difficult question they had tried to answer previously with BRON. The question was a method of aggregating BRON data: “*For all the APTs, what are the top five most common techniques used among all of them?*” Both SMEs were surprised to see that LinkQ generated the answer to their question. See Figure 1 for an example of querying BRON.

Learning Outcomes: We find that LinkQ is successful, but not 100%, at querying the domain-specific KG BRON. At the start of our live demonstration, both SMEs were skeptical of LinkQ being capable of extracting specific relationships in BRON, as they believed BRON was too complex to for an LLM to navigate. One SME described the difficulty they faced for writing queries to identify all possible paths in BRON between multiple node types (e.g., finding techniques that are associated with APTs – as tested in our demonstration), as it requires an in-depth understanding of the BRON schema. This finding highlights the ability of LinkQ to support question-answering over domain-specific KGs, thus addressing an LLM’s tendency to hallucinate when it does not know the answer to domain-specific questions.

Throughout the demonstration, LinkQ did not hallucinate false query results but at times stated there was no associated data with the user’s question (i.e. the query would return no results) – when in fact the data did exist. Empty results most often occurred when the LLM did not thoroughly explore the KG to capture the needed structure of the query. Since the SMEs were familiar with the BRON KG, they were often able to iterate with LinkQ to correct the query (e.g., by specifying the correct relationships); of course, this is a more difficult task if the end-user is not an expert with the KG. Along with this limitation, both SMEs had a number of suggestions for improving LinkQ for their use cases:

- **Give users the ability to edit the initial LLM instructions so they can specify what data they care about.** SMEs noted that the LLM would retrieve data they knew was irrelevant for their task. They suggested it would be helpful if they could edit the initial system prompt to tell the LLM which data to ignore or highlight.
- **Allow users to query for entities based on their written descriptions, rather than their properties.** One SME wanted the LLM to query BRON based on the descriptions for nodes contained in the graph database, rather than searching based on names. In this case, a RAG [13] approach might be preferred over LinkQ’s approach to Q&A.
- **Determine a ranked list of potential queries (or query results) when the LLM is uncertain.** Both SMEs told us they wanted to see multiple query versions of their question so they could determine which one to execute, especially when the LLM may have translated it incorrectly. Future work will need to investigate the cost-to-benefit ratio of this, or offer it as an optional feature that can be selected or deselected by the end-user.

- **Provide extra semantic context for entities or properties in the KG from external data sources.** SMEs noted that missing data about entities in BRON could be found from other cyber frameworks and suggested that it would be beneficial if future systems could supplement its query results with additional context from external sources.

5 CONCLUSION

This workshop paper evaluated the efficacy of using LinkQ to mitigate LLM hallucinations by generating knowledge graph queries that retrieve up-to-date, ground-truth data. Our quantitative evaluation showed that LinkQ outperforms GPT-4 in accurately answering questions through the construction of KG queries, although it still struggles with certain complex question types. From a qualitative study with practitioners on a real-world cybersecurity KG, we found that LinkQ exceeded expectations for converting NL questions to KG queries, supporting them in answering domain-specific questions that an LLM would otherwise not know the answers to. We presented concrete opportunities for improving future systems like LinkQ that still leverage its grounded question-answering capabilities while addressing additional real-world needs. Overall, our evaluations of LinkQ suggest that LLMs can be adapted for high-stakes domains when designed with appropriate guardrails to combat hallucinations so they can be used responsibly.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank our collaborators at MIT Lincoln Laboratory for participating in our qualitative study and offering their feedback on LinkQ to shape future use cases. We also thank the reviewers for their time and thoughtful suggestions to help improve this workshop paper.

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Don't Just Translate, Agitate: Using Large Language Models as Devil's Advocates for AI Explanations

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This position paper highlights a growing trend in Explainable AI (XAI) research where LLMs are used to *translate* outputs from explainability techniques, like feature-attribution weights, into a natural language explanation. While this approach may improve accessibility or readability for users, recent findings suggest that translating into human-like explanations does not necessarily enhance user understanding and may instead lead to overreliance on AI systems. When LLMs summarize XAI outputs without surfacing model limitations, uncertainties, or inconsistencies, they risk reinforcing the illusion of interpretability rather than fostering meaningful transparency. We argue that—instead of merely translating XAI outputs—LLMs should serve as constructive agitators, or *devil's advocates*, whose role is to actively interrogate AI explanations by presenting alternative interpretations, potential biases, training data limitations, and cases where the model's reasoning may break down. In this role, LLMs can facilitate users in engaging critically with AI systems and generated explanations, with the potential to reduce overreliance caused by misinterpreted or specious explanations.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Information extraction**; **Reasoning about belief and knowledge**; **Natural language generation**; • **Human-centered computing** → **Interactive systems and tools**; **Natural language interfaces**; **HCI theory, concepts and models**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Large language models, explainable AI, trustworthy AI, interpretability.

Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170455

1 INTRODUCTION

The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) and multimodal LLMs [29] as versatile reasoning tools has driven a recent trend of integrating them into Explainable AI (XAI) workflows. The prevailing approach is to feed XAI outputs (e.g., encodings of feature attributions generated from frameworks like SHAP [17] or LIME [21]) into these generative models, and then prompt the models to create more natural-sounding translations of the explanations [6, 9, 11, 13, 16, 32, 33]. There are several motivations for this approach, beyond accessibility:

- *Transforming the user task from synthesis and agreement, to just agreement.* Many people want to interpret explanations as natural-language *narratives* for improved ease of interpretability [32], but popular explainer methods like SHAP do not output explanations that can be easily transformed into useful narratives. Users must first interpret the raw explanation and then decide whether it supports the model's decision.
- *"When you've got it, flaunt it."* Generative AI tools like ChatGPT, Copilot, etc., are becoming commonplace tools in work environments where XAI is readily-deployable today for ML developers. At a glance, translating structured explanation outputs into text narratives is the kind of thing GenAI *should* be good at—relying on massive language training to form intelligible, context-bearing sentences around feature information.

While these motivations are reasonable, we argue that LLMs could exacerbate—rather than help—known risks with XAI if the LLM is not integrated in careful, strategic ways.

In this workshop paper, we examine how LLMs are currently being integrated for XAI and outline an alternative path forward. In Sec. 2, we highlight from the literature where cracks emerge in LLM-based explanation translation and dialogue support for counterfactuals. In Sec. 3, we introduce a contrary approach to these previous works: rather than instructing LLMs to produce agreeable explanations, we provide jumping-off points for few-shot training an LLM-based *devil's advocate* [4] specifically for XAI—one that actively challenges, contextualizes, and problematizes

model outputs. Finally, in Sec. 4 we discuss future opportunities for LLM-based approaches to better align with the goals of the underlying decision-support mission and foster critical engagement rather than passive agreement.

2 LLMs FOR XAI, TODAY

While XAI has seen success, especially “left of deployment” (e.g., helping ML developers discover and correct spurious model behaviors [17, 21]), there remains challenges for users who rely on AI explanations for decision support. People using AI systems as tools have limited time and attention, and they often prioritize their decision tasks over sanity-checking the AI. Moreover, they bring with them a panoply of cognitive biases related to information processing and sensemaking, and an AI-generated explanation is not immune from those biases. Recent work has focused on using LLMs with the goal of making them *less prone to interpretation errors* than the raw XAI output [31]—we discuss further below.

Producing Explanation Narratives and Summaries. A typical approach is to use LLMs to create natural language explanations from structured feature-attribution explanations in order to make them more accessible and easier to understand. Various pipelines have been proposed to ensure that these natural language explanations are intelligible. For example, Zytek et al. quantitatively demonstrated LLMs can construct good quality explanation narratives from SHAP feature values [17], and showed that users overall preferred LLM-based narrative explanations over plots of SHAP values in a comparative study (N=20) due to their ease of understanding and informativeness [33]. Their resultant system Explingo [32] uses a pipeline of *narrator* and *grader* LLM components they developed to produce and score candidate explanation narratives from the SHAP features values produced alongside the classifier decision.

A key finding was that having few-shot exemplar narratives that map between the structured SHAP values and a narrative—both hand-written and bootstrapped ones (e.g., produced automatically to fulfill baseline scoring criteria from the *grader* component)—were important to ensure that new LLM narratives were sensible to human evaluators. In other words, the LLM alone could not translate between the SHAP vectors to natural language while maintaining the criteria of accuracy, conciseness, completeness, and fluency. Consequently, few-shot exemplars may be difficult to write a priori, and their effectiveness or completeness as exemplars might depend on the decision domain.

AI Explanations in High-Stakes Decision Domains. Similar narrative-generation approaches have been applied in complex decision domains like classifiers for cybersecurity (e.g., network intrusion detection [16]). In these scenarios, a user’s assessment about an AI output may greatly impact their downstream actions, so explanations should help a user reject the output when the model is wrong. But studies often lack convincing evaluations to demonstrate that narratives help users detect AI errors better than the AI outputs alone or ‘raw’ explainer-generated explanations.

Presenting Explanations of Counterfactual Explanations. LLMs have also been used to summarize explanations focused on helping users interpret model behaviors through *counterfactual* examples. Crisan et al. [6] conducted a small study (N=10) to explore how different counterfactual explanations [27] (which were presented with a visualization of LIME [21] and an LLM-generated summary) affected users’ perceptions of the underlying model’s correctness, fairness, and trustworthiness. Overall, the study demonstrated that LLM-presented counterfactual example (CFE) outputs with LIME do not inherently improve understanding or trust calibration. Participants often struggled to make sense of LLM-explained LIME feature attributions, finding that numerical importance scores lacked meaningful context and that LLM-generated summaries made explanations sound more plausible rather than more transparent. Some users

accepted the explanations at face value, while others dismissed them when they clashed with their mental model of the data, revealing a tendency toward confirmation bias rather than critical engagement.

Conversational LLM-Based XAI Assistants. Interestingly, large language models as XAI assistants can now support freeform questions from the user rather than generating a 'one size fits all' explanation. This is a compelling idea, but so far research shows that overreliance on AI [2] is not necessarily solved by using an LLM. Recently, He et al. [13] studied the effects of a conversational XAI assistant, in which users could engage in a back-and-forth with an LLM for their explainability questions. The authors conducted a large-scale empirical study (N=306) in a loan approval task, comparing this LLM-based conversational XAI assistant to a static XAI dashboard as well as a rule-based conversational XAI assistant. Four XAI methods were employed (SHAP, PDP [10], Mace [28], the What-If Tool [20], and a Decision Tree [22]), enabling the assistant to answer a variety of questions. Unsurprisingly, the LLM-based XAI assistant produced natural and persuasive explanations, which resulted in higher user engagement and perceived trust in the AI system. However, the authors found that these highly plausible LLM-generated responses led to users misplacing their trust in the AI system, even when its predictions were incorrect—aligning with previous findings in which users overrelied on incorrect AI suggestions, even when provided with explanations [2].

Takeaways. While these findings reveal possible failure modes for LLMs in XAI, we argue in Sec. 3 that reframing the role of an LLM in XAI into one that challenges the structured explanation outputs from XAI (and where users are encouraged to interpret the LLM's outputs with healthy skepticism) can create an upside from the general limitations of LLMs, like the tendency to smooth over model inconsistencies persuasively rather than surface them [13].

3 NUDGING A HELPFUL ASSISTANT INTO A HELPFUL ADVERSARY

The explainability pitfalls mentioned in Sec. 2 risk being worsened with LLMs, as they are often instructed to explain XAI outputs as “simply” and “naturally” as possible to non-experts [33]. Consequently, users may passively accept rather than critically engage with smoothed-over explanations—making them less likely to dispute an AI system's (potentially incorrect) decision [13].

If we cannot rule out LLMs from producing unfaithful or placebic explanations that might unjustifiably engender more user trust [8], then perhaps the XAI community should think about roles for LLMs more akin to a helpful adversary. In domains like law and economics, helpful adversaries in the form of opposing litigators and activist investors can surface the truth toward ends like justice and fair market prices. In fact, Chiang et al. recently experimented with creating a LLM-powered *devil's advocate* to assist in group decision-making regarding AI recommendations, and found that it was perceived as a useful collaborator in helping the group develop appropriate trust in another AI's recommendations [4]. We aim to apply this idea to XAI, where the devil's advocate can help users arrive at more correct interpretations of explainer outputs rather than only producing a compliant natural-language translation. In this setting, the devil's advocate has additional *context* about the AI-under-test beyond its prediction/recommendation in the form of the explainer outputs, but it is possible that this context leads to multiple (perhaps conflicting) rationales about the model's behavior. Users who reckon with the incompleteness or ambiguity in an explanation should have better-justified system reliance and improved decision outcomes compared to trusting a single, plausible narrative. If we expect the latter to be the typical response when prompting an LLM to “*Help me make sense...*”, then what prompting strategies could help move users beyond this?

Adversarial Strategy	Input Prompt
Uncertainty Awareness	Instead of presenting every AI decision as fact, you should surface uncertainty and highlight the conditions under which an explanation might be unreliable, e.g., <i>“The model is 78% confident in this classification, but the decision boundary is unstable. Here are alternative inputs to probe the model...”</i>
Alternative Explanations	Instead of treating a single explanation as absolute, you should present multiple interpretations and counter-explanations, prompting users to compare them, e.g., <i>“LIME suggests Feature X is most important, but SHAP highlights Feature Y instead. Here are possible reasons why they differ...”</i>
Bias Detection	Instead of smoothing potential flaws in the model, you should interrogate its outputs for potential bias or fairness issues and alert users when disparities exist, e.g., <i>“This model’s predictions for Group A differ significantly from Group B. Here is an analysis for whether this is a fairness issue...”</i>
Counterfactual Thinking	Instead of promoting a linear exploration, you should encourage counterfactual investigation, helping users see how slight input changes would alter predictions, e.g., <i>“If Feature X were reduced by 10%, the model’s decision would flip. Here are some other similar scenarios that flip the model’s output...”</i>
Scrutinize Assumptions	Instead of letting users rely on flawed mental models, you should encourage them to re-examine their own biases when they disagree with AI predictions, e.g., <i>“You disagree with this prediction, but could there be factors influencing the model’s decision that aren’t obvious?”</i>
Explanation Audit	Instead of presenting XAI outputs as infallible, you should demonstrate that explanations are simplifications and may not fully capture model behavior, e.g., <i>“SHAP assumes feature independence, which may not hold in this case. Here is an example of its limitations in this scenario...”</i>
User-Calibrated Depth	Instead of explaining a model’s prediction in the same manner every time, you should adjust the level of explanation dynamically based on how you perceive the user’s expertise and preferences, e.g., <i>“Based on your previous questions, here is a deep dive into the feature attributions for Output X...”</i>

Table 1. Prompting strategies for an LLM devil’s advocate that leverages XAI to challenge AI outputs.

Prompting Approaches. We think there is potential in reshaping LLM prompts as a means of producing more engaging interpretations of XAI outputs. First, it may be important to reframe the relationship between the user and the LLM in the prompt. For example, some LLM-based systems begin with an initial prompt to explain the overarching task (e.g., *“You are a helpful XAI assistant...”*). Alternatively, level-setting for more scrutiny of the XAI could work to surface alternative interpretations, e.g., *“You are a helpful XAI adversary, promoting healthy skepticism in AI...”* Then, examples of desired inputs and outputs in the prompt can help the LLM perform better at the task (few-shot in-context learning) without fine-tuning [1]. In Table 1, we provide a list of prompt exemplars (organized by different strategies) that can be used as a springboard for future research and exploration. We note that these were synthesized based on shortcomings found in naively-prompted LLM translations of XAI explanations, but empirical evaluations are ultimately needed to assess the effectiveness of these strategies.

4 LLMS FOR XAI, TOMORROW

With advances in generative AI coming at a rapid pace, it is hard to know exactly what the goals and methods of XAI will look like on the distant horizon. It is possible that advanced generative AI models may wholly replace some of the classifiers whose outputs and XAI-generated explanations (e.g., SHAP values, saliency maps) have been translated into narratives using LLMs. New architectures that produce and use reasoning tokens (e.g., OpenAI’s o1 [15] and o3, DeepSeek’s R1 [12], and Gemini 2.0 Flash Thinking [7]) are likely to improve the quality of generated responses and

lead to new ways of interrogating the reliability of the model's process. A chain-of-thought reasoning step is already part of some existing XAI LLM systems like Explingo [32]. But as we have seen, even with highly-skilled LLMs, users still need a method (and the will) to engage interrogatively with an AI explanation: *it is a human-AI interaction challenge, not just a technology hurdle.*

In the remainder of this section, we discuss workflows and research directions that could lead users to new ways of working with XAI and LLM devil's advocates to arrive at better insights and decisions.

Use LLMs to Explore Different Theories of the Case. One key use case LLMs can help in is generating counterfactual explanations for what is needed to change a prediction based on information from the explainer. Rather than simply summarizing the explanations in natural language, the LLM can provide useful insights and counterfactual scenarios to test the limits of the explanations. Fredes et al. [9] and Giorgi et al. [11] present methods of using LLMs to generate natural language explanations based on a set of counterfactuals for different AI systems.

We can extend these types of approaches to allow LLMs to serve as devil's advocates for counterfactual explanations. One option is to increase the temperature of LLMs [18, 19] in generating these explanations to provide more variance in the outputted explanation. Another direction could be to challenge the weighted outputs of the counterfactual explainer, rather than taking them as ground truth. For example, when considering a loan application, a counterfactual explainer might output that if the applicant made \$5000 more in salary, they would have been approved. But an LLM can interrogate the counterfactual given and provide alternatives for the user to analyze. LLMs could also help to highlight systematic model biases—such as an overreliance on a particular feature that may be correlated with training data biases (e.g., demographic information). With the ability to understand the model internals plus nuances of the world, an LLM can provide a combination of global and local context to dispute and improve these counterfactual explanations.

Support Evidence for a Jury of Decision Makers, Not a Mechanical Judge. It is frequently discussed that different types of users (e.g., model developers versus decision makers [23–25]) need different types of explanations to support their workflows, such as outlined in the study by Hoffman et al. [14]. This was echoed in recent studies that found users preferred LLM narratives over SHAP and LIME diagrams [6, 33]. It is well known in the XAI community that these commonly used diagrams are confusing to non-experts—future research should address the lack of interpretable XAI visualizations, rather than relying on LLMs to translate them for the end-user.

As an alternative approach, LLMs can be used for different persona-based prompting regimes depending on who the explanation is targeted for. For example, in a medical diagnosis XAI system, the LLM can have a highly technical persona when providing explanations to a doctor or medical student [3], or use layman's terms when communicating to a patient or family member. These different levels of explanatory descriptions can be based off the same XAI output but customized for the target audience. While this might simply sound like a translation problem, LLMs could also guide the thinking of the user to challenge their assumptions. For example, when communicating to a doctor, the LLM could provide a set of possible other diagnoses with associated explanations (this would be reformulating the XAI problem as search and retrieval rather than classification). Furthermore, different modalities of information in an LLM explanation can be conveyed to the user; for instance, a natural language explanation with a supporting visualization.

Design for a Productive Adversarial Process. Creating more mentally demanding workflows around AI outputs has its own tradeoffs. Bućinca et al.'s study [2] found that *cognitive forcing* interventions—which prime a user's deliberative thinking about an AI output—can help the user make more correct decisions in cases where the AI model is

incorrect. However, users gave these interventions the lowest favorability ratings, reporting lower trust and preference for designs that most effectively reduced overreliance. This presents a fundamental challenge for designing devil’s advocate-style explainability systems: while friction and cognitive effort could improve decision-making, they may also reduce user satisfaction and long-term adoption.

To combat this tradeoff, developers can consider structuring engagement around success metrics, incentives, and usability improvements. For example, we could leverage concepts from game theory [5, 26] to make critical engagement more rewarding by having users “defend” their decisions against counterfactual reasoning before finalizing an action. These systems could also incorporate progressive difficulty by starting with simple explanations and gradually introducing more complex challenges as users demonstrate comfort. Finally, creating structured workflows that acknowledge thoughtful decision-making—such as visualizing the impact of users’ skepticism over time or providing trust calibration feedback—could help the user feel they are being guided through nuanced exploration of an AI system rather than interrogated for their prior beliefs. Regardless, there will inevitable difficulties in employing a devil’s advocate when users are accustomed to helpful chat assistants [30]; research will need to explore the balance between the two personas.

5 CONCLUSION

The widespread use of LLMs to translate XAI outputs (e.g., SHAP, LIME, CFEs) into narrative explanations assumes that natural language improves user understanding. However, recent studies suggest that this translation-based approach is insufficient and can even be counterproductive—leading to overreliance, misplaced trust, and superficial engagement with AI decisions. LLM-generated explanations often make model outputs appear more plausible rather than more transparent, and conversational XAI assistants smooth over inconsistencies which risk reinforcing cognitive biases. To address these challenges, this workshop paper proposes a shift from LLMs as passive translators to instead serve as devil’s advocates. Although this approach may introduce user discomfort, adversarial reasoning can begin to combat overconfidence and promote deeper engagement with AI systems. Future work should investigate how LLM-driven XAI systems can dynamically adjust explanation depth, provide active counterfactual reasoning, and challenge overreliance to ensure that explanations genuinely support better decision-making, rather than making AI outputs easier to accept.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the organizers of the HCXAI workshop as well as the reviewers for their time and helpful feedback in improving the quality of our paper.

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Explainable AI in Usable Privacy and Security: Challenges and Opportunities

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Large Language Models (LLMs) are increasingly being used for automated evaluations and explaining them. However, concerns about explanation quality, consistency, and hallucinations remain open research challenges, particularly in high-stakes contexts like privacy and security, where user trust and decision-making are at stake. In this paper, we investigate these issues in the context of PRISMe, an interactive privacy policy assessment tool that leverages LLMs to evaluate and explain website privacy policies. Based on a prior user study with 22 participants, we identify key concerns regarding LLM judgment transparency, consistency, and faithfulness, as well as variations in user preferences for explanation detail and engagement. We discuss potential strategies to mitigate these concerns, including structured evaluation criteria, uncertainty estimation, and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). We identify a need for adaptive explanation strategies tailored to different user profiles for LLM-as-a-judge. Our goal is to showcase the application area of usable privacy and security to be promising for Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI) to make an impact.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Usable Privacy, LLMs, Explainability, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170451

1 Introduction

With increasing cybersecurity threats – e.g., through the growing number of devices introducing more vulnerabilities – and privacy threats – such as user data being used to train AI models – empowering and informing users about these risks has become increasingly important. This is underscored by the fact that most cybersecurity incidents are facilitated by human error [43]. In the field of usable privacy and security, model judgements and explanations and the effective handling of hallucination scenarios are particularly important, as users’ sensitive data is at stake and misguided judgments can have severe consequences. A promising approach, which has already gained traction in other research fields and holds potential for usable privacy and security, is utilizing LLM-as-a-judge [14, 49]. This approach involves instructing an LLM to evaluate a given document and assign scores. However, despite its potential, key challenges remain unresolved. The explainability of LLM-generated scores, beyond instructing the LLM to self-report its reasoning, remains underexplored. Additionally, tailoring these explanations to different user profiles to enhance their effectiveness in the context of usable security and privacy has yet to be investigated. Furthermore, hallucinations in LLM-as-a-judge scenarios remain largely unexamined, and mitigation strategies have yet to be explored.

Our specific use case motivating this research is PRISMe, an interactive privacy policy assessment tool we designed [12]. It employs an LLM-as-a-judge approach to evaluate and rate privacy policies, providing users with an

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overview while incorporating a conversational component that allows them to ask questions about the policy. Understanding how users interact with explanations provided by such a tool is crucial to ensure understanding, trust, and good decision making [18], as well as determining which types of explanations are most helpful for different user groups. Our goal is to maximize users’ privacy and security awareness without exposing them to unintended risks, such as misinterpretation or a false sense of security.

While multiple benchmarks assess LLM hallucinations in question-answering settings [17] and allow to transfer insights to PRISMe, such an understanding is still lacking for LLM-as-a-judge as in our initial policy assessment. While our previous work [12] has focused on discussing issues and potential solutions for the interactive chat component, we aim to focus on the LLM-as-a-judge component here.

In particular, we identify the following areas for future research and outline our initial thoughts on addressing them:

- Investigating how different user types interact with LLM-generated explanations in the context of privacy and security (addressing individual factors influencing explainability needs of different users building on Li et al. [24]).
- Customizing LLM-as-a-judge assessments for different user profiles to enhance interpretability and effectiveness.
- Continuing the trajectory laid out by Abdul et al. [1] and work from previous Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI) research like [7, 8, 18] to create user-tailored, interactive explanations that in our use case help minimize exposure to security and privacy threats.
- Understanding and detecting hallucinations in an LLM-as-a-judge setting and developing mitigation strategies tailored to privacy and security contexts (addressing the when to trust). This continues the research theme of appropriate trust calibration in the HCXAI community [13, 16, 25].

Our goal is to highlight the promising application of usable security and privacy to the HCXAI-community, where studying model explanations and LLM hallucinations from a human-centered perspective involving personalization can have a significant positive impact on lay users.

2 Related Work

Challenges with Privacy Policies

Privacy policies aim to reduce the *information asymmetry* between service providers and users [27, 48]. However, they are often designed for legal compliance, with dense, complex, and lawyer-centric language [38]. This makes it difficult for users to make informed decisions about their privacy online [30, 44]. Legal regulations like the GDPR [10] do not prevent persuasive language, which makes unethical practices even harder to detect [5, 32]. Additionally, such regulations may create a false sense of trust and security. Users rarely read and typically don’t understand privacy policies [33, 39], which leads to informational unfairness [11]. Generative AI [22] and Augmented Reality complicate data management practices further, thereby exacerbating transparency issues [2, 4, 5].

LLM-based privacy policy assessment

LLM-based privacy policy assessment has shown to be as effective as NLP methods in extracting key aspects from privacy policies, such as contact information and third parties [34]. ChatGPT-4 [31] offers performance and adaptability in answering privacy-related questions [15], which motivated our use of LLMs in a interactive privacy policy assessment tool. Privacify [45] is a browser extension performing information extraction and abstract summarization of policies addressing compliance and data collection information. While it lacks interpretation, customization, and interactive features, it further motivated us to utilize the LLM-as-a-judge paradigm in a tool that interprets and explains privacy policies and allows users to interact with the provided information [12]. We explain our tool in Section 3.1.

LLM-as-a-judge

The LLM-as-a-judge paradigm originates from the practice of using LLMs to evaluate other LLM-generated outputs [49]. This approach has been widely applied in text evaluation tasks, where LLMs rate and score input text [14, 23] even evaluated in a RAG setting [46]. Despite becoming a new standard in NLP evaluation, LLM-as-a-judge is subject to biases [6, 46, 47], its judgments do not always align with human assessments [3, 40], and the presented reasoning sometimes is flawed [46], motivating research on LLM explanations.

LLM Explanations

In the field of HCXAI, LLMs are increasingly used to make traditional Explainable AI (XAI) methods' outputs more understandable for humans [50]. LLMs' explanations of their own outputs cannot be seen as mechanistically reflecting their inner workings but rather as samples of post-hoc rationalizations [37]. However, step-by-step self-explanations of the model to derive an output can significantly improve output quality [19, 26]. To ground explanations, citation-based explanations could link to evidence in the context [37]. LLMs explaining themselves could help users to critically reflect, justify, and evaluate if prompted accordingly [36].

Hallucinations

Hallucinations can be defined as the generation of nonsensical outputs or output that is unfaithful to the provided source content [29]. Huang et al. divide hallucinations into ones concerning faithfulness, i.e., whether outputs are faithful to instructions and context given, and ones concerning factuality, i.e., whether outputs are factually correct [17].

3 Use Case: Privacy Risk Information Scanner for Me (PRISMe)

We investigate LLM explanations and hallucinations in the application area of usable privacy and security. To this end, we utilize the exemplary use case of PRISMe, an interactive privacy policy assessment tool. This section explains PRISMe and a previous user study we conducted with it [12].

3.1 System

Figure 1 illustrates PRISMe, the tool we developed. When users visit any website, PRISMe fetches its privacy policy with our scraper utilizing headless browser automation. We automatically analyze its privacy policy, highlighting concerns using smiley icons (Figure 1, top middle). Following the LLM-as-a-judge paradigm, the tool dynamically selects and evaluates criteria on a 5-point Likert scale for policy assessment (see prompts in Appendix A) utilizing GPT-4o [31]. The smiley icon (green, yellow, red) provides a quick summary of the policy's overall rating. Clicking it opens the Overview Panel (Figure 1, left), which summarizes key issues, with links to the dashboard and chat interfaces for further exploration. The Dashboard Panel (Figure 1, bottom middle) displays detailed scores for each assessment criterion, rated with corresponding smiley icons. Below the dashboard, an explanation of each score is provided. Users can further explore specific criteria via the Criteria Chat (Figure 1, right) or use the General Chat for broader privacy-related inquiries. Settings, accessible via a cogwheel icon, allow users to customize the length (short, medium, long) and complexity (beginner, basic, expert) of chat responses and policy assessments, tailoring the tool to their preferences and technical expertise.

3.2 User Study

Utilizing the prototype described above, our prior work contains a user study with 22 participants to evaluate it [12]. Participants used the prototype in three scenarios. In the first scenario, they were instructed to take their time exploring the privacy policies of Paypal and focus.de (a popular German news media website) using PRISMe. The aim was

Fig. 1. When the user visits a website, our prototype evaluates the privacy policy in the background and displays privacy alerts via colored scrollbars and a point-of-entry smiley icon (top middle). Clicking the smiley opens an Overview Panel (left) summarizing key privacy issues, with navigation to a Dynamic Dashboard and chat interface. The dashboard (bottom middle) provides detailed policy evaluation criteria, which users can chat about (right) by clicking the respective "More" button.

to investigate understanding and awareness. The second scenario addressed participants' efficiency using PRISMe: participants compared four online bookshops (Amazon, Hugendubel, Buchkatalog and Kopp), considering the privacy policy evaluations provided by our prototype. The last scenario allowed participants to use our tool on any website of their choice (37 different websites were visited). The aim was to investigate understanding, usability, and awareness.

User studies investigating human perception of XAI often focus on related concepts like trust, understanding, usability, or human-AI collaboration performance [35]. Comments made by participants during the scenarios and in semi-structured interviews on how they perceived assessment transparency and trustworthiness of the tool motivated us to investigate explainability of LLM-as-a-judge and to connect to the HCXAI community. Some participants wanted clear policy evidence to justify specific ratings. They found that the LLM-generated explanations were often overly generic, with little distinction between descriptions for good and bad ratings. Another issue was inconsistency in criteria selection. Participants noted that the LLM interpreted similarly named criteria differently between policies or selected entirely different criteria for similar policies. Additionally, some participants observed incoherence between chat responses and LLM-provided ratings—the explanations justifying ratings sometimes did not align with the sentiment expressed in chat responses. Participants still found LLM provided explanations helpful.

Our study also revealed different user profiles regarding their usage behavior. Besides usage behavior, our profiles take into account participants' self-reported prior knowledge and confidence in their understanding of typical privacy policies and general data protection as collected in a questionnaire before the study. We suspect these groups differ in the way they process LLM explanations and potential hallucinations, raising different requirements for explanation.

- *Targeted Explorers*: Users with prior knowledge who critically inspect evaluations. They prefer specific, extensive explanations and clearly defined evaluation criteria.
- *Novice Explorers*: Users with little prior knowledge who rely on tools like PRISMe for guidance. Their learning goals emerge as they explore. They engage actively and take their time to process information.

- *Information Minimalists*: Users who seek quick, high-level summaries with minimal engagement. They prefer concise overviews rather than interactive exploration.

These diverse information-seeking behaviors require tailored strategies to effectively communicate explanations and foster awareness. This offers ground for fruitful discussions with the HCXAI community.

4 Discussion

This section discusses LLM explanation and hallucination issues, balancing transparency, trust and critical thinking, and the trade-off between explainability and privacy. We take into account the user profiles we have identified.

4.1 Investigating the LLM Explanations and Hallucination Issues

One approach to increase the transparency in an LLM-as-a-judge approach like ours is to reduce the degrees of freedom the LLM has. A fixed criteria catalog with precise definitions and requirements for assigning individual scores could be created. This would likely also improve the judgment accuracy [46]. A drawback of such fixed criteria definitions is that they may be too rigid and unsuitable to accurately evaluate different risk profiles. This could pose risks to *Information Minimalists*, as they mostly rely on initial ratings that in such a case may miss critical information. Also, providing this context does not ensure the LLM actually follows it upon inference. Utilizing output token uncertainty for tokens on the scoring may help judge the LLM's confidence in its judgement [41]. Multiple assessments may be sampled to see where variance in assigned scores occurs may help quantify confidence [28]. Communicating such confidence levels supports all user profiles, particularly *Information Minimalists*. Visualizing attention may also help as a proxy for explanations of what tokens contributed how much to the output [9]. While *Targeted Explorers* are likely happy about additional model explainability to calibrate their level of trust, not overwhelming other user groups with too much additional information is important. Investigating this trade-off could continue the debate on personalizing explanations.

Hallucination scenarios in LLM-as-a-judge use cases have yet to be investigated. The majority of issues may be faithfulness-related. The LLM may ignore the actual policy at hand for evaluation and refer to generic themes. This is supported by the sometimes rather generic explanations the LLM provides for its evaluation. Providing clearly defined criteria definitions in this context may help to translate the evaluation of each individual criterion into a RAG problem. As a benefit, explanations for evaluations are probably more specific and can refer to evidence from the policy, however at large computational costs with multiple RAG-queries being performed for the different criteria. Sampling multiple assessments and checking them for internal consistency is also a common hallucination detection strategy [17, 28] and could help identify unwanted hallucinated evaluation criteria. Communicating specifics and citing evidence effectively supports *Targeted Explorers* to build trust in provided explanations.

Regarding factuality, one problem is that the LLM fabricates actually irrelevant evaluation criteria. Factuality of the Likert-scale ratings is rather difficult to judge as it is not entirely clear what a policy rated with a 4 instead of a 3 on the criterion data minimization should do better. Assigning Likert-scale ratings is always prone to subjectivity and there is no ground truth. The often rather generic self-explanations provided by the LLM for its rating might not suffice. Here, we arrive at a similar conclusion to Sarkar [37] and call for future research, particularly in the LLM-as-a-judge setting.

4.2 Balancing Transparency, Trust, and Critical Thinking

LLM-generated explanations should help users make informed decisions by enabling an appropriate level of reliance instead of blindly trusting the system's judgments [16]. While explanations can mitigate informational unfairness [42], they should also encourage users to reflect critically on privacy policies rather than passively accepting automated

evaluations. Different user profiles require varying levels of customization in explanations [18]. Future research should explore how to personalize explanations effectively while mitigating biases in LLM-as-a-judge frameworks.

A key challenge in the LLM-as-a-judge approach is aligning its outputs and explanations with human judgment. While lay users often show high agreement with LLMs in expert domains, experts tend to disagree more frequently [40]. Experts value factual accuracy, up-to-date and evidence-based content, and prefer concise, precise, and unambiguous language. In contrast, LLMs often produce verbose outputs with generalized reasoning and limited expert-level rationale. Szymanski et al. [40] found that prompting LLMs with expert personas – like we do – can partially reduce this misalignment. However, this comes at the cost of reduced alignment with lay users, who generally prefer less technical language. Incorporating data protection experts into the loop for screening sample assessments to provide clearer guidelines to the LLM judge combined with evidence-based evaluations via RAG should help. To avoid user overwhelm, particularly for *Information Minimalists*, the prompt design needs to counter LLMs’ tendency to favor long and comprehensive responses in complex language. Even though rare, LLM-generated explanations also raise concerns about subjectivity and the risk of confidently justifying incorrect answers [20]. Despite this, they often align well with human explanations. Their tendency toward illustrative examples and selectivity [20] can be seen more as a feature than a bug as it helps users to build an understanding without getting overwhelmed, given the information presented by the LLM includes the most important aspects. The alignment with human explanations is found to likely increase trust, which becomes problematic considering convincing justifications for wrong answers. Particularly *Information Minimalists* and *Novice Explorers* are likely to be misled. To what extent forcing an LLM to verify its answer in a separate step, or to incorporate expert reviews, is an open question, where the HCXAI community could contribute significantly.

4.3 Balancing Privacy and Explainability

There is a tension between privacy and the quality of the explanation provided to users. Running smaller, local LLMs offers improved privacy around user interests and preferences, at the cost of reduced output quality in both the judge and conversational components. By increasing the transparency and quality of the explanations of the LLM-as-a-judge component, there is an increasing risk of service providers slightly modifying their privacy policies to take advantage of lacking adversarial robustness in the LLM and receive better scores without improving their data protection practices. Lakshminarayanan and Gautam [21] already noted such adversarial robustness trade offs for Explainable AI in general. Personalizing assessments requires users to directly or indirectly disclose aspects of their identity, which can compromise privacy, especially if such data is processed by cloud-based models. Inspired by Lakshminarayanan and Gautam [21], we suggest giving the user control by making automated personalization opt-in to protect privacy.

5 Conclusion

As the field of usable privacy and security increasingly relies on opaque LLMs, the need for human-centered explainable AI (HCXAI) approaches to enhance transparency is more critical than ever. Intransparent LLM-generated judgments can undermine user trust and lead to errors, posing significant risks when sensitive user data is at stake. Our work highlights key research gaps to address, including user-adaptive explanations, improved interpretability, and robust strategies for detecting and mitigating hallucinations in LLM-as-a-judge frameworks. Bridging these gaps is essential to ensuring that AI-driven privacy tools are not only effective but also trustworthy and user-centric.

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A Appendix

A.1 Prompting Approach for Initial Assessment Generation

Your output must be a maximum of 600 words long! You are an expert in data protection and a member of an ethics council. You are given a privacy policy. Your task is to uncover aspects in data protection declarations that are ethically questionable from your perspective. Proceed **step by step**:

- (1) **Criteria:** From your perspective, identify relevant ethical test criteria for this privacy policy as criteria for a later evaluation. When naming the test criteria, stick to standardized terms and concepts that are common in the field of ethics. Keep it short!
- (2) **Analysis:** Based on this, check for ethical problems or ethically questionable circumstances in the privacy policy.
- (3) **Evaluation:** Only after you have completed step 2: Rate the privacy policy based on your analysis regarding each of your criteria on a 5-point Likert scale. Explain what this rating means. Explain what the ideal case with 5 points and the worst case with one point would look like. The output in this step should look like this: [Insert rating criterion here]: [insert rating here]/5 [insert line break] [insert justification here]
- (4) **Conclusion:** Reflect on your evaluation and check whether it is complete.

Important: Check for errors in your analysis and correct them if necessary before the evaluation. You must present your approach clearly and concisely and follow the steps mentioned. Your output must not exceed 600 words.

A.2 Prompting Approach for Chat Answer Generation

System prompt criteria chat: Keep it short! Privacy policy: <Privacy policy here> | Rating: <criteria evaluation result here>. Users want to know more about how this rating is justified in the privacy policy. When answering the questions, focus on the given topic of the rating. Keep it short! <Complexity and answer length according to settings>

System prompt general chat: You are an expert in data protection with many years of experience in consumer protection. You have analyzed the following privacy policy and are aware of its risks and ethical implications for users: <Privacy policy here>. You should advise users and explain the implications for them in a conversation. <Complexity and answer length according to settings>

Legally-Informed Explainable AI

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Explanations for artificial intelligence (AI) systems are intended to support the people who are impacted by AI systems in high-stakes decision-making environments, such as doctors, patients, teachers, students, housing applicants, and many others. To protect people and support the responsible development of AI, explanations need to be *actionable*—helping people take pragmatic action in response to an AI system—and *contestable*—enabling people to push back against an AI system and its determinations. For many high-stakes domains, such as healthcare, education, and finance, the sociotechnical environment includes significant legal implications that impact how people use AI explanations. For example, physicians who use AI decision support systems may need information on how accepting or rejecting an AI determination will protect them from lawsuits or help them advocate for their patients. In this paper, we make the case for Legally-Informed Explainable AI, responding to the need to integrate and design for legal considerations when creating AI explanations. We describe three stakeholder groups with different informational and actionability needs, and provide practical recommendations to tackle design challenges around the design of explainable AI systems that incorporate legal considerations.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **HCI theory, concepts and models**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Legally-Informed Explainable AI, actionability, contestability, AI explanations, legal considerations, design challenges

Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170444

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are increasingly involved in high-stakes decision-making by humans, such as healthcare, housing, financial, and educational determinations [19, 27, 37, 45]. Even initial deployments of these systems have shown how error prone they are, from incorrectly prescribed treatments [3] to incorrectly denying insurance coverage [5] or reviewing applications [7]. As a part of responsible AI development, many turn to *Explainable AI (XAI)*—AI systems that provide human-understandable explanations for their reasoning and output [19, 37, 45]. Explanations are intended to support the people—doctors, patients, teachers, students, housing applicants, and many others—who are impacted by decisions made by AI systems.

Users, AI decisions, and the explanations generated by AI systems do not exist in a vacuum but are embedded in a complex sociotechnical environment [39, 56, 71]. Human-Centered Explainable AI [29] has focused on understanding people’s needs to inform and improve explanations for an AI system’s behavior. For example, past HCXAI Workshop papers have highlighted nuances around how explanations need to be tailored to specific users’ context, such as those of older adults aging in place [50] or of people performing manual tasks alongside an AI system in manufacturing [67].

As the concept of explainability has evolved, researchers have emphasized that to achieve transparency and accountability, AI systems do not just need to communicate why or how a decision was made, they also need to enable pragmatic action [20, 41, 42, 47, 61, 65, 68]. That is: they need to be *actionable*. An important class of actionability is *contestation*—a person’s ability to push back against an AI system’s use and its determinations. End user explanations can help individuals make better-informed decisions while calibrating their trust of the AI system [31, 35, 37, 53, 63] and expanding their range of actions [48].

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AI systems, by virtue of making decisions more opaque, can tip the balance of power away from those who are more vulnerable and those advocating for the vulnerable. For example, in healthcare, physicians who use AI decision support systems may have the information at hand to push back against an AI system’s recommendation to advocate for a patient or protect themselves from a malpractice lawsuit [49]. Housing applicants may not know an algorithm has violated their rights and experience increasing housing instability as a result [44]. Should perceived harms occur in the presence of AI decision-support, legal representatives may not be able to audit black box systems [16, 38]. Further complicating matters, those who are affected by AI decisions are especially vulnerable when the laws pertaining to the AI decisions are prone to change suddenly and significantly or when the laws may not be responsive to those technological innovations [13]. All of these scenarios point to the obfuscation of legal rights and options currently perpetuated by AI.

We argue for **Legally-Informed XAI**, responding to the need to design AI explanations to account for the legal concerns of those impacted by AI, to ultimately ensure actionability and contestability. An important theme in HCI research is the *power dynamics* that shape human-AI interactions. The deployment of AI decision-support tools increasingly shifts power toward those deploying the systems. People interacting with AI decision-support tools have reduced agency as a result but are often still responsible, accountable, or liable [64]. The ability to contest AI decisions restores agency to users. However, opaque systems are increasingly hard to contest because it is more challenging to get information demonstrating a system is making a mistake or breaking the law [5]. As a first step, we highlight three groups of stakeholders—*decision makers*, *decision subjects*, and *legal representatives*—along with their legal considerations that need to be accounted for to mitigate the power dynamics exacerbated by algorithmic decision-making tools. We then provide practical recommendations to incorporate legal considerations into AI explanations for responsible AI development.

2 Stakeholders, Actionability, and Contestability

In this section, we detail the legal considerations of three groups of stakeholders from an XAI perspective.

Decision makers are people that act alongside AI systems to make decisions, serving as buffers between AI recommendations and more vulnerable populations. Some decision makers have a legal obligation to work in the best interests of others. For example, medical physicians are called on to provide oversight of AI medical recommendation systems, protecting patients from harmful AI decisions [11, 33, 55]. Decision makers could also include those with relatively weaker legal obligations to act in the best interests of another person, such as those processing job, loan, or housing applications. If decision makers are to protect against or avoid unwanted outcomes, then it is important to support decision makers in understanding their legal liability and contesting improper AI decisions or applications.

Decision subjects are people directly subject to decisions made by an AI system or someone using AI decision-support. Users, developers, and deployers of AI systems sometimes use the black-box nature of the system to evade liability, leaving decision subjects without recourse [5, 51]. For decision subjects, contesting AI systems is fraught with power dynamics, particularly in contexts where decision makers are not incentivized to advocate for decision subjects. Examples of such contexts include tenant screening, loans, insurance claims processing, or public surveillance. Prior work [43, 58] has found that culture and economic precarity can shape perceptions of AI, noting that mistrust of human institutions, feelings of obligation, or fear may result in undue trust in, or acceptance of, AI decisions. We assert that AI systems must provide sufficient information to enable contestation, and that this may often involve information about legal rights.

Legal representatives are people who represent decision subjects, decision makers, technology creators, and others seeking recourse through the courts for harms involving AI systems. While the harmed individual faces a power imbalance in favor of the AI system’s developers and deployers, the legal representative of the harmed party also faces a power differential: they may not have the ability to audit an AI system or to make sense of the raw audit data. For example, Jin and Salehi [38] investigate public defenders scrutinizing computational forensic software and find barriers to building cases against them despite access to performance evaluations, such as difficulties understanding how these technologies are developed and used. Legal representatives can also benefit from explanations, but their informational needs differ from those of their clients. Consequently, there are growing calls to recognize and involve legal representatives when understanding and designing AI systems.

3 An Evolving Technological and Legal Landscape: A Healthcare Case Study

In this section, we take a first step in drawing out the complexities of creating Legally-Informed XAI through an extended case study of medical AI decision systems. Physicians, their patients, and legal representatives are caught in an evolving landscape of technology and law. While we focus on medical AI, the principles we discuss are present in other domains as well, including education, finance, criminal justice, and privacy, among others [14, 44].

There are hopes that AI can improve many aspects of medical care, including workflows, diagnoses, and treatments [34]. However, the integration of AI in actual medical settings has had mixed success. Prominent concerns have been documented including: alert fatigue [69]; incorrectly prescribing cancer treatments [3]; misdiagnosing heart attacks [6, 46]; wrongly denying opioids [4, 8]; difficulty understanding AI recommendations [22]; and accentuation of historical and systemic bias for marginalized groups [11, 15].

Policy changes from national to local levels also impact medical decision making. The last several years have seen large-scale policy changes in the United States in response to new technology, unprecedented medical events, and court rulings. A common failure model of machine learning systems in particular is the inability to respond to rapid changes to the operating environment that causes it to differ from the historical training data on which the system was trained [28]. In the medical domain, for example, the 2020 pandemic saw the emergency authorization of vaccines and treatments [23]. In 2021, the United States Supreme Court issued rulings on women’s health, creating an uneven map of where medical procedures could be performed within the country [25]. Laws and regulations regarding FDA approval processes for medical devices and software incorporating AI also changed [2]. Even hospitals’ guidelines about treatment vary, such as the kinds of antibiotics or procedures that should be followed. Additionally, there are also regular changes around approved or recommended medications, medical devices, and procedures.

3.1 Physicians’ Legal Considerations

Physicians’ legal considerations are closely tied to their needs around *actionable* and *contestable* AI systems. Medical doctors are tasked with making decisions at the intersection of medical knowledge and patients’ values and individual needs [52]. Physicians are and feel accountable for the well-being of their patients and their own livelihoods as they use medical AI systems. Physicians must often make nuanced decisions, such as helping patients decide between cancer treatments to support their quality of life or administering a medication for an unapproved use when other treatments are not working, which may not be recommended by an AI system. Physicians must also advocate for patients, sometimes going against AI recommendations that may be incorrect, or against insurance companies that unjustly deny coverage to patients [5]. Access to legally salient information could help empower physicians to push

back against opaque denials. However, a lack of design around, and access to, these details prevents physicians and others from successfully contesting decisions, leaving patients no choice but to sue for coverage [5].

Additionally, physicians need to protect themselves from legal liability if a patient is harmed by a decision with an AI system [18, 40]. Physicians' concerns around malpractice liability are pervasive and materially impact medical practices [54, 66]—physicians may order more tests and procedures, take more time to explain risks, restrict the scope of their practice, and refer patients to other specialists [17, 26, 54]. These practices do not seem to improve the quality of care [66] despite increased costs for patients [17, 66]. Further, both the threat of and actual legal claims are associated with negative psychological, physical, and behavioral impacts for physicians [54].

3.2 Patients' Legal Considerations

As decision subjects, patients are vulnerable to the use of AI systems by both physicians and others such as insurance companies. XAI systems are typically tightly coupled with the AI black-boxes they are explaining. This means that explanations are likely geared towards the decision maker (landlords or property managers in this case). Meanwhile, the explanations given directly to decision subjects may not convey actionable information that would be to the benefit of the decision subject and to the disadvantage of the decision maker; explanations in this case may even be *dark patterns* [21] or *explainability pitfalls* [30].

This risk is heightened because while there are incentives for companies to create AI explanations and systems that are actionable for decision makers such as physicians, they are not incentivized to do so for decision subjects. Insurance companies are already using AI systems to increase profits by using opaque algorithms to deny medically necessary treatments for vulnerable patients groups, such as the elderly or people with disabilities [5]. Outside of the tangible physical harms patients face with these denials, they also bear many intangible emotional and psychological harms as they work to push back against unjust decisions. Consequently, decision subjects such as patients are more at risk of absorbing negative impacts with fewer paths for recourse outside of legal action.

3.3 Legal Representatives' Considerations

As AI systems are increasingly deployed in real world medical environments, there will invariably be undesired and unanticipated effects on decision makers and decision subjects that result in tangible and intangible harms. When harms happen, doctors, patients, insurers and others will turn to legal representatives to discover and argue for the extent to which accountability lies with different parties—the decision maker, decision subject, the entity that deployed the AI system (e.g., hospital system), or entity that developed the system. Once a lawsuit is raised, there is a different stage of vulnerability where recourse now resides in the ability of the legal representative to discover the facts of what happened within the AI system that support their case. When an AI system is at the core of the harm, ascertaining the relevant factors for a persuasive case can become more complicated than normal, requiring access to proprietary information about the algorithms, models, and data used to develop the AI system. In these cases, a power imbalance exists in favor of the party with access to the system.

Although legal experts are stakeholders in the design of AI systems [49], further research is needed in how to incorporate legal expertise into the design of AI systems and explanation systems. The incorporation of legal considerations into the design of AI explanations has largely focused on theoretical impacts of the law on the design of explanations. Legal scholars [32, 34, 60] have discussed legal imperatives for explanations, what explanations should enable, and the forms that explanations should take. Scholars have also advocated for auditing [11, 36, 57] an algorithm's inner workings, outputs, or data, and the advantages and legal imperatives of each. However, there are significant challenges

in understanding how to design explanations for use in the legal system. For example, studies have demonstrated that traditional counterfactual explanations from AI systems are not intuitive to judges and are limited in their ability to support understanding in a legal case [70]. This can significantly impact how lawyers are able to represent physicians and patients in court.

4 Design Opportunities for Legal Considerations

To protect physicians and patients from harmful outcomes from decisions made with AI systems, it is imperative to understand how to incorporate legal implications into medical AI explanations. We highlight two initial opportunities to begin addressing this need.

The first opportunity is around investigating the kinds of legal information that can support physicians. As mentioned before, as decision makers, physicians are placed in positions of power and legal responsibility, acting as a first defense against negative AI determinations about patients' medical needs. *Legally informative* information explicitly describes laws, regulations, and legal rights that are relevant to those impacted by the AI system. For example, this includes information that doctors are fully liable for harms from decisions made with in-house (i.e. hospital-made) AI systems in which they serve as the final decision maker [64]. On the other hand, *legally actionable* information can be used for legal action once harm has occurred, but is not legally related in and of itself. For example, doctors' documentation is not legal information, but can be used in a malpractice suit. Helping doctors understand what information from the AI system can become legally actionable for themselves and others can be critical for contestability and the broader development of responsible AI systems.

The second opportunity relates to evaluations of new XAI systems. Evaluations are touch points with reality: they ideally reflect and (re-)direct AI system designs to account for the kinds of legal information and considerations that users actively have. Decision makers, decision subjects, and legal representatives have differing positionalities and vulnerabilities with respect to AI systems and the power dynamics that are reinforced by the presence of said systems. Creating "Legally-Informed" XAI, necessitates legally-informed evaluations—evaluations that can help us understand and adjust how AI systems support users' legal considerations. Legally-informed evaluations must take into account several important considerations highlighted in prior HCXAI Workshops, including the inherently multi-stakeholder nature of critical environments [59]; the importance of understanding and designing around the actions each stakeholder group can take [48]; and the variation in expectations from explanations specific to different groups [24, 62].

5 Co-Disciplinary Next Steps

How does one identify legally informative and legally actionable information? How does one design XAI systems to incorporate this information? As a practical first step, we advocate for co-disciplinary analyses—where researchers, developers, lawyers, and other stakeholders actively work together—to understand patterns across current litigation and reported harms.

One place to start is to analyze litigation and harms databases which reflect what kinds of situations are litigated (or not). Many law schools are maintaining databases tracking current litigation, such as Georgetown's Health Litigation Tracker [10] or George Washington University's Database of AI Litigation [9]. Lawsuits take time to develop and litigate, and may not reflect all of the potential risks to users (i.e., doctors and patients). For example, Epic, the American healthcare software company that develops the most widely used electronic health record system in the United States, deployed an AI-based sepsis prediction model that was highly criticized for its poor performance and ultimately retracted because of how much it disrupted patient care [69]. While a lawsuit did not cause the system to be retracted,

it still had a significant and negative impact on how doctors cared for patients. Consequently, we also recommend that interdisciplinary teams analyze crowd-sourced databases that report these kinds of harms as well, such as the AI, Algorithmic and Automation Incidents and Controversies Database [1]).

Coordinated, co-disciplinary analyses of these cases by researchers, developers, and lawyers can help reveal technical, social, and legal challenges that users are facing as the impacts of AI systems ripple across users' sociotechnical environments. Co-disciplinary analyses of current litigation and harms can build the necessary human capacity for cross-disciplinary communication to effectively address users' legal considerations. Prior work has highlighted the challenges of and need for cross-disciplinary communication to align algorithmic and legal pathways for actionability and contestability [49]. For example, there are fundamental terminology differences among communities, such as what information from an AI system constitutes an "explanation" [49]. Joint conversations around litigation and harms can expose these communication differences and build the capacity among people in different fields to create a shared understanding through conversation, increasing the ability to identify and address disciplinary blind-spots [12]. Through a shared understanding, people can then together better design legal, technical, and social infrastructures that truly serve users' information and action needs, expanding their actionability and contestability.

Coordinated, co-disciplinary analyses around current litigation and harms can also positively support communication around users' needs in several ways. Conversations around litigation can engage co-disciplinary groups in creating practical solutions to on-the-ground challenges. Analyzing existing litigation and harms can ensure both conversations focus on actionability and contestability—two of the major outcomes for users that can positively support their abilities to respond to deployed AI systems. Centering conversations on legal harms and repercussions impacting users can productively direct conversations about the actions that users, and others supporting them, can take to advocate for themselves, and the information they need to help them take these actions. This can reveal the information to include in explanations based on what is legally significant in lawsuits.

Tying these kinds of information to the actions users need—validating information from the system, comparing alternative outcomes from AI decisions, communicating about AI decisions or outcomes (among others)—can be one way to build better evaluations, too. By stating assumptions about how different kinds of information support users' legal considerations, evaluations can then be developed to test these assumptions and improve AI systems in response. Consistently evaluating AI systems and explanations can help adapt explanatory content to the dynamic, legal landscape that shapes users' sociotechnical environment. For example, co-disciplinary teams can conduct qualitative analysis around how lawyers leverage explanatory information, providing helpful feedback on how they may incorporate this information when litigating a harm or contestation.

6 Conclusions

Without accounting for legal considerations in people's sociotechnical environments, AI explanations risk tipping the balance of power away from those who are vulnerable and those advocating for the vulnerable. *Legally-Informed* XAI is needed to ensure the actionability and contestability of AI systems. Towards this end, we describe the need to account for the legal considerations of three stakeholder groups decision makers, decision subjects, and legal representatives. As an example of the complexities that Legally-Informed XAI may need to address, we engage in an extended discussion of legal considerations via the context of medical AI systems. We offer design opportunities to begin understanding and shaping Legally-Informed XAI to ensure AI systems are actionable and contestable by people impacted by their determinations.

Acknowledgments

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation GRFP under Grant No. DGE-2039655. Any opinion, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the authors(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

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Algorithmic Mirror: Designing an Interactive Tool to Promote Self-Reflection for YouTube Recommendations

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Fig. 1. Four-step workflow for reflective exploration of YouTube recommendations in Algorithmic Mirror: (A) Export watch history via Google Takeout, (B) Process via semantic analysis using Latent Lab, (C) Generate a semantic map of video topics and sources (pulled vs. pushed content), and (D) Reflect on interests and algorithmic recommendations—illustrated by interconnected nodes.

Big Data analytics and Artificial Intelligence systems derive non-intuitive and often unverifiable inferences about individuals' behaviors, preferences, and private lives. Drawing on diverse, feature-rich datasets of unpredictable value, these systems erode the intuitive connection between our actions and how we are perceived, diminishing control over our digital identities. While Explainable Artificial Intelligence scholars have attempted to explain the inner workings of algorithms, their visualizations frequently overwhelm end-users with complexity. This research introduces 'hypothetical inference'—a novel approach that uses language models to simulate how algorithms might interpret users' digital footprints and infer personal characteristics without requiring access to proprietary platform algorithms. Through empirical studies with fourteen participants, we advance the discourse on algorithmic literacy by providing users with accessible insights into potential algorithmic interpretations of their data.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Critical Algorithmic Reflection, Recommendation Algorithm Visualization, Spotify, YouTube.
Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170477.

1 INTRODUCTION

Online, recognizing and identifying one's own image is a difficult but important task. Recognizing oneself helps develop self-consciousness and introspection, a process that Lacan calls 'mirror stage' [10]. The mirror allows individuals to encounter their reflection and construct an image of a unified self. Online, however, our sense of self remains largely invisible to us [2]. As individuals scroll on algorithmic feeds, online platforms monitor and assemble a mosaic of our digital footprints (e.g. browsing histories, reactions, mouse movements, and clicks) scattered across multiple sites. Collected data are used to analyze or predict aspects of an individual's life, including work performance, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behavior, and location [11].

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To ensure humans’ right to understand and contest AI-driven decisions, HCI and Explainable AI (XAI) scholars have prioritized algorithmic transparency. Traditional algorithm visualizations often overwhelm end-users with complexity [7], while proprietary algorithms remain protected by trade secrets [8]. Recent personalized XAI approaches aim to make explanations more accessible and relevant to users’ individual contexts, moving beyond one-size-fits-all solutions [4]. Systems like CHAITok and The Algorithm have attempted to simulate recommendation patterns using small user-selected datasets [1, 12], but these simulations lack the authenticity of users’ actual digital footprints.

Meanwhile, Large Language Models (LLMs) offer promising capabilities for XAI [14]. For example, some work has investigated using LLMs to directly explain ML models [3, 9], to understand user questions to generate the appropriate explanation [13] or to transform explanations into natural language narratives [15]. We believe that LLMs can be used to generate plausible inferences from a user’s digital footprint, potentially bridging the gap between complex algorithmic systems and intuitive user understanding.

In this study, we provide users with a personalized data visualization that we call “Algorithmic Mirror” for real-world algorithmic investigations. Algorithmic Mirror acts as a digital mirror, bringing together fragmented digital footprints from online platforms and time periods to reveal how platforms and algorithms shape users’ inner lives over time. Our key design concepts are:

- (1) *Interactive Map Visualization*: reassembling scattered digital footprint into a single map of personal digital footprint and inferences;
- (2) *Hypothetical Inference*: simulating how algorithms might interpret user digital footprint and infer personal characteristics generated by Large Language Models (LLMs) without access to the actual proprietary algorithms used by social media platforms;
- (3) *Temporal Dimension*: utilizing long-term data to enable users to reflect on the effects of recommendation algorithms and their actions over time.

We then examine how this design can support users’ reflection on their online behavior and data, with the following research question:

RQ: How might a tool for simulating algorithmic inference be used to facilitate critical reflection over data?

Taken together, our findings contribute to the research on XAI for enhancing users’ critical algorithmic literacy, as well as the ability to understand and evaluate how algorithms work and impact information we see and decisions we make.

2 DESIGN PROTOTYPE: ALGORITHMIC MIRROR

Drawing on previous personalized XAI tools, we propose Algorithmic Mirror. This design prototype aims to bring together scattered digital footprints into a single map and visualize how algorithms interpret users’ footprints. By doing so, it highlights the influence of filtering algorithms on content exploration and algorithmically-mediated lives.

Algorithmic Mirror is built upon a publicly-available language model-powered knowledge exploration system called Latent Lab [6]. The tool provides an automated and easy-to-use pipeline for converting high-dimensional unstructured data into interactive 2D map visualizations. The interface allows users to explore labeled clusters of similar topics and search by semantic context. In our study, participants obtained their YouTube watch history via Google Takeout and uploaded the data to Latent Lab. Below, we discuss the four main key design components of Algorithmic Mirror.

Interactive Map Visualization Algorithmic Mirror leverages Latent Lab to create an interactive 2D map of video data, where each dot represents a video. Transcripts are embedded via OpenAI’s text-embedding-ada-002 model and then reduced to two dimensions using UMAP. Clusters signify semantic similarity, and overlaid contour lines illustrate data density. Users can pan, zoom, and view high-level or detailed labels and contours, supported by an occlusion

Fig. 2. Algorithmic Mirror Interface. We highlight four main components of the interface with dashed lines. The watched videos are in pink, searched terms in purple, watched videos after searching in yellow, watched advertisements in green, and watched shorts videos in blue.

algorithm that prioritizes popular topics for legible labeling. Clicking any point opens a sidebar showing the detailed view with the video’s header image, title (with a direct link), and its full transcript.

Topic Extraction and Data Processing Algorithmic Mirror uses Latent Lab to model how recommendation systems analyze digital footprints, inferring user interests and preferences. Latent Lab automatically extracts up to three primary topics from each video transcript using GPT-4o. These topics are aggregated, ranked, and embedded to position them within semantically relevant areas of the map, forming a hierarchical topic tree that scales from broad to specific themes as users zoom. This structure ensures users can navigate clusters with increasing detail and thematic nuance.

Summarization and Timeline The summarization bar samples transcripts visible on the map, summarizes them via GPT-4o, and presents a concise overview of the current map region. A timeline slider lets users filter videos by date, dynamically updating contour lines and labels to highlight how content shifts over time.

Dataset Overlay Latent Lab allows users to overlay one dataset onto another, enabling the exploration of one dataset in the context of another by projecting the overlaid points into the semantic space defined by the target dataset’s UMAP reducer. This process is non-commutative, meaning overlaying dataset A onto dataset B yields different results than overlaying B onto A, as the spatial relationships depend on the target dataset. In Algorithmic Mirror, this feature is used to analyze cross-platform content, such as overlaying YouTube viewing data onto Spotify listening history (or vice versa) to reveal semantic relationships. (see Figure 4 for visualization of dataset overlay).

Participants ($n = 8/14$) often first clicked the ‘Play’ button which animates the map month by month, noting that this process allowed them to see what P5 termed “*watching myself grow*”. P2 stated, “*The tool allows me to think more deeply about the temporal depth and maturity of my interests*,” observing changes in YouTube usage from initially using it as a music tool to later relying more on recommendations. P4 echoed this insight: “*I like the fact that I can see it over time... it does reflect interests that I’ve had as a person*.” P5 described how “*it takes me back to what I was doing or who I was in the past*.” In multiple instances, participants then selected specific time ranges by choosing a start and end date in the Timeline Slider. P6 asked: “*What was I looking up when I was taking these exams and when I was on this holiday?*” and used the timeline slider to examine those two moments.

Users critically examined inferred data Most participants ($n = 9/14$) found that the categories and summaries inferred by Algorithmic Mirror were accurate representations of their interests. They expressed fascination and discomfort with seeing a simulation of how recommendation algorithms on online platforms might interpret their behavior. Looking at the generated summary, P13 noted, “*The summary looks right. It’s always interesting when something interprets you to back yourself*”. This curiosity often led the participants to examine the implications of these algorithmic inferences critically, with P10 noting that the inferred ‘weight loss’ category was for ‘fitness content’ (“*I think watching fitness content means that you can get a lot of ads that have to do with weight loss*”). Participants also reflected on the broader effect that platform profiling had on their content consumption. P4 wondered, “*Has this mirror changed because I changed it or has it changed because the algorithm or some other external thing has changed it?*”

Users critically examined collected data Looking at maps of inferred interests and generative summaries, some participants ($n = 5/14$) questioned why Algorithmic Mirror was so accurate. They experimented with the Timeline Slider to see how much and how long their history had been recorded by YouTube (3 years on average, up to 10 years). P5 observed, “*They [recommendation algorithms] remember you, like how you were interested*.” P12 questioned if collecting such data allows platforms to shape future interests, noting, “*how would it [recommender system] try to track my interest over time and project new interests? [...] I can imagine it can try to predict how my personality would evolve*.”

Users reflected on alignment between consumption and interests Watching their maps evolve over time, a majority of participants ($n = 12/14$) noted that Algorithmic Mirror helped them reflect on whether the viewing consumption aligned with their personal goals and interests. P6 found the tool helpful in identifying content that “*doesn’t necessarily spark joy*” but they still continue to watch, prompting them to question engagement with such content. P9 noted, “*The proportion of hobbies I want to pursue [...] isn’t that high*.” P11 expressed shock, “*I was surprised to see how much time I spent watching things I didn’t really want to watch*.”

Our findings suggest that algorithmic inference simulations from personal digital footprint enable users to critically evaluate how data collection and inference practices shape their personalized content experiences.

5 CONCLUSION

Our research explored how Algorithmic Mirror could facilitate users’ critical reflection over their data on online platforms. Our research offers insights into how individuals can recognize and identify themselves in the digital age to promote more conscious engagement with online content. Our findings suggest design recommendations in XAI field to reassemble scattered digital footprints into a single map, simulate algorithmic inference with LLMs, as well as display a timeline for capturing evolving patterns. We emphasize engaging, user-centric presentations of online behaviors and inferred preferences can enhance critical algorithmic literacy. Future work should aim to reach broader populations with varying educational backgrounds and literacy levels, should promote features that encourage independent reflection, and should follow participants’ interactions over a longer period.

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A PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS

ID	Gender	Age Range	Origin	Education	Daily YouTube Session Length
1	Female	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
2	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< two hours
3	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	> two hours
4	Female	18-25	Indian	Master	< an hour
5	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
6	Female	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
7	Female	18-25	Chinese	Bachelor	< two hours
8	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< two hours
9	Male	18-25	Japanese	Bachelor	< an hour
10	Male	25-30	American	Master	> two hours
11	Female	25-30	American	Master	< two hours
12	Female	18-25	American	Master	< an hour
13	Male	18-25	Indian	Master	< an hour
14	Male	25-30	Japanese	Master	> two hours

Table 1. Participant Demographics. The sample shows an equal gender distribution (7 males, 7 females), with participants predominantly in the 18-25 age range (11 participants). Most participants are of Japanese origin (8), followed by American (3), Indian (2), and Chinese (1). All participants hold higher education degrees (8 Bachelor’s, 6 Master’s). YouTube viewing habits indicate most participants (11) watch less than two hours daily, with only 3 participants watching more than two hours.

B INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

Interview Protocol: Interaction with Algorithmic Mirror
<p>Phase 1: Initial Exploration Please browse this interface freely (10 minutes)</p>
<p>Phase 2: User Experience Assessment</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What aspects of the tool did you find particularly effective or appealing?2. What features or elements did you find challenging or less useful?3. Could you suggest specific improvements that would enhance your experience with the tool?
<p>Phase 3: Future Usage Intent Would you be interested in continuing to use this interface after the study concludes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">o If yes: What would motivate your continued use?o If no: What factors influence your decision not to continue?
<p>Phase 4: Reflection Process Evaluation What are your overall thoughts on this reflection process?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">o How effective was it in promoting self-reflection?o What impact did it have on your understanding of your online behavior?

Table 2. Semi-structured Interview Protocol

C DATASET OVERLAY (SPOTIFY AND YOUTUBE)

Fig. 4. Left panel: Algorithmic Mirror of Spotify listening history, Right panel: Multi-platform Algorithmic Mirror overlaying YouTube viewing data onto Spotify listening history (or vice versa) to reveal semantic relationships. Users can toggle between single-dataset views or combined overlays, with distinct colors (e.g., green for YouTube and purple for Spotify) highlighting cross-platform patterns and thematic connections.

“Help me to understand explainable AI “: XAI-UI – an Explanation Interface to evaluate user-centered XAI.

XAI-UI: A Human-Centered Explanation Interface for Evaluating and Guiding XAI in Clinical Sepsis Prediction.

An explanation User Interface for the guided use and evaluation of XAI in clinical sepsis prediction modules.

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Current explainable AI (XAI) tools lack the essential interactive and adaptive features needed to support a diverse range of users in understanding and applying AI insights effectively. This presentation introduces the Explanation User Interface (XAI-UI)—an innovative framework designed to address the interpretability challenges of AI-driven systems for sepsis prediction. The XAI-UI integrates state-of-the-art XAI methodologies, such as feature importance analysis, and temporal visualizations, with dynamic user interfaces tailored for interactive and adaptive experiences. These features ensure that the explanations provided by AI systems are not only technically sound but also actionable, accessible, and aligned with user-specific requirements. This approach is particularly crucial for high-stakes domains, like healthcare, where transparency, ethical use, and decision-making speed are critical. Importantly, the XAI-UI framework provides a modular and scalable design, making it applicable across a broad range of industries that utilize AI. It directly tackles key challenges in XAI, such as the disagreement problem (variability in explanations across models) and the absence of standardized evaluation metrics. By leveraging adaptive feedback, sophisticated evaluation criteria, and user-centered design principles, XAI-UI fosters trust, usability, and broader adoption of XAI systems, setting new standards for transparency and accountability in AI applications.

CS CONCEPTS • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence** • Human-centered computing → Visualization → Visualization application domains → Information visualization • Human-centered computing → Human computer interaction (HCI)

Additional Keywords and Phrases: XAI, User Interface, Explanation Interface, User-centered AI,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15170432>

ADDRESSING REVIEWER COMMENTS

Reviewer 1 rightly noted the absence of an empirical user study. As this is a conceptual, design-focused position paper, we have not yet conducted real-world validation. However, we fully acknowledge its importance and have clarified in Sections 4 and 5 that user studies in clinical settings are a key focus of future work. These will evaluate how different design features of the XAI-UI improve clinical decision making and XAI usability.

Reviewer 2 emphasized the framework's conceptual clarity, modularity, and transferability—feedback we greatly appreciate. In response to the comment on length, we have shortened the main text to six pages, including the reviewer responses, and are open to further reducing or omitting the appendix if needed.

We thank both reviewers for their thoughtful input, which underscores the value of XAI-UI as a modular, adaptive, and user-centered explanation interface.

1 INTRODUCTION

As AI becomes integral to various domains, explaining its decisions is crucial, especially in high-stakes contexts where legal requirements demand transparency. A "good explanation" is inherently interactive, shaped by the user's needs, goals, and knowledge [15]. Moreover, the quality of being an explanation does not inherently belong to statements, visualizations, or examples [10]. Instead, effective XAI requires collaboration between the explainer and the user. XAI designers must acknowledge that an explanation is not merely algorithmic outputs – it must be meaningful to the user and hence, factors like cognitive workload, time constraints, and expertise must be considered to tailor XAI to the users' goals and roles [15].

Traditional XAI approaches often fail to meet the diverse needs of users or integrate human-computer interaction (HCI) principles. Often personal preferences and background factors are overlooked, causing cognitive burden, particularly for users with limited capacity or motivation to engage with explanations [4]. A striking 30% of users struggle to comprehend XAI, even for simple tasks [11]. These shortcomings largely arise from a techno-centric approach, as only 20% of XAI studies involved users [12] and rarely included information processing theories [19]. The Human-Centered Explainable Artificial Intelligence (HCXAI) community [3], shifted XAI to center on users' needs and also increasingly on Explanation Interfaces [2] (XUI). This approach separates the explainable model from the interface [6], focusing on model analysis, user communication, and user experience (UX) – addressing how to structure and present explanations to align with user needs. Thus, while XAI focuses on what to explain, XUI research explores how to deliver explanations.

This position paper introduces an innovative mockup of a human-centered XAI interface (XAI-UI) stepping beyond the limitations of current XAI. Its use case is a critical application: clinical decision support for sepsis prediction. Sepsis, affecting 50 million patients annually [18], progresses rapidly and requires timely, high-stakes decisions often made with incomplete data. The standard diagnostic "blood culture" test takes eight hours, too long for critically ill patients [20]. Early sepsis diagnosis is a challenging yet underexplored domain and existing models like the widely implemented Epic Sepsis Model, demonstrate unsatisfactory performance, necessitating a deeper analysis of their limitations in clinical practice [7].

The XAI-UI leverages user feedback and varied metrics to identify the best XAI approaches for specific scenarios, addressing unresolved challenges: how to determine the best XAI approach and format and how to evaluate the effectiveness of XAI. There are many post-hoc XAI approaches, yet these yield inconsistent relevance values despite explaining the same network predictions, i.e. the disagreement problem [5, 8]. The lack of guidelines and standardized evaluation metrics further complicates XAI selection. By combining user ratings, preferences and performance, the XAI-UI provides a user-centered guide for XAI. Its interactive, adaptive features bridge technical complexity and real-world usability, advancing a truly user-focused era of XAI.

2 PROCESS

Our conceptual work focuses on defining the requirements for designing and visualizing the XAI-UI with high-end mockup screens. The initial stage involves reviewing XAI UI literature to identify design principles, required XAI approaches, and evaluation metrics. The second stage describes how to use direct and indirect user feedback to refine the design. Finally, iterative improvements are outlined based on the analysis of collected user data.

2.1 Requirements Specification

The requirements specification aims to define the functional, technical, and user-centered needs for the XAI-UI mockup, by reviewing XAI methods and interface design literature, particularly in high-stakes domains. All articles were identified via Google Scholar with the following keywords: "XAI," "interpretable AI," "explainable AI," and "UI."

The insights include sepsis-specific XAI UI requirements from [20], which analyzed why clinicians abandon AI-powered sepsis prediction modules, and principles for user-centered XAI from [9, 10], who described a broad set of principles for user-centered XAI systems. Additional contributions are discussed in relevant sections.

To align the XAI-UI framework with clinical needs, we identified key user groups: frontline clinicians (e.g., emergency physicians), who need fast, actionable insights; clinical researchers and data scientists, who focus on model behavior and explanation methods; and nursing staff, who monitor patient data and alerts. Their differing informational needs are reflected in the modular, goal-driven design of the interface. By tailoring explanations to specific goals – like hypothesis generation or decision-making – we aim to support diverse roles across the clinical workflow.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Design aspects and requirements of the XAI-UI

3.1.1 Goal-driven XAI

As highlighted in [20], the requirements for XAI in sepsis prediction emphasize the need to support clinicians at various stages of decision-making, especially during the early stages, rather than focusing solely on final-stage predictions. The presented Explanation Interface assigns functionalities to four key goals to support clinicians in understanding AI output:

- **Hypothesis Generation:** Providing initial insights to help clinicians identify sepsis as a potential condition.
- **Data Gathering:** Recommending additional tests or collecting additional data to reduce diagnostic uncertainty.
- **Hypothesis Testing:** Enabling interactive exploration to assess how new data might influence predictions.
- **Decision-Making:** Supporting final treatment decisions, such as initiating specific interventions.

Focusing on goal-specific explanations, such as hypothesis generation, allows to adhere to the *Naturalness* principle by ensuring explanations are intuitive and aligned with clinicians' mental models. The current mockup overview, as depicted in Figure 1, incorporates next to the risk score and the most important features also these four goals (Figure 1H) to ensure that the interface captures diverse user needs based on their specific objectives. To further refine the system, user feedback analysis will utilize these goals to evaluate user requirements and design features. Recognizing that user behavior and evaluation criteria for XAI may vary depending on the intended goal, this design ensures that the system can be adapted to different needs and provides metrics relevant to each user's context. This goal-driven structure enhances usability and ensures that XAI supports clinicians effectively at every stage of the decision-making process.

3.1.2 Multiple XAI Approaches & Visualizations

A critical requirement of the XAI-UI is the evaluation of several XAI methods (Figure 1H; A.1: Table 2) to enable a comparative analysis, addressing the *disagreement problem* with four metrics that evaluate agreement, providing highly trustable features and less trustable features (see section 4). The XAI method that shows the highest agreement will be selected by default (as shown in Figure 1H, highlighting LRP) for all subsequent visualizations. A breakdown of contributing factors to the AI's predictions is provided, e.g. temporal bubble plot visualizations (see Figure 1F or 1D).

Figure 1: This screen displays XAI analysis details for a selected patient. (A) summarizes patient details, (H) shows the selected XAI model, metrics, goals, and actions. (E) provides an active feedback button. The risk level (B) shows the risk score and uncertainty, (C) offers actionable recommendations, (D) highlights top features, (F) visualizes feature importance over time, and (G) adds other plots.

Figure 2: XAI-UI drop down menu view

3.1.3 Adaptive, Personalized Interfaces and Recommendations

User- and content specific adaptation and personalization is critical to adhere to the design principle of *Sensitivity* and *Responsiveness* (Table 1). Also, Sewnath et al. [16] conclude that XAI UI designers should only provide information that is relevant to the users' need. Therefore, the XAI-UI enables to dynamically adjust content based on user behavior, preferences, and context. Users can easily personalize different design elements, i.e. remove, add or rearrange, with a drop-down menu (Figure 2). Systematic quantitative and qualitative feedback from user interactions informs iterative improvements of the XAI-UI. In addition, users receive tailored recommendations for further tests, data exploration, or visualizations—enabling them to draw concrete conclusions in time-constrained clinical settings.

4 FEEDBACK ANALYSIS

To assess the effectiveness of the XAI-UI, a combination of tailored metrics and feedback mechanisms has been developed as the foundation for upcoming user studies. Evaluating XAI systems—particularly in clinical contexts—requires attention to accuracy, interpretability, and actionable insight under time pressure. Therefore, the evaluation integrates technical performance indicators with user-centered feedback. This dual approach is aligned with core design principles such as Understandability, Sensitivity, and Responsiveness, and with the XAI User Experience (UX) Standards [9] (Table 1).

Table 1: XAI Design Principles and XAI User Experience Standards for guiding UI interface design adapted from Lei et al. [9]

XAI Design Principle	Description
Naturalness	Explanations should use natural language for logical, detailed content, supporting rapid comprehension.
Responsiveness	Provides dynamic, tailored explanations and uses progressive disclosure to reduce cognitive load.
Flexibility	Encourages diverse explanatory methods, catering to varied user preferences.
Sensitivity	Adjusts explanations in real-time based on the user's psychological state and context.
XAI UX Standard	Description
Satisfaction	Measures overall usability and psychological pleasure derived during interaction.
Trust	Reflects whether the explanations increase user confidence in the AI system.
Persuasiveness	Indicates the degree to which explanations convince users and impact decision-making.
Efficiency	Evaluates whether users can quickly and fluently grasp the AI explanations, reducing effort.
Understandability	Examines the ease with which users comprehend explanations, aligning with mental models.

Feedback collection is structured around four core clinical goals: hypothesis generation, data gathering, hypothesis testing, and decision-making. These stages mirror clinical reasoning workflows and guide both the interface design and the evaluation strategy. Hypothesis generation is supported by summaries and risk scores that help clinicians quickly identify potential diagnostic directions. During data gathering, interactive tooltips and confidence intervals suggest further diagnostic steps, enhancing exploration and understanding. Hypothesis testing is facilitated through interactive visualizations that allow users to examine alternative explanations and evidence. Finally, decision-making is guided by ranked feature contributions and treatment suggestions that offer actionable insights. This goal-oriented structure enables context-sensitive evaluation and contributes to increased usability and trust across diverse user groups.

The XAI UX standard metrics evaluate the XAI-UI workflow (Figure 3), by favoriting features via a clickable star symbol or offering active feedback input (Figure 1E). Comparative analysis of user goals and interactions, including time spent on specific views, identifies goal-specific processes. Expanding on this, the following dimensions of interaction data can be critically examined:

- **Frequency of Interaction:** Monitoring how often clinicians use different XAI approaches reveals system relevance. High use indicates reliance, while low use hints usability issues.
- **Time Spent:** Tracking time spent on explanations highlights system clarity and efficiency. Short times suggest intuitive designs, while longer durations may indicate areas needing simplification or support.
- **Task Completion Rates:** Measuring how often clinicians successfully complete diagnostic or decision-making tasks with different types of XAI and different visualizations.
- **Error Correction Trends:** Tracking instances where clinicians identify and rectify errors based on XAI outputs.
- **Confidence Shift Metrics:** Monitoring changes in clinician confidence before and after reviewing XAI outputs.

To measure the effectiveness of the XAI approach in improving clinical decision-making, the following data is collected:

- **Clinical Decision Accuracy:** Compare clinician decisions made with XAI to gold-standard labels (e.g., true sepsis cases), log errors (e.g., missed sepsis cases) and analyze whether specific explanations reduced errors.
- **Speed of Decision-Making:** Measure the time clinicians take to make decisions with and without XAI and in relation to their specific user-goals.

Figure 3: Feedback menu for rating workflows

- **User Engagement Metrics:** Track how often clinicians return to the system or request additional explanations in relation to their specific user-goals.

To enable a longitudinal comparative analysis of XAI, the following metrics, adapted from [1, 17], will be analyzed and then depicted in the right side panel of the XAI-UI (Figure 1H) to evaluate the suggested actions and explanation:

- **Faithfulness:** Faithfulness ensures that the explanation accurately reflects the model's decision-making process. Metrics include *Correlation*, *Comprehensiveness*, *Sufficiency*, and *AUC-TP* (see A.2).
- **Robustness/ Relative Input Stability (RIS):** Robustness ensures explanations remain stable under slight input variations. RIS shows the proportional change in explanations relative to changes in the inputs.
- **Complexity/ Effective Complexity:** Complexity ensures explanations are interpretable and actionable for end-users. *Effective Complexity* calculates the minimum number of features required to maintain predictive accuracy.

Tackling the *disagreement problem* of XAI and the *Sensitivity* design principle, multiple XAI approaches allow to highlight the aspect on which explanations agree or disagree [14]. The following metrics [adapted from 8, 14] are used:

- **Feature Agreement:** The fraction of common features between the sets of top-k features of two explanations.
- **Rank Agreement:** The fraction of features that are common between the sets of top-k features of two explanations and that have the same position in the respective rank orders.
- **Sign Agreement:** The degree to which two explanations align in terms of both the top-k features they identify and the directions of those features' contributions (positive or negative).
- **Signed Rank Agreement:** A combination explanation agreement evaluating the overlap of the top-k features between two explanations while also ensuring that these shared features have identical signs (positive or negative) and ranks.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The XAI-UI framework introduces an innovative approach to addressing critical challenges in XAI, particularly in high-stakes medical domains like sepsis prediction. By integrating user-centered design principles, adaptive interfaces, and robust evaluation metrics, the XAI-UI ensures that explanations are not only technically sound but also actionable and aligned with user goals. Its ability to handle key challenges, such as the disagreement problem and the absence of standardized evaluation guidelines, stresses its potential to foster trust, usability, and broader adoption of XAI.

The XAI-UI is currently a conceptual framework, representing a necessary first step before real-world validation through user studies can take place, which are already in preparation. Furthermore, while the XAI-UI incorporates advanced metrics, its effectiveness in addressing the full spectrum of clinical scenarios, particularly rare edge cases, needs further exploration. Scalability and integration with existing clinical workflows also pose challenges that require additional research.

Future research will focus on evaluating user feedback and identified metrics, optimizing workflows, and prioritizing user-driven design principles to refine the XAI-UI. Particular attention will be given to validating the workflows and evaluation metrics that proved most effective, such as faithfulness, robustness, and goal-specific interactions. User studies will assess how these metrics improve clinical decision-making and streamline workflows. While this study centers on a clinical use case, key components of the XAI-UI—such as explanation metrics like faithfulness, robustness, and agreement—are domain-agnostic and applicable to other high-stakes fields.

Additionally, insights from this study will inform iterative design improvements, ensuring explanations remain clear and actionable for diverse users. Integration within clinics and real-time adaptability to feedback will further enhance its impact. Leveraging these results, the XAI-UI can set a foundation for a trusted, effective XAI framework tailored to the complexities of medical decision-making, ultimately improving patient outcomes and advancing XAI standards.

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A APPENDICES

A.1 XAI Models used in the XAI-UI

Table 2: XAI Models of the XAI-UI

XAI Method	Family	Example in Sepsis ICU Prediction
SHAP	Feature Attribution	Identifies the contribution of features like heart rate to a sepsis prediction.
TimeSHAP	Feature Attribution	Identifies temporal contribution of features, like vital signs
LIME	Feature Attribution	Explains why a model predicted sepsis by locally analyzing features such as blood pressure and glucose levels.
Feature Importance (FI)	Feature Attribution	Ranks features like lactate levels, respiratory rate, and urine output by their influence on predicting sepsis risk.
Sensitivity Analysis	Gradient-Based	Assesses the sensitivity of a sepsis prediction model to changes in inputs like oxygen saturation and fluid balance.
GradCAM	Gradient-Based	Visualizes the importance of time-based ICU data, like fluctuations in blood pressure, for sepsis prediction.
LRP	Gradient-Based	Allocates relevance scores to features (e.g., P-glucose or B-leukocytes) to explain their contributions to sepsis prediction
Deep Taylor Decomposition	Gradient-Based	Provides explanations tailored to temporal data
Counterfactual Explanations	Example-Based	Suggests that lowering lactate levels or increasing fluid intake could change a sepsis prediction to non-sepsis.
Partial Dependence Plots	Feature Attribution (Global)	Analyzes the global effect of features like lactate or C-reactive protein on sepsis risk, showing their averaged impact
Attention Mechanisms	Feature Attribution	Highlights the time steps (e.g., hours before diagnosis) where features like oxygen saturation significantly influenced the prediction

A.2 XAI Faithfulness Metrics

Faithfulness: Faithfulness is the most critical aspect when comparing XAI methods, as it ensures that the explanation accurately reflects the model's decision-making process. Key metrics used for the XAI-UI include correlation, comprehensiveness, sufficiency, and Area Under the Threshold Performance Curve (AUC-TP). These are defined as follows:

- **Faithfulness Correlation:** This directly measures how well feature attributions align with changes in the model's predictions. It is essential for assessing the core alignment between the explanation and the model.
- **Comprehensiveness:** Highlights the importance of features identified by the explanation by measuring the prediction degradation when these features are removed. This is vital for understanding whether the explanation identifies the model's true decision drivers.
- **Sufficiency:** Complements comprehensiveness by evaluating whether the most important features alone can approximate the model's prediction. Together, comprehensiveness and sufficiency provide a balanced view of how well the explanation captures critical features.
- **Area Under the Threshold Performance Curve (AUC-TP):** This provides an aggregated measure of how removing top features affects performance, offering a holistic view of feature importance across thresholds.

Towards Responsible AI: Explainable AI as a Catalyst for Participatory Development Practices

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This paper builds on the call for more human-centred XAI (explainable AI), arguing that XAI is a necessary but under-researched component of meaningful participatory AI. To enable the meaningful participation of diverse stakeholder communities at various points in the AI lifecycle, they must be able to understand, interpret, and scrutinise the entire socio-technical system. However, while significant research has centred on XAI, much of this has been primarily useful for developers, those with expert knowledge, or specific end-users. XAI solutions tailored to affected or other interested communities are currently less explored – especially how information needs change along the AI lifecycle. This paper sets out to stimulate discussion on how XAI can support the meaningful involvement of affected and other communities—an essential step towards more responsible AI systems—by highlighting current challenges and proposing a research agenda for moving forward.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Participatory AI, Development, Responsible AI, Stakeholder Engagement, Explainable AI, Transparency, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170408

1 Introduction

Moving towards more responsible AI development practices is a pressing concern, partly driven by numerous incidents where AI systems have resulted in negative impacts [30]. *Explainable AI* (XAI) is often considered key aspect of responsible AI, i.e. where AI systems provide information to render themselves less opaque and more human-comprehensible. XAI can focus on different aspects of the system, e.g. a model’s general operation or why a specific recommendation/output was provided [11]. XAI has been a topic of research for several years, but in practice, much of the work has primarily served those with technical expertise; e.g. developers seeking to debug systems or to conduct technical audits [4, 14, 37]. Whilst important, supporting transparency for all communities that may be affected by or have an interest in the system appears less-considered – despite this being (directly/indirectly) encouraged by guidance documents [15, 16, 31–35] and regulations [41]. Thus, a shift towards more human-centred (vs. only developer- or user-centred) XAI is an essential step towards more responsible AI development, and various works are calling for and inducing such shift [e.g. 3, 7, 12, 14, 19, 28, 38–41].

This work endorses this shift of the audience of XAI. Importantly, we want to emphasise that **inclusive XAI has an essential role for meaningful participatory AI development**. *Participatory AI* (also termed *stakeholder involvement* (*ShI*)) refers to the process of engaging affected communities and other groups with a stake in the system throughout the AI lifecycle in order to understand their needs and concerns regarding the system’s application context and to ensure these are considered during the system’s design [8, 9, 20]. Such participatory approaches have been associated with benefits such as (i) a better understanding of the system’s socio-technical context [6, 25, 26, 44] and thus (ii) the improved detection (and thus mitigation) of potential risks and harms [10, 26, 43], as well as (iii) a shift of decision power during development towards the communities the system will affect [5, 8, 20, 38, 42]. However, to harness these benefits along the entire AI lifecycle—including during system development and testing—all affected communities

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(including non-users) and those with an interest in the system have to be able to scrutinise and understand the system and its context so that they can provide informed opinions and recommend adjustments. Thus, XAI that is appropriately tailored and accessible to the diverse stakeholders of a system is key to unlocking meaningful engagement – beyond early explorations of needs in an application context [7, 19, 38].

2 Background: Various Stakeholder Communities are Insufficiently Involved During Model Development and Testing

In previous works [e.g. 20–22, 36], we investigated stakeholder involvement practices along the AI lifecycle (see [2] for details on lifecycle stages). We found that the majority of literature, guidance, and tooling for participatory AI development focused on early explorations (i.e. objective setting stage and system requirements definition stage) where communities are involved to explore their broad needs, wishes, and concerns in the system’s application context. However, involvements at later stages—for instance, when a system’s model and test results become more concrete—has largely been overlooked in research on stakeholder involvement. For example, in a study in which we analysed existing tools that support AI practitioners’ stakeholder involvement efforts, we found only a single tool that supports community engagement during the testing stage [21]. This lack of attention for stakeholder involvement at later stages of the lifecycle is detrimental: it prevents not only continuous stakeholder involvement along the AI lifecycle (which is essential, see [20, 22]), but also renders system assessments that go beyond technical performance tests as difficult or impossible. As a result, the accountability towards involved stakeholders is diminished [8, 20]. We want to emphasise that this is especially important in a time of growing calls for participatory AI development that advances rAI efforts [e.g. 5, 8, 9, 17, 18, 20–22, 26, 27, 36], which is not yet sufficiently supported throughout the AI lifecycle in practice.

While the lack of stakeholder involvement at the development and testing stages is a general issue of participatory AI development (i.e. not something that is XAI-specific), we suspect similar issues during stakeholder involvement for the development of human-centred XAI methods. However, we also believe that **XAI has the potential to significantly improve participatory AI development**, by providing a mechanism for unlocking more meaningful stakeholder involvement along the entire AI lifecycle (as we next explore).

3 XAI as Key to Unlock More Inclusive Participatory AI Development Practices

We see a real opportunity for XAI to enable greater stakeholder involvement, particularly during system development and testing. A key barrier to broader engagement at these stages may be the perception that AI systems are too complex to explain in ways that allow for meaningful participation or useful input from affected and interested communities. **Tailored, inclusive, and more human-centred XAI methods could help to overcome these barriers**, i.e. by providing stakeholders with the insights required in a manner that helps them understand, scrutinise, and evaluate whether the system fits their needs [1, 7, 12, 19, 38]. For example, Cobbe et al. [7] highlight that information about a system supports its reviewability (i.e. its understanding and scrutiny) only if it is *contextually appropriate*; that is, if the information provided, the way it is presented, and the form it takes all are all aligned with the audience’s needs and goals for making sense of, evaluating, or acting upon that information (thereby supporting accountability).

How audience-appropriate information can unlock the involvement of stakeholders with low levels of (AI) literacy has been illustrated in a study by Kuo et al. [24]: they involve civil servants and unhoused individuals through comicboarding to assess their needs and preferences regarding an algorithmic decision-support tool that supports emergency housing allocation. Such methods show promise in making XAI more accessible to a broader audience – for example, by visually representing explanation techniques (such as feature importance, confidence levels, or example-based explanations),

and by clarifying when and how a particular explanation method is appropriate or useful within a given context. In this manner, all stakeholders (especially and importantly including affected communities) would be able to scrutinise the model's (and systems) operations, including before it is deployed, flagging inaccuracies, risks, and harms so they can be handled. In short, more continuous and inclusive/accessible stakeholder involvement beyond early deliberations would further align AI development practices with responsible AI efforts.

However, XAI that is tailored to different stakeholders and to their information needs at different phases of the lifecycle is currently under-researched. Thus, we urge the CHI and related communities to explore **how the relevant stakeholder groups and their information needs differ along the AI lifecycle**, so to support meaningful engagement. In previous studies, we emphasise the need for contextually appropriate information to supporting meaningful transparency during system development; arguing the case generally [7], as well in particular contexts such as for clinicians (here varying with their level of familiarity with the system) [40]. Both studies emphasise not only that user needs are dynamic, but also that different stakeholders prioritise insights at different stages of the AI lifecycle [13]. Importantly, these stakeholder needs can vary based on multiple factors, including the community's level of expertise, prior experience with AI systems, the domain or use case, and perceptions of the trustworthiness of the developing organisation – factors that several studies have shown to significantly influence information expectations [e.g. 3, 7, 19, 23, 29]. These findings further emphasise that different XAI methods and approaches might be needed at different stages of the AI lifecycle, driven by the specific information requirements of the various stakeholders. However, we currently lack insights into the methods, practices, and design considerations best suited to meeting these needs in context. This lack of knowledge hinders XAI that is tailored to specific stakeholder needs, limiting its potential to provide information that effectively supports more continuous and meaningful stakeholder involvement (as well as accountability more generally). To help address these aspects, the next section outlines a research agenda focused on better understanding and supporting these diverse requirements.

4 Open Questions & Preliminary Research Agenda

We suggest following research agenda as a starting point to explore the type of XAI that is required to support more continuous and inclusive participatory AI development. It is designed to stimulate discussions and research that addresses current areas of uncertainty, i.e. how we can better use XAI to unlock more inclusive AI development practices and thus more responsible AI systems.

4.1 Understanding XAI needs across AI lifecycle stages

- (1) **Information needs along the lifecycle.** How do the information needs of involved communities change as system development progresses through the AI lifecycle?
- (2) **Purpose of XAI.** What is the purpose and benefit of XAI for each stage of the AI lifecycle?
- (3) **Relevant Factors.** What are the factors that influence information needs? These might include exploring:
 - (a) Level of expertise of the involved community, technical as well as in the lived experience.
 - (b) Role of the involved community, e.g. clinician, hospital IT expert, patient (see 4.2, point (2))
 - (c) Use case of the system, i.e. the system's objective.
 - (d) Perceived trustworthiness of the system creator (team or organisation).
 - (e) Involvement strategies, i.e. whether communities were involved from the outset.
 - (f) Which other factors are important here?

- (4) **General purpose AI.** How does this change for e.g. LLMs where use cases are vast and hard to pinpoint while stakeholders are extremely diverse?

4.2 Involved Communities during XAI development – and using XAI for AI development more broadly

- (1) **Communities in focus.** Which communities should be involved for more responsible AI development? How can we ensure that especially at-risk communities are included? This question concerns AI development more broadly, also outside of XAI efforts.
- (a) Which communities are especially relevant at which stage of the AI development lifecycle – or does this change at all? This question concerns AI development more broadly, also outside of XAI efforts.
 - (b) How can especially at-risk communities be accessed in a respectful manner, e.g. preserving their privacy and well-being?
 - (c) What are barriers beyond the typical challenges of responsible stakeholder involvement [20], i.e. challenges unique to including stakeholders with XAI methods?
- (2) **Information need per community.** What are the most crucial aspects of the system that each community has to understand? How does this change with the deployment context/industry?
- (3) **Relationship between XAI and participation.** Which interplay of XAI and participation is required to advance responsible AI efforts (instead of e.g. commercial interests)?

4.3 Implementing XAI that addresses these needs

- (1) **Type of XAI.** Considering the information needs/role of XAI at each stage of the AI lifecycle, what type of XAI is most suitable to fulfil these (e.g. model- and outcome-specific explanations)?
- (2) **Inclusive XAI.** Responsible AI development requires the participation of *all* affected communities, especially at-risk groups. How can we design XAI to make it accessible to all? We see a clear risk to design XAI that is only useful for specific, e.g. highly educated sub-groups, meaning that at-risk communities are further disadvantaged.
- (3) **Balancing detail with overload.** How can we provide sufficient details for meaningful participation while preventing information overload?
- (4) **Universality of guidance.** What is the correct balance on universal guidance on XAI for participatory development vs guidance that is tailored to a specific use case or industry?
- (5) **Practicability of guidance.** How can we make guidance more actionable as current research [see e.g. 39] shows that AI practitioners struggle to translate XAI guidance to their own projects?.

5 Summary & Moving Forward

In this paper, we have positioned XAI as an essential component in unlocking more participatory and responsible development practices throughout the process of AI development. We bring this discussion to CHI to engage the community in a timely and informed dialogue. Highlighting the role of XAI in supporting participatory approaches is critical now – so that the CHI and responsible AI communities can collaboratively identify concrete ways forward and foster future research and collaboration toward more transparent and accountable AI systems.

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Expanding HCXAI in the Age of AI Agents: Challenges and Recommendations

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AI agents—autonomous, multi-tasking systems beyond traditional AI—will reshape human-AI interaction shifting the focus from a simple human-versus-system autonomy debate to a triadic model: human users, AI agents, and digital resources. Further, the widespread adoption of agentic systems as consumer products will accelerate the large-scale integration of novel human-AI agent hybridization into everyday life, necessitating renewed examinations of agent identity, accountability, and trust in AI agent-rich digital environments. In this position paper, we argue that Human-Centered eXplainable AI (HCXAI) can help addressing these trends by developing causal explanations that span multiple levels of abstraction and integrate different digital resources, as well as personalized, interactive explanations that serve as identity warranty mechanisms when humans and AI agents interact together and with other digital resources. Finally, as a research field, HCXAI can help redesign the explainability-trust relation in these novel digital ecosystems. We introduce examples of these explanations, calling for an interdisciplinary collaboration to refine these high-level proposals and ensure a still human-centered digital future.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Applied computing**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; **Philosophical/theoretical foundations of artificial intelligence**;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: generative AI, AI agents, Large Language Model, Human-centered eXplainable AI. Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170379

Introduction

The Human-Centered eXplainable AI (HCXAI) paradigm posits that XAI is more than just ‘opening’ the AI black-box: it requires understanding who opens it, what they are trying to achieve, and design explanations that meet these needs [3, 4]. In this position paper, we suggest that recent HCXAI efforts to address the explainability of Large Language Models (LLMs)¹ should be realigned with the rapid evolution of AI agents—autonomous, multi-tasking systems that act on digital environments. To do so, HCXAI must expand its focus from explainability as a means of interpreting model outputs to explainability as a mechanism for managing accountability in action. Human-centered explanations must clarify agency with causality, provide warrants of online identity, and foster trust across human-AI agent-digital resource interactions. This is our take on “operationalizing human-centered perspectives in XAI” [4, pag. 2] in the age of AI agents. We elaborate on this argument identifying three HCXAI challenges related to AI agent explainability and proposing recommendations to ensure that explainability evolves with the rise of agentic AI.

Beware the dawn of the AI agent age

What are AI agents? In the domain of generative AI, the term **AI agent** refers to systems powered by LLMs that can execute a wide range of tasks while manifesting agentic capabilities [11, 18].² Here, **agency** denotes the capacity to make decisions, act, and influence the behavior of other systems in a working environment through a combination of programming instructions and learning capabilities. It emerges from a combination of interactivity, autonomy, and adaptability [8, 9].³ Unlike traditional machine learning-based AI systems designed for specific tasks, such as image

¹See, for instance, the ACM 2025 HCXAI workshop proposal at <https://drive.google.com/file/d/182UnoNxuzr0T0ztB9suKnhhNw8YmYbVn/view>

²We prefer the term **AI agent** over **AI assistant** [12], as the latter implies social roles that may be philosophically problematic [7, 10].

³We note that agency does not require possessing mental states, such as those humans have [8, 9].

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classification or risk assessment, AI agents leverage natural language interfaces to interpret prompts, and execute actions via integrated tools, accessing external APIs, search engines, and plugins, while self-improving based on user feedback and inter-agent communication. Importantly, while AI systems, including LLMs, typically *suggest*, AI agents *do*. In this sense, they are akin to new generation, multi-task and multi-system instances of Robotic Process Automation [14]. By interacting with their environment and acting upon internal logic, they embody a genuine form of artificial agency that has long been a central focus of AI research [20].

AI agents: reality of fiction? AI agents are designed to automate routine tasks such as scheduling meetings, finalizing hotel reservations, as well as managing conversations on behalf of human users. Although these systems remain largely aspirational at present, a few development frameworks have already emerged, each offering unique capabilities to enhance automation and user interaction. For instance, OpenAI’s Operator⁴ is engineered to autonomously execute web-based tasks by interacting with graphical elements on webpages via a ‘universal interface for AI.’ Microsoft’s AutoGen⁵ provides an open-source framework for building AI agents that cooperate to solve tasks, focusing on multi-agent orchestration and autonomous workflows within digital ecosystems. Google DeepMind’s Gemini 2.0 Flash Thinking⁶ leverages multimodal reasoning and native tool use—such as integrated search and code execution—to address complex queries. Fully autonomous AI agents remain aspirational, but the recent DeepSeek case highlights that the race toward agentic AI is well underway. In the near term, they may assist only with routine tasks. However, future AI agents could manage job applications, financial planning, and even social interactions.

Human-AI interaction research with AI agents

The rise of agentic AI will reshape human-AI interaction research. Below, we highlight two trends that require attention.

First, while humans directly engage with digital resources—such as webpages, apps, intranet portals, online forums, databases and various AI systems, soon these interactions will be increasingly mediated by personalized AI agents acting on their behalf [12]. This evolution gives rise to a **triadic relation among the human user, their AI agent(s), and the digital resources accessed by them**, including other AI agents or more ‘traditional’ AI systems. In this new paradigm, autonomy is shared: each component possesses a distinct degree of autonomy, expressed in relation to the specific tasks they perform [16, 23]. As a result, it becomes essential to design (1) human-centered interfaces for interacting directly with AI agents, and (2) AI agent-centered mechanisms for them to engage with digital resources. Notably, through interaction, AI agents will reshape digital resources and be reshaped in the process. As a result, while these agents learn and evolve by managing and processing information on behalf of humans, challenges inherent to traditional AI systems, such as lack of transparency, risk of discrimination, and vulnerability to adversarial perturbations, will propagate throughout the triadic relation, requiring the development of novel approaches to manage risk, ensure accountability, and foster trust.

Second, it is reasonable to expect that AI agents will soon be offered as services by major players in the generative AI space, as well as by competitive open-source frameworks. Consumers will simply choose their preferred service provider, select a fee plan, and manage the operations of their personal ‘herd’ of AI agents. Consequently, from a human-AI interaction perspective, **consumer and their personalized AI agents will constitute hybrid agentic systems**, that is, systems emerging from interactions between human users and AI agent enhancing their cognitive, epistemic, and, crucially, agentic capabilities through multimodal and multi-system interactivity. (Traditional AI systems, such

⁴<https://openai.com/index/introducing-operator/>

⁵<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/autogen/>

⁶<https://deepmind.google/technologies/gemini/flash/>

as a medical diagnostics or pricing tools, are typically designed to augment cognitive and epistemic capabilities of their users by sharing predictions, but not agentic abilities.) Then, as AI agents will become increasingly integrated into various sectors of society, these human agent-AI agent (hybrid) systems will shape digital ecosystems at scale, while communicating and interacting with each other, much like shepherds and their cattle transform the natural landscape with pastoralism.⁷ This large-scale agentic hybridization calls for a reexamination of notions of agent identity, accountability, and trust in the context of AI agent-rich environments. Moving away from Heidegger's ideal of 'humanity as shepherd of Being,'⁸ the rise of AI agent will give us the more pragmatic role of 'shepherds of our agentic machines.'⁹

In summary, the rise of AI agents compels us to reexamine our approach to human-AI interactions starting with the human-centered AI paradigm, which has traditionally focused itself on the binary relation between human control over (AI) system automation [24]. Approaches such as complementarity, distributed cognition, and 'AI extenders' offer valuable insights to human-AI agent hybridization [6, 13, 19]. However, it is **the HCXAI framework that can help addressing the rise of AI agents** by providing appropriate explanations for their activities, ensuring accountability across multi-layered and multi-system interactions, and maintaining trust in settings where the interaction between humans and digital resources, e.g., medical AI systems or investment platforms, are mediated by AI agents. To do so, HCXAI has to redirect efforts from interpreting AI system outcomes to explaining actions of agentic AI while keeping the 'human' at the center. The following section outlines three challenges and simple recommendations to adapt HCXAI methods to AI agent-rich environment.

HCXAI research in the age of AI agents: Three challenges and recommendations

I. AI agent activity requires causal and deep explanations

AI agents magnify classical HCXAI challenges, such as the lack of transparency in decision-making and the need to align AI system processes with human values. These systems may optimize unintended objectives, leading to unpredictable or even harmful outcomes. Data used to train them—especially the LLMs underpinning their logical capabilities—remain largely inaccessible, with minimal oversight on how biases propagate through the training pipeline and beyond. As AI agents are designed to autonomously act upon information, this can amplify inequalities and propagate errors manifold, especially when humans and multiple AI agents operate together committing fraud, spreading misinformation, or violating regulations. As a result, it can become difficult to pinpoint responsibility in such hybrid systems: their law-breaking actions may involve accidental combinations of computational errors, random effects, perturbations, or user-instructed fraudulent behavior.

Thus, **explanations for AI agent activities—and those of the human-AI agent hybrid—must be both causal and deep.** By *causal*, we mean that explanations should uncover the underlying decision-making processes that lead to a given agentic action: agency enables interventions on the environment and interventions are at the core of causality.¹⁰ HCXAI research can start integrating methods from causal inference and structural causal models, and counterfactual reasoning [17]. This emphasis on causality may seemingly contrast with traditional AI systems, where explanations

⁷Hybridization happens in human-AI interactions as well [6, 13, 19]. However, traditional AI systems does not have agentic capabilities.

⁸In his *Letter on Humanism*, 1947, Heidegger famously claimed that humanity is not the lord of the beings, but, rather the shepherd of Being ("Der Mensch ist nicht der Herr des Seienden. Der Mensch ist der Hirt des Seins.") Namely, humanity does not control or dominate Being (*Sein*) but rather cares for and listens to it, allowing it to unfold, like a shepherd attends their cattle with care.

⁹A reality that materializes Günther Anders'—a student of Heidegger—pessimistic perspective on our humanity in the age of technology: "[...] we are certainly not 'shepherds of [B]eing.' Far rather we might consider ourselves the 'shepherds of our product- and gadget-world' as a world that needs us, more strikingly than we do ourselves, as servants (e.g., as consumers or possessors)" [1, pag. 281]. This perspective is challenged by the prospect of artificial general intelligence, where AI agents may no longer require human oversight or 'shepherds' to guide their actions.

¹⁰Improving on current frameworks for LLM reasoning traces, such as ReAct [28].

often (but not exclusively) describe statistical correlations in relation to the outcome. However, correlative explanations are still necessary in the context of the relation human user-AI agent-digital resources. In fact, at selected steps of the activity causal chain, we may provide information on the outputs of an AI system that are used by the AI agent to act on the environment. Simply put, human-AI agent-digital resource interactions require substantially augmenting the type of explanations we consider in HCXAI including causality to address agency systematically. (Literature on causality, machine learning and their issues provides a solid starting point [5, 22, 27].) That is why *deep* explanations require reconstructing the full causal chain of an AI agent’s activity, which involves considering (1) appropriate user-dependent explanatory levels, and (2) relevant sub-relations with humans and other systems—i.e., the *who* and *what* of HCXAI in AI agent-rich interactions. For instance, user-dependent explanatory levels may refer *strategic level*, where explanations convey the overall objective guiding the agent, such as minimizing risk in automated trading. The *tactical level* specifies the intermediate decision processes, such as forecasting models that indicate probabilities or trends instead. Finally, the *operational level* focuses on the precise execution details, such as the triggering of stop-loss orders or other specific control measures. Different users access different levels and all explanations describe explicitly the digital resources interacting with the AI agent and any human intervention, supporting audit trails of human-AI agent-AI interactions at scale.

An example is in order. **Human-centered explanations will be key for the improvement of personalized AI agents through user feedback.**¹¹ This will become particularly relevant in consumer-based services, where users must understand whether, how, and when to intervene in their AI agent’s decision-making as part of their ongoing interaction with the system (Much like shepherds tending to their cattle, following our bucolic analogy.) Causal and deep human-centered explanations would then (1) identify and elaborate on stopping events in AI agent activity, such as endless feedback loops, sudden drops in performance, or rule-based triggers (e.g., halting a financial transaction that exceeds a certain risk threshold predicted by another AI system) at different levels, and (2) provide recommendations tailored to the user’s expectations, available resources, and risk appetite. Designing appropriate interfaces will not be an easy task, however. For instance, the frequency of explanation and user feedback would depend on various factors, including the type of AI agent and its operating environment (e.g., automatically creating music vs. triggering pharmacological treatments in a hospital.)

II. Fighting fire with fire: Safeguarding online identity with agentic explanations

The deployment of AI agents introduces new risks in online identity management, necessitating the integration of novel explanation-aware verification capabilities. The challenge for HCXAI lies in promoting explanations as identity verification structures of hybrid human-AI agent systems. These explanations must clearly report on human-initiated actions vs. AI-agent-driven activities, providing a transparent and time-sensitive view of agency distribution within hybrid systems, both for its human users and third parties. Simply embedding in explanations traditional methods, such as CAPTCHA gatekeeping, is unlikely to suffice in a future where human-versus-AI agent recognition systems may necessitate invasive detection techniques, such as behavioral or biometric measures, that raise their own ethical concerns. Here, HCXAI research can intervene by developing explanation-aware identity mechanisms that transparently communicate who—or what—is acting in digital environments. Unlike binary systems like CAPTCHA, real-time, interactive explanations would empower users to understand, modify, or halt a hybrid system’s activities dynamically.

¹¹For instance, even now, systems like ChatGPT solicit user feedback to refine responses. This is an OpenAI-triggered process, however.

But how? Again, an example is due. For instance, designers could consider providing consumer subscribing to their agentic AI service with a **master AI agent** serving as a warranty of online identity, overseeing the actions of other AI agents linked to that user and ensuring that their digital presence remains verifiable. Unlike standard AI agents, master AI agents would operate under stricter requirements, such as cryptographic signatures of their activities, ensuring that every interaction with them can be traced and justified. (After all, every shepherd needs a good cattle dog.) These agents would offer real-time, interactive explanations that clarify the origin and intent of AI-mediated actions, the degree of AI autonomy versus human involvement, and historical accountability through an auditable explanation trail via natural language interfaces. Or, as part of post-hoc evaluation of completed activities, for instance, in professional or social platforms, when a user engages in discussions via AI-assisted communication tools, these master AI agents could generate explanations indicating which parts of the conversation were AI-assisted (either deterministically or probabilistically with ‘artificial agency scores’), ensuring clarity in human-human interactions. In identity-sensitive environments such as digital contracts or content authorship, their use of cryptographically signed logs could further ensuring transparency and control over the identity of human users, AI agents, and other digital resources.

III. Rethinking explainability and trust in human-AI agent-AI interactions

As AI agents will become prominent in digital ecosystems, our understanding of trust and its relation with explainability must be reconceptualized. In fact, trust and explainability will extend to different interactions, including AI agent-AI agent and AI agent-digital resource ones, which traditional trust models—rooted in human cognitive and affective frameworks—and explainability methods struggle to address. Here, HCXAI remains relevant as the goal—despite the prominence of interactions between different systems—is to ensure that AI agent autonomy remains explainable and gives human users reasons to trust these systems. **As a field, HCXAI will provide sought-after methodological guidance**, promoting studies that investigate the effects of casual and deep explanations on (different types of) human users, and the provision of information to them *and* their AI agents to ensure the agent type-dependent trustworthiness of the systems they interact with. Some good news: computer science literature abounds of multi-agent trust(worthiness) and reputation measures based on, for instance, reliability, data integrity levels, and secure communication protocols [21]. Additionally, quantitative models of ‘trust as anti-monitoring’ offer a mental state-independent perspective on trusting in interactions between different systems, including AI agents [15, 25, 26]. Altogether, this program can leverage a precise formalization of trust in AI agent-rich environment and a formalization of its relation with explainability helping advance empirical research on trust in AI and overcoming methodological fragmentation and other long-standing challenges in that field [2].

Conclusions

The integration of AI agents into our digital ecosystem challenges traditional human-centered frameworks, necessitating to consider the perspective of human users, their AI agents, and the digital resources interacting with them. HCXAI can help managing this new perspective implementing causality-aware explanation layers, developing explanation-based identity warranty mechanisms, and helping redesign the explainability-trust relation in AI agent-rich ecosystems. We call for interdisciplinary collaboration to refine these high-level proposals and ensure a still human-centered digital future for our societies, including those who, due to socio-economic barriers, risk being left behind in the AI agent race.

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The Importance of Explainable AI for Gig Workers: A Case for Human-Centered XAI in Gig Economy

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AI-driven decision-making systems operate in the background of gig work platforms, playing a central role in job allocation, performance evaluation, and compensation. However, the opaque nature of these algorithmic systems has posed significant challenges for gig workers in terms of transparency, accountability, and fairness. Existing Explainable AI (XAI) frameworks, developed primarily for traditional domains, fail to adequately address the unique challenges and lived experiences of gig workers. This position paper argues for a tailored approach to XAI in the gig economy, building upon prior research in human-centered XAI (HCXAI). We propose future research directions aimed at developing XAI methods that center the needs and experiences of gig workers, promoting algorithmic transparency, and empowering workers in an AI-mediated labor landscape. By addressing the longstanding challenges of algorithmic opacity in gig work, we can work towards a more equitable and accountable future for this rapidly growing workforce.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Explainable AI, Human-centered AI, Gig Work, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170518

1 INTRODUCTION

The gig economy, characterized by short-term contracts and freelance work facilitated through digital platforms [2], has experienced significant growth in recent years. At the heart of this ecosystem are AI-driven decision-making systems that operate in the background, governing task allocation, performance evaluation, and compensation on platforms such as Uber, DoorDash, Amazon Mechanical Turk, UpWork, Fiverr, etc [30]. While these algorithmic systems play a crucial role in shaping the experiences of gig workers, they often function as opaque "black boxes," leaving workers with little understanding of how decisions that significantly impact their livelihoods are made [31]. This lack of transparency poses significant challenges for gig workers in terms of accountability, fairness, and the ability to contest decisions that may have far-reaching consequences, such as income instability or unfair deactivation [32]. Recent studies have documented how gig workers also experience financial and emotional challenges [33, 34]. Often, the algorithmic control creates a significant "transparency gap" between existing platform designs and the information drivers need to make informed decisions about promotions, fares, routes, and task allocation [29]. Unlike domains such as healthcare or finance, where AI users often have domain expertise and a degree of influence over the systems they interact with, gig workers are largely excluded from the development and deployment of the AI systems that govern their work [39]. This exclusion widens the power asymmetries between gig workers and platforms, further underscoring the need for Explainable AI (XAI) frameworks that cater specifically to the needs and challenges of this unique workforce.

Existing XAI research has primarily focused on developing explanations for AI systems in structured, high-stakes domains, such as medicine or law, where the intended users are often experts with domain knowledge [40, 41]. However, the dynamic, platform-mediated nature of gig work presents a distinct set of challenges that current XAI frameworks are ill-equipped to address. These challenges include asymmetrical power dynamics between workers and platforms, a lack of AI literacy among gig workers, the need for contextualized and real-time explanations in ever-changing work environments, and the pervasive algorithmic control that workers are subjected to, often without a clear understanding

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of how these systems operate [42]. Recent research has responded to these challenges through several innovative approaches. Some worker collectives have begun developing data-driven tools that crowdsource and analyze workers' data to estimate platform practices such as "take rates" – the percentage of rider prices retained by rideshare platforms [1, 37]. In one notable example, a Colorado-based rideshare union collaborated with researchers to develop FairFare, a tool that collected data on over 76,000 trips from 45 drivers over 18 months [37]. This worker-led data collection effort directly contributed to the passage of legislation requiring greater transparency and data disclosure from platforms. Additionally, researchers in CSCW and HCI communities have increasingly examined worker data collectives as a means to advance policy, hold platforms accountable for data transparency, and empower the collective worker voice [1, 29]. These efforts leverage frameworks such as data feminism to design sustainable and power-aware data collectives that address challenges in various gig sectors, including ridesharing, freelancing, crowdwork, and carework. Despite these important developments, fundamental questions remain about designing, governing, and sustaining such data infrastructures. Furthermore, design researchers have examined the impact of design decisions on who gets to design [35].

Despite these challenges, gig workers have developed a critical understanding of the algorithms that shape their work experiences through daily interactions with AI-driven platforms [36, 38]. This critical understanding highlights the gap between AI designers' intended use of algorithms and the actual lived experiences of workers. By studying how gig workers interpret and adapt to these algorithms, researchers can develop XAI frameworks that better align with their needs, provide actionable insights, and mitigate potential harms such as algorithmic bias, wage suppression, and account blocking and deactivation risks. In this position paper, we argue for a new approach to XAI that is specifically tailored to the needs and experiences of gig workers.

Building upon prior research in human-centered XAI (HCXAI) [39], we propose a research agenda aimed at developing worker-centric explanation frameworks that prioritize transparency, agency, and actionable insights. We begin by arguing the critical ways in which XAI for gig work differs from existing approaches. Next, we explore how gig workers' own critical understanding of algorithms can inform the design of explainable systems. Finally, we outline a set of research directions and questions to guide the development of XAI methods that center the needs and experiences of gig workers, ultimately contributing to a more equitable and accountable future for this rapidly growing sector of the economy.

2 WHY XAI FOR GIG WORK IS DIFFERENT

Existing XAI approaches have predominantly been developed for structured, high-stakes domains like healthcare [41] and legal contexts [40], where explanations are typically sought by domain experts. The gig economy presents fundamentally different challenges that require rethinking explanation design:

Asymmetrical Power Dynamics: Gig workers operate within a power imbalance that fundamentally shapes their interaction with algorithmic systems. Unlike professionals in healthcare or finance who typically possess institutional authority and professional standing, gig workers lack bargaining power and formal protections [3], making it difficult to contest opaque AI decisions. For example, when a gig platform like Uber, Lyft or UpWork deactivates a driver's account due to an algorithmic decision, the driver may have limited recourse to challenge the decision or seek reinstatement. Rosenblat and Stark [4] documented numerous cases where ride-hailing platforms terminated drivers based on automated systems with minimal transparency or appeal rights. Similarly, Jhaver et al. [27] found that content creators on freelance platforms frequently experienced unexplained changes in visibility or ranking with no official channels for contestation.

This power asymmetry means that explanations for gig workers cannot simply focus on technical transparency but must explicitly address questions of worker agency and contestability.

Lack of AI Literacy: The gig economy includes workers with widely varying levels of education, technical expertise, and familiarity with algorithmic systems [26, 31]. Many workers do not have technical backgrounds, necessitating explanations that are both interpretable and actionable without requiring specialized knowledge.

For example, a freelance writer on Upwork may find it challenging to comprehend how the platform's algorithm determines their job recommendations or search rankings, limiting their ability to optimize their profile and secure more clients. Prior work found significant variations in AI literacy among platform workers, with many struggling to interpret even basic algorithmic concepts [7, 32]. This heterogeneity in technical literacy makes conventional XAI approaches ineffective, as they typically assume a baseline level of technical understanding that varies widely among gig workers across different platforms.

Dynamic Work Environments: Unlike traditional workplaces with relatively stable conditions, gig work involves ever-changing environments requiring contextualized and real-time explanations [42]. The algorithmic systems governing gig work frequently adapt to changing market conditions, economic and geographic factors, and temporal patterns, creating a constantly shifting landscape for workers [25, 30].

A freelance graphic designer on a gig platform must navigate a constantly shifting landscape of client preferences, market trends, and platform policies, making it difficult to rely on static explanations of the algorithms that govern their work. Wood et al. [30] documented how platform algorithms may change behavior based on localized supply and demand, time of day, or even individual worker history. These dynamic conditions mean explanations must be contextual and adaptive rather than universal and static.

The temporal urgency of gig work creates additional challenges for explanation design. Food delivery workers often have only seconds to decide whether to accept an assignment [23], making lengthy or complex explanations impractical. This urgency requires explanation approaches that can deliver critical information efficiently within the workflow constraints of gig work.

Algorithmic Control: Gig platforms deploy sophisticated control mechanisms that extend beyond simple task allocation to shape worker behavior through incentives, constraints, and surveillance [4, 30]. Workers are subjected to algorithmic nudging, gamification, and monitoring, often without understanding how these systems operate or their cumulative effects.

For instance, a worker on a microtask platform like Amazon Mechanical Turk may be pressured to accept lower-paying tasks or work longer hours due to the platform's reputation system and task allocation algorithms. Prior work [14] documented how these control mechanisms create a form of "digital piecework" where workers must continuously optimize their behavior to algorithmic requirements without fully understanding those requirements.

These control mechanisms can have significant consequences for worker wellbeing and autonomy. Prior work [13, 34] found that opaque performance metrics create anxiety and uncertainty among ride-hailing drivers, who develop elaborate theories and workarounds to navigate algorithmic evaluation systems. Explanations in this context must go beyond individual decisions to illuminate broader patterns of algorithmic management and their effects on worker agency.

These four dimensions demonstrate why conventional XAI approaches are insufficient for gig work contexts. An effective framework must simultaneously address power asymmetries, diverse technical backgrounds, dynamic work environments, and pervasive control mechanisms. This requires moving beyond technical transparency to consider

worker agency, contextual explanations, and collective understanding. The following sections build on these insights to propose a worker-centered XAI framework that addresses these unique challenges.

3 CRITICAL ALGORITHMS AND GIG WORKERS' UNDERSTANDING

Gig workers have developed a critical understanding of the algorithms that shape their work experiences through their daily interactions with AI-driven platforms. Despite the opacity of these systems, workers have learned to recognize patterns in task distribution, payment fluctuations, and ranking systems [31, 38]. This process of algorithmic sensemaking occurs through both individual experience and collective knowledge sharing. Workers actively experiment with platform systems to identify how algorithmic decisions affect their earnings and opportunities. Rosenblat [10] documented how ride-hailing drivers develop detailed mental models of surge pricing patterns by systematically testing different locations and times. Similarly, Wood et al. [30] found that food delivery workers identify temporal patterns in order allocation to maximize their earnings throughout the day. Many workers extend this learning process beyond individual discovery by sharing knowledge through online forums, social media groups, and messaging platforms [36]. These communities collectively decode the "black box" mechanisms that govern their livelihoods. Recent work [9, 11] observed how freelancers on global platforms share techniques for optimizing profile visibility and securing better assignments through keyword strategies and profile adjustments. This critical understanding is significant for Explainable AI because it highlights the gap between AI designers' intended use of algorithms and the actual lived experiences of workers. By studying how gig workers interpret and adapt to these algorithms, researchers can develop XAI frameworks that better align with their practical needs. Rather than generic explanations of algorithmic principles, AI systems should provide actionable insights that allow workers to strategize and optimize their performance while ensuring fair treatment. Workers' existing knowledge reveals what aspects of algorithmic systems they find most consequential. Prior work [15, 22] found that workers often prioritize understanding earnings calculations and assignment systems over other algorithmic functions. This suggests that explanation systems should focus on these high-impact areas rather than technical details that may be less relevant to worker concerns. Furthermore, an explainability framework tailored to gig workers can mitigate potential harms such as algorithmic bias, wage suppression, and account deactivation risks. Research has documented how the opacity of platform algorithms can enable discriminatory practices [16, 28] and gradual reduction of worker compensation [31]. Transparent explanations could help workers identify and contest such practices. Ensuring that workers understand the rationale behind AI decisions is crucial for fostering trust and enabling meaningful contestability. As prior work on XAI [17, 20] suggest, explanations must support not just understanding but also actionable recourse—clear paths for workers to address problems or challenge unfair decisions. Therefore, Explainable AI for gig workers is not merely about technical transparency but about empowering a workforce that heavily depends on AI-driven platforms for economic survival. An effective approach to XAI for gig workers must recognize and build upon workers' existing algorithmic knowledge. This requires a participatory approach to explanation design that includes workers as stakeholders rather than merely end-users. In the following section, we outline a research agenda for developing such worker-centered explanation frameworks.

4 A CALL FOR A NEW STUDY ON XAI FOR GIG WORK

We propose a dedicated research agenda for Gig Work XAI:

- (1) **Developing explanations that prioritize worker agency and understanding** requires moving beyond technical transparency to focus on actionable insights. Drawing from participatory and co design approaches

[18, 19, 21], these frameworks should incorporate worker perspectives from the outset rather than retrofitting explanations to worker needs. This includes investigating what types of decisions workers most need explanations for (e.g., task allocation, pricing, performance evaluation), what level of detail is most useful in different contexts, and how explanations can support not just understanding but also contestation of unfair algorithmic decisions. For example, a worker-centric explanation framework might provide ride-hailing drivers with specific insights about how acceptance rates affect future ride assignments, including concrete actions they can take to improve their position.

- (2) **AI Literacy Interventions:** Studying how different explanation styles impact gig workers' trust, understanding, and autonomy is essential for developing effective XAI systems. This research direction examines how explanations can accommodate varying levels of technical literacy without creating additional barriers to participation in platform work. Potential approaches include progressive disclosure models that provide basic explanations initially with options to access more detailed information, visual explanations that reduce reliance on technical terminology, and peer-learning approaches that leverage workers' existing knowledge-sharing practices [38]. These interventions should be evaluated not just on comprehension metrics but on how they affect workers' ability to make informed decisions about their work.
- (3) **Power-Aware XAI:** Integrating feminist and intersectional approaches to address systemic inequities in AI-driven gig work represents a critical departure from conventional XAI frameworks [42]. This research direction examines how explanation design can acknowledge and potentially rebalance power asymmetries between workers and platforms. This includes investigating how collective explanations could support various groups of workers, and how explanation frameworks might be designed to support regulatory oversight and policy interventions. Power-aware XAI recognizes that explanation is not neutral but can either reinforce or challenge existing power structures in the platform economy.
- (4) **Real-Time, Contextual Explanations:** Ensuring that explanations adapt to gig workers' tasks and environments addresses the dynamic nature of platform work [31, 36, 40]. This research direction explores how explanations can be delivered in ways that align with workers' workflows and decision-making processes. Key questions include how to provide timely explanations for time-sensitive decisions (e.g., whether to accept a ride request), how explanations might adapt to different contexts (e.g., high vs. low demand periods), and how to balance the need for immediate information with more comprehensive understanding. This may involve developing new interaction models for delivering explanations within existing platform interfaces or creating complementary tools that workers can consult during their work.

To advance this research agenda, we propose the following research questions:

- How do gig workers currently interpret and navigate algorithmic decision-making? What mental models do they develop through experience, and how do these models influence their work strategies and decisions?
- What kinds of explanations do gig workers find most useful and actionable? How do factors such as timing, format, level of detail, and actionability affect the utility of explanations in different work contexts?
- How do power dynamics influence the effectiveness of AI explanations for gig workers? How might explanations address or potentially reinforce existing power imbalances between workers and platforms?
- What role does AI literacy play in improving the usability and impact of XAI systems for gig workers? How can explanations accommodate varying levels of technical understanding without creating additional barriers to participation?

Understanding these questions is crucial to developing an XAI framework that aligns with gig workers' needs. A well-designed XAI system can empower gig workers by providing clarity on how AI decisions are made, enabling them to make informed choices, challenge unfair decisions, and optimize their work strategies. Furthermore, ensuring that XAI accounts for power asymmetries and social contexts is essential to fostering equitable working conditions in AI-driven labor markets.

5 CONCLUSION

The gig economy presents unique challenges that demand a rethinking of XAI frameworks. In this position paper, we argued why the existing approaches to explainability fail to address the specific needs of gig workers, who face asymmetrical power dynamics, lack of AI literacy, dynamic work environments, and pervasive algorithmic control. These distinctive characteristics of platform-mediated labor require explanation approaches that go beyond technical transparency. Gig workers have already developed sophisticated understandings of the algorithms that govern their work through daily interactions and collective knowledge sharing. By building on this existing knowledge and prior HCXAI research, we advocate for a worker-centered research agenda that prioritizes explanations that are contextual, actionable, and power-aware. As platform-based work continues to expand globally, worker-centered XAI approaches will only grow in importance. By empowering gig workers with meaningful explanations of the systems that govern their livelihoods, we can work toward a more equitable and accountable future for AI-driven labor markets.

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XAI meets Data-Centric AI: The Need to Explain Data Processing

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Data preprocessing is an essential part of any AI system, as indicated by the current trend of data-centric AI. However, until now, explainability efforts have almost exclusively focused on models. Choices in preprocessing, such as handling missing data, outliers, scaling, and class balancing, and their effects are currently not part of the explanations. If we continue this way, we are left with only a partial understanding of the model's outputs. This transparency deficit creates risks for accountability, fairness, model performance, and more. We argue why we need full pipeline transparency and, as part of that, data preprocessing explainability, even in an age of AutoML and foundational models.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: XAI, explainability, data-centric AI, full pipeline transparency, data preprocessing, human-in-the-loop, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170480

1 Introduction

The model-centric perspective of XAI research. The importance and popularity of explainable AI (XAI) research has increased with the popularity and omnipresence of AI. It addresses critical issues such as transparency for building trust, improving systems, and fulfilling regulatory requirements. However, most, if not almost all, research in the discipline is focused on the comparatively narrow goal of increasing a user's understanding of a trained model.

The case for full pipeline transparency. While researchers have rightly identified the importance of opaque model architectures, the steps leading up to model training, such as data collection, cleaning, engineering, and transformation, are largely disregarded in XAI research and related fields. However, these steps significantly impact the resulting outputs and, therefore, the fairness, trustworthiness, and overall effectiveness of AI systems. The motivational goal of explainability research is to make AI systems more transparent, and these processing steps before model training are an essential part of those systems. An explanation of only the model itself is an incomplete explanation; a genuinely holistic and human-centered approach to XAI must include full-pipeline transparency. This holds particularly true as more and more non-data scientists gain access to AI through libraries, non-code platforms, AutoML systems, and LLMs. The increased access has many benefits, but it also holds risks as users with less educational and foundational knowledge of data science are building systems. The emerging trend toward data-centric AI, which is a reaction to the significance of data quality and engineering in AI systems, also emphasizes this argument.

We, therefore, argue that one necessary next step in XAI research encompasses explaining the effects of preprocessing on model outputs. To design effective, sustainable, and responsible data preprocessing systems, data scientists need to know (1) how large the impact on the resulting model is, (2) what steps might cause adverse effects for individual model outputs, (3) how the model behavior, in addition to model outputs changes, is affected, (4) how preprocessing steps influence each other, and (5) how the selection of an implementation for a step affects the system.

2 The Open Problem in Explainability Research

XAI research has become a large and active field. However, so far, its scope is limited.

XAI Research isolates model explanations. Even extensive surveys with different goals such as taxonomy, meta-analysis, open challenges, comparison, evaluation) almost exclusively cover model explanations. For example, the recent survey by Abusitta et al. [1] covers various approaches to model explainability, but contains neither existing work nor open

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problems regarding other stages of AI. Saranya and Subhashini [12] do an extensive literature review and address future work across many sectors. They identify a deficit in the quality of the data used in research but do not mention explainability work beyond models. Schwalbe and Finzel [14] provide one approach among many to create a taxonomy, a meta-review, and a method review. They state that "the goal of the process is to achieve making an AI system's actions and decisions transparent as well as comprehensibly", but continue to treat the model as the only part of the system, not the many steps leading up to and following the creation of that model. A meta-survey by Saeed and Omlin [9] from 2023 analyzed 73 survey papers from the area of XAI, classifying them into three phases of the AI life cycle: Design, Development, and Deployment. Only three of the covered surveys belong to the design phase, two covering the quality of the data used and one the number of samples a user can inspect and the selection of these samples/explanations. This distribution reveals a research gap between the procurement and selection of data and the model training process.

Bridging the gap between training dataset explanations and model explainability. Training dataset explanations [2] have been a previous step in pursuing full pipeline transparency. They inspect the original training dataset and allow users to judge its properties and the effect on the model outcome. Following that in the data life cycle, the training data is further processed before model training. Depending on the data and model, the extent varies, and with that the effect.

Previous Work. XAI literature reveals little existing research around transparency in data preprocessing.

Dasu and Loh [4] propose evaluating the effect of data cleaning by measuring changes in the statistical properties of the data itself. Statistical distortion reflects how much the process skews the data relative to the achieved glitch improvement. While this can be a helpful perspective on data, it neglects the relationship with the rest of the AI system, hindering full pipeline transparency. The data affects model training, of course, and therefore, statistical distortion affects the model. However, different properties of data and, through them, preprocessing steps interact very differently with different model architectures. Data scaling, for example, is pointless for some architectures but essential to others. In pursuing full pipeline transparency, it is necessary to always look at data, preprocessing, model, and training together.

Gonzalez Zelaya [5] approaches this holistic view by measuring changes in model output. They introduce volatility, which covers the likelihood of a data point receiving a different model output and a learned model to approximate it efficiently. While this approach considers the interplay between preprocessing and model, the change in model output is a very limited source of information. The change for a data sample right along the decision surface and at a maximal distance would weigh the same. Changes in model behavior that do not result in a change of output, i.e., the same result for a different reason, are not considered at all. From the perspective of XAI, however, that is a particularly interesting case as it is similar to a common motivational challenge in the field: Models achieving high accuracy through undesired features or patterns. Additionally, the community has long concluded that no singular approach to model explainability will appropriately cover every circumstance, intent, and user [8]. Why should that be different when explaining other steps of the pipeline?

3 The Path Forward

The movement toward data-centric AI and why it matters. As in XAI, the research on AI has been very focused on models, model architectures, training, and hyper-parameters for a long time, while data and its handling were undervalued [11]. This focus, in conjunction with fixed and limited datasets, hindered the ability of models to transfer from research into practical application, generalize from one problem to another, or achieve the highest possible accuracy

[16]. Data-centric AI focuses on increasing both the quality and quantity of data to make contained information accessible to the model in training. It is also important to avoid unfair, discriminatory, or otherwise harmful systems. Combining model-centric AI and data-centric AI yields optimal results, and they should be combined and developed in conjunction with one another. This development of AI research outlines how XAI, too, could (and should) evolve in the next few years.

The context of process-centric explanations. Yurrita et al. [15] have made the case for process-centric explanations. This perspective tries to overcome the focus of XAI on outcome explanations and include choices made in the process in the explanations. They also make an argument for full pipeline explainability because considering the entire lifecycle is necessary to provide contestability in decision-making processes. We can take inspiration from their design when designing data preprocessing explanations as part of full pipeline transparency. As they derive the explanations from what might be contested, we should derive the content of preprocessing explanations from the information needed for the application scenario. One such application would be the design phase of an AI system, where explanations should reflect the impact of each preprocessing step in a way that describes its usefulness to the system. Yurrita et al. [15] argue that information should cater to decision subjects. Similarly, preprocessing explanations need to take a form that is useful to the target audience, which will be different in different use cases. Lastly, they suggest holistic evaluation protocols. This is also important for preprocessing explanations, which should be measured and evaluated by the process outcome in the context of the full pipeline.

One explanation approach does not fit all. These examples show that one way of explaining preprocessing will not work for all circumstances. This mirrors model-centric XAI research, where it is already established that a broad spectrum of approaches is not simply the symptom of the search for an optimal system but rather a necessity [8]. This line of thought can also be expanded to strengthen our argument for preprocessing explainability in the first place: If different forms of representations, ways of procuring explanations, and metrics for evaluation are needed, depending on the circumstances of the application, why should the model be the only aspect worth looking at for all of them?

Human-centered perspective and context. When developing and applying data preprocessing explanations, we must build on all the existing work and discussion from the XAI and related communities. This means:

- Not regarding each system in isolation, but considering the interaction between data, data preprocessing, model, and application.
- Allowing for human interaction or human-in-the-loop systems for trust and better performance.
- Considering the still present trade-off between accuracy and transparency [1].
- Learning from related research even if it pursues a different goal, such as fairness measures for preprocessing [3].
- Considering transparency in the context of responsible AI, fairness/bias mitigation, accountability, regulatory changes, and more.
- Participating in a discussion on which areas AI should be applied to and where inherently interpretable systems or post-hoc explanation systems are societally responsible.
- Empowering those involved in creating, deploying, and monitoring AI systems instead of reducing flexibility through automation.
- Building inclusive and culturally sensitive AI systems with all voices heard.

Beginning of a topology for preprocessing explanations. In the same way that the model-centric XAI community is structured along a number of dimensions[6], preprocessing explanations can also be designed along several characteristics. According to the use case they solve, they can be classified according to:

- *Design*: intrinsic vs. post-hoc
- *Model Dependence*: model-specific vs. model-agnostic
- *Scope*: local vs. global explanations
- *Data-type*: tabular/relational, text, images, stream data, ...
- *Target Audience*: data scientists, end users, domain experts ...

However, there are still several properties that are generally desirable for all approaches although they might not always be equally achievable. These desired qualities which construct a basis for evaluation can in part be adapted from XAI research. They include correctness, complexity, robustness and more. Nauta et al. [7] provide an overview over these characteristics, their applicability to different approaches, different names used for similar concepts and how to evaluate them.

For preprocessing explanations we suggest a few additional criteria:

- *Model-insight*: How is the model considered in the explanation process? Not at all, model output changes, model internals...
- *Granularity*: What degree of detail is considered in the preprocessing? The whole process, individual steps...
- *Diversity*: What kind of preprocessing can be explained? What are restrictions on input pipelines or steps?
- *Exploration vs. Investigation*: How freely is the user able to investigate? Are individual steps or problems targeted? Or are insights general independent of user preconceptions?
- *Interaction*: Are steps explained in isolation? Is there interaction with other preprocessing steps covered? If so, independent of position in the pipeline?

4 Interaction with Current Trends

Recent trends in AI research have given some users the impression that the challenge of data preprocessing is being solved through end-to-end systems. Large language models (LLMs) seem to suggest that instead of curating data, users can simply feed anything they have to the model in training. If these systems are on the rise, do we still need preprocessing pipelines at all. AutoML systems handle model selection, parametrization, and training for the user to build the optimal system. Since good preprocessing is dependent on the model, how should users still build their own?

So given these trends, do we still need data preprocessing and with it preprocessing explainability?

Democratization of AI through AutoML and LLMs. Recent developments in AI, such as AutoML and generative AI/foundational models/LLMs, have led to huge progress in democratizing access to AI technology and allow users with little to no data science background to use and build models. This positive development contributes to reducing inequalities and allowing more domain expertise to enter the field. Based on these trends, it can seem easy to argue that it becomes less important to pay attention to the individual steps of the process as long as the result is satisfactory, making full pipeline transparency redundant. However, quite the opposite is true for several reasons. As the accessibility of AI increases, the amount of solid foundational skills of the average user decreases. Additionally, the more the field as a whole grows, the harder it becomes to know about all relevant background aspects. That makes it more important to help users understand what is interacting in the full pipeline, not less.

AutoML is a heterogeneous landscape without design for complete understanding. With current AutoML systems, the situation for data preprocessing is quite heterogeneous. Many, especially early, systems do not include any data preprocessing steps, leaving this task up to the user, who might not fully understand the need, process, or implication of the process. It also means once again that data preprocessing happens completely separate from model selection and training, which unintentionally biases the resulting model choice and might limit the best possible result. Other systems do cover data preprocessing to a varying extent. Salhi et al. [10] identify 11 current AutoML platforms that include a subset of data cleaning, integration, reduction, and transformation. None of them have an intended way for the user to understand the data preprocessing that has happened. The commercial platforms usually expose very little of the inner workings to the outside. Due to the nature of AutoML, access to the resulting model is always necessary in some form and while this model may not be interpretable by design or presentation, post-hoc explainability methods exist that can provide insight. With regard to preprocessing, however, there is no implicit need to expose anything to the user, leaving it unclear what the system has or could have done, let alone how. Open source systems, by design, allow the user to modify the code to obtain more information on the process. However, the necessary changes vary widely in complexity and, in any case, require coding skills and a deeper understanding than these systems claim to necessitate. Only one in 11 systems provides the structure to access the resulting preprocessing pipeline. Even starting from that, there is a long way still to fully enabling, instructing, and guiding users to understand this part of the system fully.

LLMs are not on their own the solution to all problems. The most prevalent trend in any subfield of AI currently is the use of foundational models to tackle existing and new problems. While a lot of valuable research and applications have come from these advancements, they also expose several issues. They are neither intrinsically transparent and explainable, nor do we currently have suitable post-hoc methods, beyond asking an LLM to explain itself or another LLM, which is not more reliable than the original output. Even worse, they can contribute to what Sarkar [13] has called the "Illusion of Explanation", leading the user to believe they understand the process when they do not. In terms of accessibility, the natural language interface of LLMs is great for end users, but that is worth nothing if the information content of an explanation is not reliable. We cannot foresee what developments will happen over the next few years and what issues will be resolved. However, we cannot ignore that this technology neglects users who lack the resources or infrastructure to leverage large datasets and complex models, increasing inequalities. This issue is critical for lower and middle-income countries and other areas disadvantaged by structural inequalities. At the same time, these groups face challenges that make data preprocessing more important in traditional systems, such as data quality issues caused by social inequalities, propaganda, and lack of resources available for data collection, as well as transparent system design. Resources needed for effective foundational models also increase the difference between large commercial enterprises and research institutions, non-profits, and open initiatives. Data origin and usage are also usually a topic for discussion, both regarding quality and moral issues for LLMs and similar systems. These are all arguments to still prioritize data quality compared to quantity and not completely neglecting more traditional approaches in the hopes of foundational models solving issues in the future. Data preprocessing is an important part of data quality, and explainability, especially in a human-centered way, is a necessity of the process.

5 Conclusion

Data preprocessing is an essential part of any AI system, as indicated by the current trend of data-centric AI. However, until now, explainability efforts have almost exclusively focused on models. Choices in preprocessing, such as handling missing data, outliers, scaling, and class balancing, and their effects are currently not part of the explanations. If we

continue this way, we are left with only a partial understanding of the model's outputs. This transparency deficit creates risks for accountability, fairness, model performance, and more. We need full pipeline transparency and, as part of that, data preprocessing explainability, even in an age of AutoML and foundational models. The human-centered perspective is as necessary in explaining preprocessing, as it is essential to model-centric XAI. Just like model-centric and data-centric AI complement each other, XAI will yield the best results, when explanations for data, preprocessing, models and more, are used together.

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Exploration of Temporal Aspects of AI Explanations

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As AI systems are increasingly integrated into high-stakes domains such as healthcare, finance, and transportation, the need for Explainable AI (XAI) to foster appropriate human-AI trust and collaboration is more critical than ever. While previous research has examined the interpretability and effectiveness of different XAI methods, the temporal dynamics of AI-generated explanations remain underexplored. This study investigates how temporal constraints influence human understanding and decision making when interacting with AI explanations. Specifically, we examine the impact of explanation timing on user trust, agreement with AI decisions, and response times. Using a controlled user experiment based on Where's Waldo puzzles, we simulate decision-making under time pressure. Participants receive AI-generated statements about Waldo's presence in an image, with some also receiving additional explanations through the Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) framework. In addition, we analyze how AI confidence scores affect user confidence and decision latency. We hypothesize that time constraints may introduce cognitive biases that affect the effectiveness of AI explanations. Our findings will provide valuable insights for designing AI explanations that support users in both time-sensitive and deliberative decision-making contexts.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Philosophical/theoretical foundations of artificial intelligence**; Artificial intelligence; • **Human-centered computing**;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Explainability, Explainable AI (XAI), Human-Centered XAI, Human-AI Interaction, Trust, Decision Making, Time Sensitivity, Presented at the Human-centered Explainable AI Workshop (HCXAI) @ CHI 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15170490

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is used in many different industries and areas of life, making it particularly useful for important decisions in domains like finance, healthcare and transportation [23]. Successful human-AI team collaboration can be extremely powerful. In healthcare, for example, in a team of human caregivers and an AI agent, the AI team member can support by providing direct access to a patient's medical records and proactively recommending treatment plans. At the same time, the human nurse may be better able to interact socially with patients and make health-related decisions. In this way, each team member can support the team's overall functioning and performance (with their competencies). Beyond clinical care, AI is increasingly being integrated into diagnostic imaging, triage systems and operating room workflows, where decisions must often be made under severe time constraints. For example, an AI-assisted radiologist can receive real-time alerts about potentially malignant nodules, helping to prioritize scans that require immediate attention. However, when time is limited, the radiologist may not be able to thoroughly investigate or challenge the AI's reasoning, raising critical issues of trust, interpretability, and accountability under time constraints. In the transportation domain, AI-driven systems can help analyze baggage scans, facial recognition, and passenger risk assessments to detect potential threats in real time. AI can be a beneficial tool for humans in situations

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that require rapid decision-making due to its capacity to process large volumes of data in real time and identify patterns more expeditiously than humans. This is particularly relevant in high-stakes, time-sensitive contexts such as airport security, where prompt decision-making is crucial. For instance, in a scenario where an AI system flags an anomalous object in a scan, the human security officer has only seconds to interpret the alert, verify the threat, and take action.

This challenge is not limited to high-stakes domains. Recent research has shown that even in knowledge work, focused attention spans are shrinking to an average of just six minutes, with frequent context switching and interruptions placing additional strain on human decision-making in AI-enabled environments [28]. As attention becomes increasingly fragmented, the time available to interpret and act on AI output becomes more limited, making the speed and clarity of AI explanations even more critical in everyday settings. Given these considerations, we wonder why the “time dimension” has played such a little role in XAI research so far. Doctors or security personnel do not have unlimited time to make decisions - with or without AI. We all are part of a system where “*time is money*” [18]. In this regard, it would be quite interesting to see how time pressure influences an operator’s decision-making when cooperating with AI systems, as well as if XAI methods would affect this process. Could concise, high-utility explanations help a surgeon quickly verify an AI-recommended diagnosis? Or could an overly complex explanation slow down a TSA agent during a rush hour threat assessment? These are questions that remain underexplored. Consequently, this workshop paper calls for more systematic research in this area and describes an ongoing experiment where we want to answer these questions.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 From Human-AI Collaboration to XAI

Achieving productive human-AI collaboration requires mutual understanding and trust [15, 16, 27]. The European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) mandates transparency in AI-driven decision-making, requiring companies to explain how their algorithms function [29]. Lee and Rich [19] shows that people generally trust algorithmic decisions less than human ones, but this trust can be influenced by various factors, including their social community or even their level of distrust in human systems. However, according to Dodge et al. [8], when users trust an explanation, they are more likely to trust the underlying machine learning (ML) system. Consequently, *Explainable Artificial Intelligence* (XAI) plays a crucial role in enhancing user trust by providing interpretable justifications for AI-generated outcomes, allowing humans to make informed decisions. The primary goal of XAI is to make the reasoning processes of AI models understandable by answering a fundamental question: “Why does an AI system make the predictions it does?” By offering transparency, explanations help users comprehend and trust data-driven ML algorithms. However, despite advancements in XAI, challenges persist, such as the trade-off between accuracy and interpretability, as well as the use of abstractions to enhance explanation clarity [12, 13].

While XAI methods can help mitigate the black-box nature of AI systems [4], a crucial question remains: “How do users respond to these explanations?”. Human factors introduce unanticipated and unintended consequences, even in well-designed information systems [6]. The effectiveness of AI explanations is influenced by multiple factors, including a user’s domain expertise, time constraints, and cognitive or perceptual biases. However, existing research largely overlooks how explanations interact with users’ situational information processing—the ability to assess and act on available information in real-time—particularly under time pressure.

2.2 Human-Centered XAI

Explainable Artificial Intelligence aims to enhance the transparency and interpretability of AI-driven decisions to the user. Adadi and Berrada [1] provides a comprehensive classification of explanation methods based on different levels of insight like complexity, scope, and model dependency, distinguishing between global and local interpretability or differentiating between model-specific [11, 20] and model-agnostic techniques, like the post-hoc methods Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME) and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [24, 25]. However, a key question remains, essential not only for user understanding but mainly for fostering active engagement with the decisions-making process: "What additional information should XAI model provide to enhance a supportive and human-centered interaction?". A shift towards human-centered XAI (HCXAI) has been proposed by Ehsan et al. [10], emphasizing the need to focus on human users and stakeholders rather than solely on algorithmic transparency. This perspective advocates for a co-evolution of technical advancements and an understanding of human cognitive factors, as demonstrated in a case study on an explanation system for non-technical end-users. Similarly, Liao and Varshney [21] argues that HCXAI should be studied as an **interaction problem**, highlighting that the interpretability of explanations is inherently a human-centric property.

The fundamental challenge in XAI remains the trade-off between comprehensibility and fidelity. Simplified explanations may be easier to understand but risk misrepresenting the underlying model, while highly technical explanations, although accurate, may be difficult for non-expert users to comprehend [2]. Addressing this challenge is crucial for designing effective XAI systems that balance clarity with precision in high-stakes decision-making contexts. Bansal et al. [3] found that trust in AI varies depending on contextual factors, such as the perceived competence of the AI system and the clarity of its explanations. Similarly, Yeomans et al. [31] observed that people tend to distrust automated recommender systems compared to human recommendations, particularly in highly subjective domains such as predicting which jokes people will find funny. This distrust persisted even when the AI system outperformed human predictions. In contrast, Logg et al. [22] demonstrated that individuals often exhibit a preference for algorithmic predictions over human expert judgments in domains such as music popularity, romantic matches, and other outcome-based predictions. Furthermore, Dietvorst et al. [7] found that people are more likely to rely on an algorithm's predictions when given the ability to make minor modifications rather than accepting them as-is. A growing body of empirical research has explored whether and how different AI explanations influence human decision-making and trust in AI systems. However, the role of time constraints in shaping these dynamics remains under-researched.

2.3 Time pressure on Decision Making

Cognitive psychology has long examined the effects of time pressure on decision-making, particularly in high-stakes environments. Research indicates that time limitations often lead to cognitive biases, reliance on heuristics, and reduced analytical reasoning [17]. Under time constraints, decision-makers may engage in satisficing—opting for the first satisfactory solution rather than the optimal one. Within the domain of XAI, studies have examined how the timing of explanations affects user decision-making. Bansal et al. [3], Yin et al. [32] found that immediate AI explanations can improve decision efficiency but may also lead to over-reliance on AI-generated outputs. Conversely, Buçinca et al. [5] highlighted that users given more time to process explanations tend to engage in deeper cognitive reasoning, which can either increase or decrease agreement with AI recommendations, depending on the context.

More recently, Rosbach [26] investigated how time pressure and XAI methods influence confirmation bias in clinical decision support systems. In their study, pathologists were asked to estimate the percentage of tumor cells in different

images. The results revealed that 45% of participants exhibited a predisposition to confirmation bias. However, contrary to expectations, this bias was not significantly influenced by time pressure conditions [26]. Despite these findings, research on how users process AI explanations under strict time constraints remains limited, particularly in scenarios requiring rapid decision-making. Our work builds on these prior studies by examining how time constraints impact the effectiveness of AI explanations, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of trust calibration in human-AI interactions.

3 Investigating Time Pressure in XAI-Supported Decision Making

Analyzing the related work reveals a lack of research into the temporal aspects in understanding XAI methods. Therefore, this paper aims to explore how time pressure and XAI methods affect human-AI collaboration in decision tasks. Specifically, we want to examine the following research question:

What are the effects of time pressure on human-AI collaboration in decision tasks?

To evaluate this research question, we will conduct an online survey. Since we want to assess a large group of users that are not experts in domains such as health or airport security, we introduce a proxy task. Participants are presented with a series of picture puzzle images from the *Where's Waldo?* [14] series. Participants are provided with a statement on whether an AI thinks *Waldo* is visible in the image and are asked if they agree or disagree with this statement (see Figure 1). Thereby, we will distinguish between the following conditions:

- **Baseline** In the baseline condition, participants will only be presented with the picture and a corresponding AI decision output as described above.
- **LIME Output** We will provide artificially created LIME output in addition to the image and the AI's decision. For each of the images and the corresponding AI decisions, we will create believable LIME output that helps participants in their decisions.
- **AI Confidence** In addition to the image and the AI's decision, we will add confidence values that tell the participant how certain the AI is about its prediction. We will vary between high (89%) and low (41%) confidence.
- **Lime Output and AI Confidence** In this condition, participants will be supported with both the concepts of LIME output and AI confidence.

These four conditions will be utilized as a between-subjects factor. As a within-subjects factor, we will include the factor of time pressure. In one condition, participants will have unlimited time to inspect the image and reason about their decision. In the time pressure condition, participants will have only a couple of seconds to decide whether they comply with the AI's suggestion (indicated by a blue progress bar, see Figure 1). Thereby, we will present participants with multiple combinations of Waldo images and AI decision outputs in each setting to represent all quadrants of a confusion matrix (i.e., true/false positives, true/false negatives). This setting, provided we can reach a suitable number of participants (we aim for N=400), will then allow us to precisely investigate how time pressure influences various decision-making processes in combination with XAI methods, uncertainty information, the role of true/false positives, etc. To identify suitable timings for our time-pressure condition, we have conducted a pilot study. Here, each Waldo image was presented to study participants, and we measured how much time it took them to find Waldo within this picture. We decided to utilize the 25% percentile of all these timings as the maximum time for the progress bar. In other words, only one out of four study participants would come to a true decision considering the presented time pressure, which will require participants to use their gut feeling and comply/reject the AI's decision under uncertainty,

Fig. 1. Participants will be presented images from the "Finding Waldo" series with variations of AI output, i.e., whether an AI has identified Waldo in the images or not. In multiple conditions, we will include decision support such as LIME (right) or AI confidence. Most importantly, our study will investigate the effect of these methods in situations where operators have to perform under time pressure (represented by the blue progress bar (left)).

considering the true image, the presence/absence of supporting methods such as Lime or Confidence value. To account for potential biases, (1) no decision output will be pre-selected, and (2) when the progress bar runs out, the image will be blurred out.

For each decision, we will measure (1) how long it takes a participant to reach a decision, (2) whether they comply with the AI suggestion, and (3) how they trust and accept the AI system. Therefore, we will utilize standardized scales for trust [9] and acceptance [30] after each condition (i.e., evaluating the overall system with and without time pressure as within subjects with different levels of support as between-subjects variables).

4 Expected Results and Conclusions

While we expect to mainly confirm existing results in the scenarios where participants do not face time pressure, we hypothesize that:

- **H1:** Under time pressure, participants will significantly more often comply with AI suggestions independent of the underlying ground truth.
- **H2:** This effect will be stronger when LIME output or AI confidence information is shown.
- **H3:** The combination of LIME output and AI confidence information will yield an interaction effect concerning the underlying ground truth, leading to significantly more correct decisions.

Provided our results support these hypotheses, future work could explore whether the use of other explanation methods leads to different results, such as different effects on response times. Future work could investigate how the setup of this work could be applied to real-world applications such as medical images or monitoring of safety-critical settings. Presumably, our findings will have significant implications for the design of human-AI collaboration in real-life settings.

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